

European Research Data Landscape

Deliverables D3.2, D4.2 and D5.2

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VISIONARY
ANALYTICS

Data Archiving and Networked Services

DANS

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1. INTRODUCTION

The **general objective** of this study is to provide a detailed characterisation of the research data ecosystem in the European context, covering the EU Member States, Horizon 2020 Associated Countries (AC) and the UK. It aims to help the EC in developing more targeted policies and support actions to make FAIR and open data practices more mainstream. The results and recommendations stemming from the study will serve as an important input into shaping the future development of EOOSC. This is to be achieved through a set of **Specific Objectives** covering the following:

1. To collect data on data production and consumption by scientific disciplines and relevant sub-disciplines
2. To collect and analyse information on data deposition practices, depending on the data typology and volume
3. To collect data on the level of maturity with respect to FAIR data implementation by scientific discipline and relevant sub-disciplines, using this data to identify trends, commonalities and major disparities across disciplines to characterise European science system
4. To assess the responsiveness and readiness of research data repositories in terms of the implementation of FAIR principles, including certifications

To address the Specific Objectives, the study's data collection and analysis activities focused on two main groups of stakeholders – researchers (as producers, consumers, and depositors of data) and research data repositories. The coverage of the study is as follows:

- **Geographically**, the study covers all EU MS, the UK, and all Horizon 2020 Associated Countries (AC).
- Regarding **scientific disciplines**, the study looks at the Fields of Science (FOS) classification provided in the Frascati Manual. The analysis is carried out at the first level (6 categories) with data also provided for individual sub-disciplines at the second level (41 categories) of the classification.
- In terms of **time**, the study aims to look at the current situation, asking researchers and repository managers about their most recent practices, in order to capture the most up to date snapshot of the current research data landscape. Therefore, when asking researchers about their practices, we pay special attention to the most recent / current researchers' activities carried out prior to or during the survey. Where relevant, we also inquired about general practices.
- **Thematically**, the study covers the following issues:
 - the scope and characteristics of research data production

- the scope and characteristics of research data consumption
- research data depositing practices
- maturity of research data in terms of the FAIR framework
- responsiveness and readiness of research data repositories to implement FAIR principles

This report combines three deliverables (D3.2, D4.2, and D5.2), as they are significantly linked, and describes the results of the study in full. Chapter 2 briefly describes the methodology used in the study, while Chapters 3 to 5 present the findings of the individual study tasks. Chapter 3 looks at research data production, reuse, and depositing practices on the basis of the data collected through a researcher survey. Chapters 4 and 5 use look into FAIR practices through researcher survey data and the F-UJI assessment tool to understand the prevalence of FAIR practices among researchers. Chapter 6 assesses the FAIRness of research data repositories by using research data repository survey data, employing individual case studies, and using the F-UJI tool. Finally, Chapter 7 summarizes policy recommendations.

2. METHODOLOGY OVERVIEW

2.1. KEY STUDY QUESTIONS

The study focuses on three core areas:

- Describing researchers' practices in terms of research data production and reuse (Chapter 3)
- Analysing research data depositing practices (Chapter 3)
- Assessing the maturity of data FAIRness (Chapters 4 and 5)
- Assessing the use FAIR in research data repositories (Chapter 6)

All these issues are interlinked. Research practices have implications for how FAIR data are, and the supply of services by research data repositories and their adherence to FAIR principles affect the characteristics of the available research data.

Two – country and FOS – categories serve as the basis for breaking down the analysis of collected data on research data production, consumption, and depositing practices, as well as for FAIRness assessment. In addition, the survey of researchers enabled analysing the relationships between researcher career stages, the types and volumes of data produced and research data depositing practices by researchers. Therefore, during the analysis we look not only at the national and FOS characteristics, but also at the characteristics of the produced data in order to understand how they affect the individual researchers' behaviour.

Below we list the specific questions that the study addresses.

Table 1. Key study questions

Topic	Question
Data production practices	What are the types and size of data produced? What is the volume of data produced? What are data production standards? What are the conditions for sharing? Where is research data stored?
Data consumption practices	What are the types of data consumed? What is the quantity of data consumed? What are the sources of data, and conditions of access and reuse?
Data depositing practices	Where are data deposited? Who takes responsibility for data preservation? What are the conditions and costs of depositing? What is the role of data preservation standards and norms? What are the scopes of depositing? What is the notion of 'trusted/trustworthy' data repository? What is the time horizon for depositing research data? What is the effect of data size, generation frequency, and access and reuse conditions on deposition preferences? What is the effect of expected conditions of access and reuse on deposition practices?
Maturity of FAIR data implementation	What is the current level of awareness about the FAIR principles among scientific disciplines and sub-disciplines? What is the role of standards in FAIR practices and role of FAIR in relation to research data sharing? How frequently do researchers in different disciplines and relevant sub-disciplines engage in FAIR-related practices? What are the gaps and needs for implementing FAIR principles? What support is needed in FAIRification process?
Research data repositories and FAIR data	What are the characteristics of repositories? What is the uptake of identifiers by repositories? What services are provided by repositories? What are the operating models of repositories? How do repositories manage data?

Source: own elaboration based on the tender specifications.

2.2. DATA COLLECTION AND ANALYSIS METHODS

The study used a number of data collection and analysis methods, including desk research, surveys, and case studies.

Desk research was used to inform the development of the data collection tools (e.g. survey questionnaires), identify information on the context of this study, comparing the findings with those in other studies on similar topics (e.g. there have been numerous surveys and assessment activities undertaken to evaluate the current landscape regarding FAIR data awareness, practice, and maturity). There have also been several studies to assess the availability of relevant FAIR-enabling research infrastructures and repositories. For desk

research, we used a variety of resources, including studies and reports prepared for the European Commission, relevant Working groups or other relevant parties, academic literature, and databases (e.g. re3data).

Surveys of researchers and research data repositories helped to collect data on the practices related to research data and perceptions of these target groups. The surveys were implemented in two stages (piloting and the main survey). The tables below show the statistics on the survey distribution.

Table 2. Researcher survey distribution statistics

Stage	Start date	No. of individual invitations	Complete responses*	Partial responses*	Total responses
Pilot**	2021 10 29	6,426	45	18	63
Main survey**	2021 11 26	833,756	11,680	3,323	15,003
TOTAL	-	840,182	11,725	3,341	15,066

* - Complete responses include those, who answered at least core questions. It should be noted, that 11,077 of them also responded to the whole survey (core and additional questions). Partial responses are those, who responded at least on the first key question on data reuse. ** - In this row we use data from piloting of the two structures alternative to the one selected. Final survey row includes responses from piloting the structure use for the final survey

Table 3. Research data repository survey distribution statistics

Stage	Start date	No. of individual invitations	Complete responses*	Partial responses*	Total responses
Pilot	2021 10 29	28	6	1	7
Main survey	2021 11 29	2,244	205	104	309
TOTAL	-	2,272	211	105	316

Note: these numbers do not include the first stage of piloting, since it may need additional work in connecting to the core survey dataset. * - Complete responses include those, who responded to the whole survey. Partial responses are those, who responded at least on the first question on the country.

The closing date of the survey was the 2022 02 17. By that time, there were 17,027 answers in the researcher survey, out of which 11,083 completed the whole questionnaire and 5,944 dropped answering the questionnaire and did not reach the end.

In order to ensure the quality of the data the following steps were taken:

- Only the respondents who answered the first key question (“Do you use data made available by researchers outside your research team in your research activities?”)

were kept in the analysis. This resulted in the elimination of 1,949 respondent answers leaving 15,078 respondents who answered the researcher' survey.

- There were 1,566 respondents who spent less than 5 minutes filling out the questionnaire. We looked closer to the key questions, whether this could be possible. Analysis of the responses showed that many of those respondents either abandoned the survey early or did not reuse/produce data, making the survey shorter for them. We have thus removed responses under five minutes that both reuse and produce data and responded not only to core, but to additional questions as well. These responses were removed.
- We checked whether respondents did not rush through the survey by clicking on the same response every time (survey straight lining). In the dataset, we found 58 such cases. We took a deeper analysis of these responses and decided to delete 8 of them from the analysis due to the short time spent filling the survey and answers to other questions.
- We looked into potential duplicates by checking respondent primary/secondary country and FOS, age, role in research, contact information and whether the researcher produces and reuses data. This exercise showed a single case of duplication with some variation in response, thus, both instances were removed.
- The open questions were checked for nonsensical letter combinations. However, answers to open questions did not lead to the elimination of any respondent.

After additional cleaning for the final researcher survey dataset consists of 15,066 answers, out of which 11,077 are complete responses (covering both core and additional questions). Research data repository survey data cleaning did not eliminate responses.

Data FAIRness assessment was implemented using automated F-UJI tool, which enables the systematic assessment of the FAIRness of research datasets in data repositories based on clearly defined practical tests. The tool adheres to existing web standards and persistent identifier (PID) resolution services best practices and utilises external registries and resources to automatically assess the FAIRness of a given dataset based on aggregated metadata. This includes metadata embedded in the data (landing) page, metadata retrieved from a PID provider (e.g. DataCite content negotiation) and other services (e.g. re3data). It then provides assessment against each of the 16 FAIRsFAIR Data Object Assessment metrics. A pass/fail result is also provided for each metric. Based on the results of the systematic assessment, a score for each of the high-level FAIR principles is provided. The scores are based on the pass/fail results for each metric.

We have employed the use of F-UJI tool in two of the Tasks. In Task 4 we assessed 31 repositories with 7,827 datasets, and in Task 5 – 200 units (199 repositories and 1 artificial unit covering data objects without clear deposition outlet) with 18,338 datasets.

Six **case studies** were carried out to shed more light on the specific aspects and factors related to the FAIRification of the repositories. The case studies serve as a qualitative

supplement to the quantitative data analysis based on the survey of the repositories which, is not able to provide exhaustive information for proper assessment and comparison of different data repositories against the FAIR principles and overall data storage, curation and sharing systems. Case studies mainly involve desk research and interviews, where the research unit is an individual research data repository.

Data analysis and synthesis covered both quantitative and qualitative data analysis methods. Their combination allows ensuring a more in-depth understanding of researchers practices and FAIR maturity. However, the main method was quantitative as the core of the collected data comes from survey closed survey questions. More specifically, we used descriptive statistical analysis, graphical analysis, and statistical testing based on 95% confidence intervals. Table below provides some specifics.

Table 4. Quantitative data analysis

Method	Scope of application	Questions addressed
Descriptive statistical analysis	Estimation of descriptive indicators, such as the prevalence of types of produced data or depositing costs per scientific sub-discipline or country.	Granular information on the production, consumption, and depositing of data, overview of FAIR maturity and data from the research data repositories
Graphical analysis	Visual demonstration of the situation regarding the production, consumption and depositing of research data using figures. They help to better depict differences across groups of respondents (e.g. using column or bar charts) or the key selected answers (e.g. using heatmaps).	Granular information on the production, consumption, and depositing of data, overview of FAIR maturity and data from the research data repositories, variation among the difference respondent groups, cross-tabulation of responses to different questions
Statistical tests	Method for testing hypotheses using statistical models when data is sufficient. We have tried using chi-square test to determine the statistical significance in difference among responses from different groups of respondents. However, it proved that due to a large sample size the p-values tend to be small, even if differences in responses are minor, limiting the use of such tests. Therefore, we have opted to assess confidence intervals at 95% level, to estimate the range of true values for the population of a given group.	Extent of differences between the groups in terms of their responses to survey questions

Source: compiled by the study team.

For the quantitative analysis we have also grouped researchers according to the primary country of their affiliation and their primary FOS. We did this due to the following reasons:

- Data at the individual country and second-level FOS produced in a number of cases, with a low number of responses, grouping similar countries paints a more reliable picture.
- The numbers of individual countries and second-level FOS are high, making the analysis too granular, even in cases, where the number of responses at a country and second-level FOS are sufficiently high.

However, data at these more granular levels are also available, ensuring that specific cases can be studied.

Table 5. Respondent groups

Category	Grouping	Reasoning
Fields of science	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Agricultural Sciences • Engineering and Technology • Humanities • Medical and Health Sciences • Natural Sciences • Social Sciences 	This categorisation corresponds to the standard classification of the first-level FOS, exhaustively covering all second-level FOS.
Countries	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Associated Countries with higher investment in R&D (AC1: Turkey, Israel, Iceland, Norway, Switzerland, Faroe Islands, the UK) • Associated Countries with lower investment in R&D (AC2: Albania, Armenia, Bosnia & Herzegovina, Georgia, North Macedonia, Moldova, Montenegro, Serbia, Ukraine) • EU13 countries (Bulgaria, Croatia, Cyprus, Czech Republic, Estonia, Hungary, Latvia, Lithuania, Malta, Poland, Romania, Slovakia, Slovenia) • EU14 countries (Austria, Belgium, Denmark, Finland, France, Germany, Greece, Republic of Ireland, Italy, Luxembourg, the Netherlands, Portugal, Spain, Sweden) • Other • Group 1 (G1) - Northern Europe (Sweden, Finland, Denmark, Lithuania, Latvia, Estonia) • Group 2 (G2) - North Western Europe (Ireland, Netherlands, Luxembourg, France, Belgium) 	This classification takes groups countries according to their relation to the EU (old vs. new Member States, Associated Countries). This also partly (though not perfectly) captures broader differences in economies and innovation systems within the EU. Associated Countries are separated according to their R&D investment, since this may reflect important variation in research practices and resources available. Finally, we also indicate a separate group for respondents, whose primary country of affiliation does not fall under any of the countries of interest to the study. The number is low; therefore, we did not remove it.

	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Group 3 (G3) - South Western Europe (Spain, Portugal, Malta, Italy) • Group 4 (G4) - Central Europe (Slovakia, Poland, Hungary, Germany, Czech Republic, Austria) • Group 5 (G5) - South Eastern Europe (Slovenia, Romania, Greece, Cyprus, Croatia, Bulgaria) • Associated Countries with higher investment in R&D (AC1: Turkey, Israel, Iceland, Norway, Switzerland, Faroe Islands, the UK) • Associated Countries with lower investment in R&D (AC2: Albania, Armenia, Bosnia & Herzegovina, Georgia, North Macedonia, Moldova, Montenegro, Serbia, Ukraine) • Other 	<p>expenditure criterion also broadly (even if not fully) reflects the geographic differences.</p>
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Source: compiled by the study team.

A caveat must be made regarding the issue of data representativeness. The challenge here is assessing whether the sample of responses reflects the population well. The key issues we faced were:

- Representativeness in terms of countries. Countries with lower populations also have fewer researchers, meaning that their sub-sample would have larger margins of errors. We see this in the data, when we look at the demographics of the researcher sample, with some countries being represented by few respondents.
- Representativeness in terms of fields of science (FOS). Similarly, to the issues in terms of data distribution among countries, some of the second-level FOS have relatively few respondents.
- Representativeness in terms of familiarity with open science and FAIR. It is possible, that those researchers who have some knowledge of open science would be more inclined to respond to the study. A majority of researchers was also identified using openly accessible papers they published, which makes it more likely, that the selection is not fully random. Therefore, it may be that the results are somewhat positively biased.

Quantitative data provides the main evidence for the study, but qualitative data analysis provides complementary data. We are using qualitative content analysis, however, to a more limited extent than the full-scale in-depth analysis, due to the needs that emerged during the study. The key needs where:

Comparing the data and results with those of other studies, which needed more manual than automated work.

Extracting insights from data that survey and interview respondents provided. The study was mostly aimed at closed, therefore, the amount of qualitative data was significantly reduced, also limiting the relevance of automation in response analysis. Therefore, we approached qualitative data analysis based on the needs to better understand individual questions or extract arguments provided by respondents. To this end we:

- Determined the material to be analysed for the specific questions (i.e. write-in options)
- Analysed the entries by categories they could be assigned to (e.g. whether they are frequent or whether they provide a more in-depth understanding)
- Analysed the material to serve as illustrations
- Selected, interpreted, and provided the responses with illustrative relevance for the discussions in question

2.3. RESEARCHER DEMOGRAPHICS

Looking at the FOS, we see that the most represented fields are from the Natural Sciences, Engineering and Technology, Medical and Health Sciences, and Social Sciences, with Agricultural Sciences and Humanities being represented significantly less. Figure 1 below shows the distribution of the respondents by first level FOS. The chart on the left represents distribution of all respondents who participated in the survey while the one on the right shows the distribution of the respondents who answered the whole core part of the questionnaire. Importantly, while there was interdisciplinarity in researchers' activities and affiliations in multiple countries, we account for the primary FOS and country to facilitate the analysis. The interdisciplinarity issue could be explored in later studies using the same data.

Figure 1. Share of respondents by their primary FOS (first level)

Source: own elaboration based on unweighted researchers' survey data. N all = 15,066, N core = 11,725. Note: respondents to the core survey is a smaller sample indicating those who did not drop the survey until answering at least the key segment of the survey.

Looking at the second-level of FOS (see Table 6), we see that there is variation among second-level disciplines in terms of responses received, even within individual first-level FOS. The most represented second-level FOS are biological sciences, electrical engineering, electronic engineering, information engineering, and economics and business.

Table 6. Number of respondents by their primary fields of science (second-level)

First-level FOS	Second-level FOS	All respondents	Only respondents who answered the core part of the questionnaire
Natural Sciences	Mathematics	469	341
	Computer and information sciences	340	278
	Physical sciences	926	762
	Chemical sciences	507	398
	Earth and related environmental sciences	909	735
	Biological sciences	1,291	1,015
	Other natural sciences	112	85
Engineering and Technology	Civil engineering	352	281
	Electrical engineering, electronic engineering, information engineering	1,116	893
	Mechanical engineering	428	340
	Chemical engineering	182	129
	Materials engineering	277	221
	Medical engineering	104	84
	Environmental engineering	250	205
	Environmental biotechnology	19	15
	Industrial Biotechnology	35	24
	Nano-technology	69	48
	Other engineering and technologies	494	388
Medical and Health Sciences	Basic medicine	354	262
	Clinical medicine	951	689
	Health sciences	797	601

	Health biotechnology	167	135
	Other medical sciences	336	238
Agricultural Sciences	Agriculture, forestry, and fisheries	303	239
	Animal and dairy science	126	99
	Veterinary science	74	54
	Agricultural biotechnology	92	73
	Other agricultural sciences	179	141
Social Sciences	Psychology	406	333
	Economics and business	1,127	886
	Educational sciences	444	345
	Sociology	287	222
	Law	75	52
	Political Science	183	143
	Social and economic geography	132	105
	Media and communications	117	91
	Other social sciences	376	286
Humanities	History and archaeology	151	120
	Languages and literature	255	189
	Philosophy, ethics and religion	67	49
	Art (arts, history of arts, performing arts, music)	70	45
	Other humanities	115	85

Source: own elaboration based on unweighted researchers' survey data. N all = 15,064, N core = 11,724.

As shown in Figure 2, geographically, there are several countries represented better than others, especially Italy, Germany, and France from the EU Member States. From other non-EU countries, researchers from the UK and Turkey are the most represented, Figure 2 below shows detailed data for each country. While FOS and country of primary affiliation are the main breakdowns for the analysis, we have also included other questions on the demography of respondents:

- Type of institution of primary affiliation
- Respondent's age group and career stage
- Most common role in the research team

In terms of institutional affiliation (see Figure 3), the majority of respondents primarily work in public sector organisations, such as public universities, followed by public research institute / laboratory / another public organisation.

Figure 2. Number of respondents by country of primary affiliation

Source: own elaboration based on unweighted researchers' survey data, N all = 15,066, N core = 11,726.

Figure 3. Number of respondents by type of primary affiliation institution

Source: own elaboration based on unweighted researchers' survey data, N all = 15,070, N core = 11,727.

As shown in Figure 4, in terms of age, the distribution of respondents is centred around 26-65. The fact that many of the respondents are already older is also reflected in the career stage of respondents, with over a third being R3 (established researchers) and over a third being R4 (leading researchers) stage (see Figure 5).

Figure 4. Number of respondents by age group

Source: own elaboration based on unweighted researchers' survey data, N=11,727.

Figure 5. Share of respondents by career stage

Source: own elaboration based on unweighted researchers' survey data, N=11,727.

Finally, as Figure 6 shows, most respondents are researchers, with others being research managers, principal investigators or research managers, with more technical roles being represented significantly less.

Figure 6. Number of respondents by most common role in the research team

Source: own elaboration based on unweighted researchers' survey, N= 11,724.

3. RESEARCH DATA PRODUCTION, REUSE, AND DEPOSITING PRACTICES

This Chapter looks into the data on researchers' practices related to their data production, reuse, and depositing practices and activities. It also serves as a background before the discussion on FAIR data in Chapter 4.

3.1. DATA VOLUMES: HOW MUCH RESEARCH DATA IS PRODUCED AND WHERE DOES IT GO?

Box 3-1. Key findings on data volumes

- Around half of the respondents are not aware of the volume of data (in bytes and number of datasets) they produce or reuse.

- The majority of researchers tend to produce up to 10 GB of data, whether that would be the size of the separate dataset or the overall volume of data they reused or produces in their current/ latest research.
- The number of distinct research datasets is usually up to 10 datasets, both in the case of data production or reuse.
- Researchers in Social Sciences seem to produce smaller datasets (mainly up to 100MB) compared to other FOS.
- A larger share of researchers in Natural Sciences (than in other FOS) produce datasets over 1 TB.
- Career stage and primary affiliation of the researchers do not have a clear relationship with the volumes of produced and reused data.

To assess research data volumes, collected survey data were analysed from three perspectives:

- The size of a dataset produced/reused in the current/latest research activity;
- The number of distinct usable datasets produced/reused in the current/latest research activity;
- The overall volume of produced/reused data in the current/latest research activity. This question in the survey was open. Respondents could choose the size of the unit of measurement (MB, GB, TB, PB) and indicate the volume manually. For analysis, responses were grouped into intervals. Researchers who indicated a unit of measurement but who could not specify a size were assigned to the category "do not know/cannot answer or specify".

3.1.1. Volumes of produced research data

Over half (54%) of the respondents do not know or cannot answer what is the approximate size of the typical dataset. However, out of those who are aware of the size, over a third (33%) of respondents produce 1-100 MB size datasets and slightly less than a third produce 1-10 GB size datasets (see Figure 7). In general, around 70% of respondents who indicated the size of a typical dataset tend to produce datasets up to 10 GB.

Figure 7. Approximate size of typical produced dataset by a researcher or their team in the latest/current research activity (share of respondents)

Source: own elaboration based on unweighted researchers' survey, N = 10,972, do not know/cannot answer = 5,682. Note: percentages were calculated excluding "Do not know/ cannot answer or specify" answers.

Box 3-2. Estimating the total amount of research data produced in the studied countries

As an exercise to estimate the total volumes of data produced across the EU, we have extrapolated from the collected data. This is just an exploration of the data, and the weighting accuracy is limited. However, it may provide insight into the overall research data landscape. Based on the responses, we calculated the volumes of data produced by each respondent who answered the question about the total amount of research data produced in their current/latest research activity. The approach to calculation took the following steps:

1. We have used the latest available Eurostat data to identify the number of researchers (headcount) in the countries covered by the study¹. Certain countries were excluded from further extrapolation, as Eurostat did not provide the relevant data².
2. Using the responses (N = 6,340), we:
 - a. Excluded respondents who selected the 'do not know / cannot answer' option.
 - b. Calculated the total amount of data produced by respondents (number of respondents selecting a specific data volume range X the average value of that data volume range)
 - c. Calculated the average amount of data produced by one respondent in each country by dividend the sum from step 2.b by the number of

1 Data from 2019 for all countries except CZ, DE, HR, PT, SK, RS, TR (data from 2020) and FR, IS, UK (data from 2018).

2 These are AI, AM, FO, GE, IL, MD, TN, UA.

respondents who selected a specific data volume range, when answering the question.

3. We then multiplied the average volume of research data produced by one researcher and the number of researchers (step 1) to estimate the volume of data produced in a specific country.
4. We then estimated the total volume of research data produced in those countries.
5. We also calculated the amount of volume produced by an average researcher in the whole sample and then multiplied by the total number of researchers in countries, where data was available, to compare the result with the one obtained in step 4.

The results indicate that amount of data is over 30Eb (exabytes). The estimation in Step 4 gave the value of 35.7Eb, and the estimation in Step 5 – 31.4Eb. Thus, both results are quite close. However, the amount is very likely to be overestimated to there being several caveats regarding the used approach:

- Researchers may have affiliations in several countries, leading to double counting as we used head counts for the total number of researchers.
- Researchers may work in the same research teams; thus, the same data may be counted more than once.
- Some countries have low response rates, leading to biases in the extrapolated data.

Given the shortcomings of the approach above, it is likely that the results are overestimating the amount of produced research data.

Source: own estimations based on the survey data.

Slightly less than a half of the respondents (48%) were not aware of the number of datasets they produce. Looking at those who could provide an approximate number of datasets produced, the number varied between 0 and 25 million. However, the majority (88%) of the respondents (who are aware of the number of datasets) selected a number in the range between 0 and 20, with four datasets as the median. For analytical purposes, the number of separate datasets was divided into intervals (see Figure 8). The illustration suggests that most of the researchers produced one to five or ten datasets in the current/last research activity.

Figure 8. Number of separate usable research datasets that a respondent or their team approximately produced in their current / latest research activity

Source: own elaboration based on unweighted researchers' survey, N = 10,972, do not know/cannot answer = 5,682. Note: percentages were calculated excluding "Do not know/ cannot answer or specify" answers

On average, researchers tended up to 10 GB of data in their latest research activity. However, one-third of respondents indicated that they do not know/cannot answer or specify what is the approximate volume (in bytes) of the usable research data that one produced in the current/ latest research activity. Out of those, who are aware of how much data they produce, 30% of respondents noted the interval of 1-100 MB. This was followed by 1-10 GB (23%), 100-1000MB (14%) and 10-100 GB (14%) (see Figure 9). Even though respondents could indicate the overall volume they produce by selecting the size of the dataset (MB, GB, TB or PB) and indicating the size manually, the responses about the overall volume of data are very similar to the ones that were provided for the size of the distinct dataset. This might suggest that respondents did not distinguish between the size of a dataset and the size of multiple datasets combined.

Figure 9. Volume of data produced in respondents' current / latest research activity (share of respondents)

Source: own elaboration based on unweighted researchers' survey, N = 9,697, do not know/cannot answer = 3,357. Note: percentages were calculated excluding "Do not know/ cannot answer or specify" answers.

3.1.2. Variation of produced research data volumes by country

We have used country groups described in Chapter 2, to assess if there is a geographic variation in research data production. The data showed that no large impact on volumes of produced data. Figure 10 below illustrates how the typical size of the dataset varies among respondents. It shows that slightly more respondents affiliated with EU14, Associated Countries with higher R&D expenditure (AC1) and the UK use larger datasets. The share of such respondents who produce datasets larger than 10 GB in these groups is around 31%, while in others it varies between 18% and 22%.

Figure 10. Size of a typical dataset produced, by country group (share of respondents)

Source: own elaboration based on unweighted researchers' survey, N = 10,972, Do not know/ cannot answer or specify = 5,682. Note: percentages were calculated excluding "Do not know/ cannot answer or specify" answers.

Analysis of the number of separate datasets produced by researchers showed that there is no variation between countries concerning this question. In terms of the overall volume of research data produced, the tendency remains the same as for the size of a typical dataset: researchers in EU14, Associated Countries with higher R&D expenditure (AC1), and the UK tend to produce slightly larger volumes of data than researchers in other countries. The percentage of produced data that is larger than 10 GB reaches 35% in Associated Countries with higher R&D expenditure and 20-26% in in Associated Countries with lower R&D expenditure (see Figure 11 below).

Figure 11. The volume of produced data by country group (share of respondents)

Source: own elaboration based on unweighted researchers' survey, N = 9,697, Do not know/ cannot answer or specify = 3,357. Note: percentages were calculated excluding "Do not know/ cannot answer or specify" answers.

When using a more detailed breakdown of EU countries, data showed that researchers from Northern Member States (DK, EE, FI, LV, LT and SE) tend to produce slightly more data of 1-100MB than other countries. However, despite differences in the means, analysis of 95% level confidence intervals showed that this is not a strong finding since there are small overlaps in 95% confidence intervals between this and other country groups.

3.1.3. Variation of produced research data volumes, by FOS

The size of a typical dataset produced by researchers seems to not vary much between fields of sciences. However, there are two exceptions (see Figure 12):

- Researchers in Social Sciences tend to produce smaller datasets (mainly up to 100MB) compared to other FOS.
- Researchers in Natural Sciences produce larger datasets, with 17.2% of respondents producing datasets larger than 1TB compared to 3-10% in other FOS.

Figure 12. Size of a typical dataset by primary FOS (share of respondents)

Source: own elaboration based on unweighted researchers' survey, N1-100MB = 1,736; N1-100TB = 572. Note: columns illustrate the mean, while bars – confidence intervals in 95% level; calculations exclude "Do not know/ cannot answer or specify" answers.

The distribution of the overall volumes of produced research data mostly do not vary much between FOS. The exception remains, that respondents in Social Sciences produce less data (mainly up to 100 MB), while researchers in Natural Sciences produce more data (over 1TB) than do researchers in other FOS (see Figure 13).

Figure 13. Volume of produced data by primary FOS (share of respondents)

Source: own elaboration based on unweighted researchers' survey data, N1-100MB = 1,926; N1-100TB = 479 , Note: columns illustrate the mean, while bars – confidence intervals in 95% level; calculations exclude "Do not know/ cannot answer or specify" answers.

In addition to country and FOS breakdowns, we checked the variation of produced research data volumes when controlling the career stage and primary affiliation of the respondent. In both cases analysis showed that respondents in different career stages and working in different affiliations tend to provide similar answers about produced data volumes.

3.1.4. Volumes of reused research data

More than half (54%) of respondents are not aware of the approximate size of the typical dataset. However, looking at the respondents who have such information, over a third (36%) of respondents reuse datasets sized 1-100MB and slightly less than a third (28%) produce datasets sized 1-10 GB (see Figure 14). Overall, the researchers are more likely to reuse datasets up to 100 GB.

Figure 14. Approximate size of a typical reused dataset (share of respondents)

Source: own elaboration based on unweighted researchers' survey, N = 7,827, do not know/cannot answer = 4,193. Note: percentages were calculated excluding "Do not know/ cannot answer or specify" answers.

Almost half of respondents (46%) indicated that they do not know or cannot answer what was the number of separate datasets that they reused in their current/latest research activity. For the rest, the number varied between 0 and 10 million. 88% of the respondents (excluding those who are not aware of datasets number) noted that they reused between 0

and 20 datasets, with a median of five reused datasets. Figure 15 below shows the distribution of researchers' answers. Around 60% of respondents reused one to five datasets in the current/ last research activity.

Figure 15. Number of separate usable datasets reused

Source: own elaboration based on unweighted researchers' survey, N = 6,262, do not know/cannot answer = 2,896.

Similar to data production, researchers tend to reuse up to 10 GB of data volume in their current/ latest research activity. A third of respondents indicated that they do not know/ cannot answer or specify the approximate volume of research data they reused. However, looking at researchers who were aware, the majority (37%) of respondents marked the interval of 1-100 MB. This was followed by 1-10 GB (21%) and 100-1000MB (17%) (see Figure 16).

Figure 16. The volume of reused data. What is the approximate quantity of data from outside of your research team that you reused in your current/latest research activity? (share of respondents)

Source: own elaboration based on unweighted researchers' survey data, N = 6,554, Do not know/ cannot answer = 2,200. Note: percentages were calculated excluding "Do not know/ cannot answer or specify" answers.

Box 3-3. Estimating the total amount of research data reused in the studied countries

As an exercise to estimate the total volumes of data reused across the EU, we have extrapolated from the responses collected in the survey. This is just an exploration of the data, and the weighting accuracy is limited. However, it may provide insight into the overall research data landscape. Based on the responses we calculated the volumes of

data reused by each respondent who answered the question about the total amount of research data reused in their current/latest research activity. The approach to calculation took the following steps:

1. We have used the latest available Eurostat data to identify the number of researchers (headcount) in the countries covered by the study³. Certain countries were excluded from further extrapolation, as Eurostat did not provide the relevant data⁴.
2. Using the responses (N = 4,355), we:
 - a. Excluded respondents who selected the 'do not know / cannot answer' option.
 - b. Calculated the total volume of data reused by respondents (number of respondents selecting a specific data volume range X the average value of that data volume range)
 - c. Calculated the average amount of data reused by one respondent in each country by dividing the sum from step 2.b by the number of respondents who selected a specific data volume range, when answering the question.
3. We then multiplied the average volume of research data reused by one researcher and the number of researchers (step 1) to estimate the volume of data reused in a specific country.
4. We then estimated the total volume of research data reused in those countries.
5. We also calculated the amount of volume reused by an average researcher in the whole sample and then multiplied by the total number of researchers in countries, where data was available, to compare the result with the one obtained in step 4.

The results indicate that the amount of data is larger than in the case of produced data. This is not surprising, since the same data can be reused by more than one person. The estimation in Step 4 gave the value of 48.6 Eb, and the estimation in Step 5 – 61.2 Eb. However, the amount is very likely to be overestimated as there are several caveats to the data collected:

- Researchers may have affiliations in several countries, leading to double counting as we used head counts for the total number of researchers.

³ Data from 2019 for all countries except CZ, DE, HR, PT, SK, RS, TR (data from 2020) and FR, IS, UK (data from 2018).

⁴ These are AI, AM, FO, GE, IL, MD, TN, UA.

- Researchers may work in the same research teams; thus, the same data may be counted more than once.
- Even in different teams, researchers may reuse the same data, as long as it is available to them.
- Some countries have low response rates, leading to biases in the extrapolated data.

Given the shortcomings of the approach above, it is likely that the results are overestimating the amount of reused research data.

Source: own estimations based on the survey data.

3.1.5. Variation of reused research data volumes by country

The size of a typical reused dataset does not vary much among countries. For most of the respondents, the size of the typical dataset they reused is up to 10 GB. As in the case of data production, a larger share of researchers from Associated Countries with lower R&D expenditure (AC2) and EU13 countries indicated reusing data up to 10GB in comparison to researchers in countries with higher R&D spending (EU14, AC1 and the UK, see Figure 17). However, the difference is relatively small. Overlaps in 95% level confidence intervals between some groups means that detailed conclusions on the differences cannot be drawn. A similar situation emerges at the more detailed breakdown of EU countries.

Figure 17. Size of a typical dataset reused by *country group* (share of respondents)

Source: own elaboration based on unweighted researchers' survey data, N = 7,827, Do not know/ cannot answer or specify = 4,193. Note: percentages were calculated excluding "Do not know/ cannot answer or specify" answers.

The number of distinct datasets reused by researchers does not vary much between country groups. With regards to the overall volume of research data reused, variation is minor, but respondents from EU13 and Associated Countries with lower R&D expenditure (AC2) tend to reuse data up to 10 GB slightly more often (81%) than others (73%). Nonetheless, the finding is not strong as there are some overlapping confidence intervals at the 95% level.

Figure 18. Volume of reused data by country group (share of respondents)

Source: own elaboration based on unweighted researchers' survey data, N = 5,666, Do not know/ cannot answer or specify = 1,855. Note: percentages were calculated excluding "Do not know/ cannot answer or specify" answers.

3.1.6. Variation of reused research data volumes by FOS

The variation of the size of the typical dataset seems to be equally distributed between FOS with an exception of Social Sciences. While around 43-47% of researchers in most of the FOS reuse datasets up to 1 GB, the percentage in Social Sciences is 61% (see Figure 19). As analysis of 95% confidence intervals showed the difference is likely true (see Figure 20).

Figure 19. Size of a typical dataset reused by primary FOS (share of respondents)

Source: own elaboration based on unweighted researchers' survey data, N = 7,827, Do not know/ cannot answer or specify = 4,193. Note: percentages were calculated excluding "Do not know/ cannot answer or specify" answers.

Figure 20. Share of respondents reusing datasets that are up to 1 GB by FOS (share of respondents)

Source: own elaboration based on unweighted researchers' survey data, N = 1,708. Note: columns illustrate the mean, while bars – confidence intervals in 95% level; percentages were calculated excluding “Do not know/ cannot answer or specify” answers.

The number of reused separate research datasets also tends to not vary much between FOS. Researchers mostly reuse up to 10 datasets (71-88% of researchers who are aware of the number). Some fluctuation can be seen, i.e. researchers in Social Sciences tend to use more datasets than, say, researchers in Agriculture Sciences, however, the differences are not high. While in social sciences there were 71% of respondents who reused up to 10 datasets, the percentage in Agricultural Sciences of such researchers was 87% (see Figure 21).

Figure 21. Number of separate datasets reused by primary FOS (share of respondents)

Source: own elaboration based on unweighted researchers' survey data, N = 6,262, do not know/cannot answer = 2,896. Note: percentages were calculated excluding “Do not know/ cannot answer” answers.

When looking at overall volumes of reused data in current/last research, the majority of researchers reuse up to 10 GB of research data. A larger portion of respondents from Social Sciences indicate reusing data up to 100 MB (47%) in comparison to other FOS (31-39%) (see Figure 22). However, there are some overlapping when looking at confidence intervals at the 95% level (with Agricultural Sciences FOS), which suggests that this finding is not that strong.

Figure 22. The volume of reused data, by primary FOS

Source: own elaboration based on unweighted researchers' survey data, N = 5,666, Do not know/ cannot answer = 1,855. Note: percentages were calculated excluding "Do not know/ cannot answer or specify" answers.

The variation of reused volumes was checked by controlling for career stage and primary affiliation. However, no significant differences were noticed between starting and experienced researchers as well as between researchers affiliated with different types of institutions.

3.1.7. Brief summary of the findings

In general, around half of all respondents were not aware of the volumes (in bytes and number of datasets) they produce or reuse. Analysing the answers of the respondents who could specify the volumes, a couple of outcomes emerged. Firstly, the majority of researchers tend to produce up to 10 GB of data, whether that would be the size of the separate dataset or the overall volume of data they reused or produces in their current/latest research activity. The percentage of researchers who produce data up to 10 GB is around 70% (of those who are aware of the volume), the percentage of researchers reusing data up to 10 GB is around 75% (of those who are aware of the volume). The number of distinct research datasets is usually up to 10 datasets, both in the case of data production or reuse.

Secondly, analysing the data in different sections, it was noted that the production or reuse of the data is usually independent of the country or the FOS. However, several minor fluctuations were observed. A larger share of researchers from EU13 (new EU MS) and Associate Countries with lower R&D expenditure produce and reuse up to 10 GB of data, than the rest of the EU and Associated Countries with higher R&D spending. In addition, while data volumes do not vary much between FOS, Social Sciences seem to be an exception, where more researchers use smaller (up to 10 GB data) than researchers in other fields of science. The analysis of career stage and primary affiliation of the researchers showed that volumes of produced and reused data do not vary between younger and more professionally mature researchers nor between researchers working in public and private institutions.

3.2. DATA TYPES: WHAT TYPES OF RESEARCH DATA ARE PROMINENT IN THE EUROPEAN RESEARCH DATA ECOSYSTEM?

Box 3-4. Key findings on data types

- Researchers mostly produce and reuse experimental/observational and qualitative/quantitative research data.
- The majority of respondents store produced data in personal physical data storage or institutional local data storage, regardless of the data type.
- Only 20-35% (depending on the type of data) of researchers deposited data in research data repositories during the current/latest research activity.
- Software or code, as well as simulation data, are mostly produced and reused in Engineering and Technology and Natural Sciences. Compiled/ derived data is more prominent in Social Sciences (35%), and Humanities (48%).
- More respondents in Humanities produce qualitative data, whereas respondents in all other FOS mostly produce quantitative data.
- Researchers mostly reused data referenced in academic publications or the ones that they have already used in the past. It was also quite common to stumble upon relevant reusable data while engaging in an open search.
- The choice of data source seems to be unrelated to the type of data.

3.2.1. Types of produced research data

In terms of data types, survey data were analysed in two ways:

- Looking into five data types, namely, experimental, observational, simulation, compiled/derived, and software or code;
- Looking at seven data types by content, namely, qualitative, quantitative, geospatial, digital image/video/audio and software or code.

Experimental and observational data were the most common amongst researchers regardless of the field they specialised in (see Figure 23). Meanwhile, simulation, compiled/derived, and software or code data were produced just half as often, as experimental, or observational data.

Figure 23. Types of research data produced in current/last research activity (share of respondents)

Source: own elaboration based on unweighted researchers' survey data, N = 10,995. Note: respondents could select multiple answer options.

Quantitative/tabular data surpass every other type of data produced, being chosen by approximately 83% of respondents (see Figure 24). A close second is qualitative/textual data which was chosen by approximately 58% of respondents. Meanwhile, the rest of the data types produced by fewer respondents, potentially due to the fact that these types may be more field-specific (see analysis by FOS later in the chapter).

Figure 24. Types of research data produced (by content type) in current/last research activity (share of respondents)

Source own elaboration based on unweighted researchers' survey data, N = 10,987. Note: respondents could select multiple answer options.

3.2.2. Variation of data storage practices depending on the type of data

The majority of respondents (over 60%) store produced data in personal physical data storage or institutional local data storage, regardless of the data type. The most common

storage for experimental and observational data storage is personal physical data storage, while the institutional local data storage is used more for simulation, compiled or software/code data. Nonetheless, these differences are often minor. For all types of data, the least used storage place is the personal website. Only 20-35% of researchers deposited data in research data repositories during their current/latest research activity, depending on the type of data (see Figure 25).

An additional data breakdown was analysed specifically for the data deposited in the research data repositories. The most common types of this data were processed data, data supporting publications, and raw data. There are some variations among different country groups and FOS (confirmed by analysing confidence intervals):

- More researchers working in Engineering and Technology (especially electrical engineering, electronic engineering, information engineering and medical engineering) and Natural Sciences (especially computer and information sciences, mathematics, and physical sciences) stored software package information and software code to repositories that those working in other FOS.
- Fewer researchers from Associated Countries with lower R&D spending than from other country groups stored raw data in repositories.
- More researchers from EU13 and Associated Countries with lower R&D spending than from other country groups stored data on research instruments in repositories.
- More researchers from EU14 and Associated Countries with higher R&D expenditure than from other country groups stored software code in repositories. However, this may also be related to the fact that a slightly larger share of Natural Sciences researchers filled in the survey in EU14 countries compared to other country groups.

Figure 25. Variation of data storage practices by type of data (share of respondents)

Source: own elaboration based on unweighted researchers' survey data. N total = 10,914, N experimental = 7,015, N observational = 6,329, N simulation = 3,480, N compiled = 3,188, N software = 3,260, N other = 418, N do not know = 62. Note: respondents could select multiple answer options.

3.2.3. Variation in types of produced data by country

Researchers mostly produce experimental and observational data regardless of their country (65% and 60% of respondents respectively in each data type group). The same tendency is observed in the data deposited to research data repositories. In general, the share of researchers who produce each type of data seems to not vary much between countries, with the exception of software or code data. This type of data is more prominent in EU14 (33%) and Associated Countries with relatively higher R&D expenditure (AC1) (29%). The share in other country groups varies around 20% for software or code data type. The analysis of the confidence intervals at the 95% level proved that the difference of EU14 and AC1 from other countries is significant (see Figure 26). Although a similar difference appears in the data deposited in repositories, the analysis of confidence intervals does not provide strong support. In addition, confidence interval analysis confirmed that researchers from G1 (Northern EU) Member States stored less simulation data compared to other country groups.

Figure 26. Production of software or code data by country group (share of respondents)

Source: own elaboration based on unweighted researchers' survey data, N = 3,279. Note: respondents could select multiple answer options for different types of data; columns illustrate the mean, while bars – confidence intervals in 95% level

Analysis of confidence intervals at 95% level reveals an interesting variation regarding qualitative data: researchers tend to produce more qualitative data in EU13 (67%) as well as in Associated Countries with relatively lower R&D spending (AC2, 71%) while it is less prominent in EU14 (55%) and Associated Countries with relatively higher R&D spending (AC1, 57%). The opposite is seen in the case of software or code data (see Figure 27). Digital audio and video data types remain the least frequently used in all country groups (3-11%), this is also clearly seen in more disaggregated groupings of countries.

Figure 27. Production of qualitative and software data by country group (share of respondents)

Source: own elaboration based on unweighted researchers' survey data, N qualitative = 6,385, N software or code = 2,899. Note: respondents could select multiple answer options; columns illustrate the mean, while bars – confidence intervals in 95% level.

3.2.4. Variation in type of produced research data by FOS

Larger share of researchers in Engineering and Technology, Agricultural Sciences and Medical and Health Sciences (except for clinical medicine) produced experimental data the most, with observational data usually being a close second. Meanwhile, researchers in Social Sciences and Humanities mostly produced observational data, with experimental data being the second most popular type. A similar situation exists with the data deposited in research data repositories.

Analysis of confidence intervals at 95% level showed that software or code, as well as simulation data, are mostly produced in Engineering and Technology (46% and 60% respectively) and Natural Sciences (40% and 42% respectively). The same tendencies can be seen while looking only at the data deposited to research data repositories (although confidence interval analysis does not confirm significant difference for depositing of simulation data by Natural Sciences researchers). In terms of Natural Sciences, heterogeneity was noticed with regard to produced data. While the larger share of researchers in computer and information sciences, chemical sciences, biological sciences and other Natural Sciences produced experimental data, researchers in earth and related environmental sciences more frequently used observational data, and respondents from mathematics and physical sciences seemed to produce mostly simulation and software data. Compiled/ derived data is more prominent in Social Sciences (35%), and Humanities (48%). This type of data was also more often deposited to research data repositories by Humanities (difference confirmed by confidence interval analysis) and Social Science (differenced observed, but not confirmed by confidence interval analysis).

Confidence intervals at 95% level revealed several interesting findings. Firstly, larger share of respondents in the Humanities produce qualitative data, whereas respondents in all other FOS mostly produced quantitative data (see Figure 28). Software/code data was prominent in Engineering and Technology (44%) as well as in mathematics, computer and information

sciences, physical sciences, earth and related environmental sciences and biological sciences (second level of Natural Sciences). Geospatial data is relatively more important in the Natural Sciences (24%) Agricultural Sciences (21%) and Humanities (17%).

Figure 28. Produced data types (by content) by FOS (share of respondents)

Source: own elaboration based on unweighted researchers' survey data, N = 10,987. Note: Since respondents could choose more than one answer, the percentage is provided as a share of all respondents within a group. Respondents could select multiple answer options; columns illustrate the mean, while bars – confidence intervals in 95% level.

3.2.5. Types of reused research data

The majority of the researchers reused observational data (59%) while experimental data was a close second with 53%. Software/code was less reused but still prominent with simulation data seemingly being reused half as frequently as observational data. This may presuppose the fact that observational and experimental data types are easier to reuse in different research fields, whereas software data, for instance, is more field or topic-specific.

Figure 29. Types of research data used in current/last research activity (share of respondents)

Source: own elaboration based on unweighted researchers' survey data, N = 7,931. Note: respondents could select multiple answer options.

Most of respondents reuse quantitative/tabular data (75%). Qualitative or textual data was significantly less common than quantitative (47%), but much more prevalent than a digital image (23%) or geospatial data (21%). Digital video and digital audio data were the least prominent amongst researchers. However, it is worth mentioning that these types of data were least common in terms of produced data as well. Meanwhile, geospatial and digital image data types were reused by more respondents than produced.

Figure 30. Types of research data (by content) used in current/last research activity (share of respondents)

Source: own elaboration based on unweighted researchers' survey data, N = 7,887. Note: respondents could select multiple answer options.

3.2.6. Where does data of different types come from for reuse?

In terms of coming across data to reuse, most respondents (74%) reused data referenced in academic publications. 50% of respondents reuse data that they have already used in the past. It was also quite common to stumble upon relevant reusable data while engaging in an open search (45%). The survey showed that it was not common amongst researchers to look for reusable data in subscription databases (12%), other researchers' websites (21%) or to use the ESFRI infrastructures (2%). This latter situation however may also show more the lack of awareness of ESFRI than actual low rate of using it. And interesting finding is that researchers who reuse software or code data are significantly less likely to look for this data in supplementary files linked to publications (4%), than researchers who reuse other types of data (39%). For the rest data sources the variation between reused data types remain quite similar (see Table 7).

Table 7. Cross-tabulation of types of reused research data and data sources used by researchers (share of respondents)

Data sources \ Data types	Experimental data	Observational data	Simulation data	Compiled/derived data	Software or code	Other	Do not know/cannot answer	All datatypes
I have used this data in the past	48%	56%	57%	58%	56%	40%	35%	50%
I found data referenced in academic publications	80%	73%	80%	79%	80%	65%	38%	74%
I knew the project which delivered the data	36%	42%	44%	44%	44%	28%	4%	36%
My colleague(s) recommended this data / shared the (link to) this data with me	41%	44%	50%	47%	49%	34%	15%	40%
I have searched research data repositories	41%	40%	42%	46%	47%	38%	18%	38%
I have searched for supplementary files linked to publications	39%	33%	39%	39%	4%	30%	13%	33%
I engaged in open search (e.g. PubMed, Google Scholar, Microsoft Academic, web search)	50%	45%	45%	50%	48%	45%	34%	45%
I have searched in subscription databases (e.g. Data Citation Index)	13%	12%	14%	14%	11%	13%	13%	12%
I have searched researchers' websites	22%	23%	26%	25%	24%	19%	15%	21%
I have requested data from researchers	35%	33%	39%	37%	39%	28%	15%	31%
I have used ESFRI infrastructures	2%	2%	3%	4%	3%	2%	1%	2%
Other	2%	3%	3%	4%	3%	14%	3%	3%
Do not know/cannot answer	2%	2%	2%	2%	2%	6%	24%	2%
N	3498	3941	1913	2429	2664	301	71	6564

Source: own elaboration based on unweighted researchers' survey data, N total= 6,564. Note: Percentages were calculated based on the data type, not on data source. Respondents could select multiple answer options.

3.2.7. Variation in types of reused data by country

Analysis of confidence intervals at 95% level showed that there is limited variation between country groups with regards to these types. As in the case of data production, researchers tend to reuse software or code data more in EU14 and Associated Countries with higher R&D spending (40-43%) (see Figure 31).

Figure 31. Types of research data reused by country group (share of researchers)

Source: own elaboration based on unweighted researchers' survey data, N total= 7,931, N EU14= 5,042, N EU=13= 1,112, N AC1= 1,225, N AC2= 472, N Other = 80. Note: Since respondents could choose more than one answer, the percentage is provided as a share of all respondents in a particular country group.

Variation may be noticed, when analysing data types by content. Firstly, in all country groups (with the exception of Associated Countries with a lower R&D spending (AC2)), quantitative data is dominant with regard to data reuse (73-76%). Larger share of respondents from countries with higher R&D expenditure tend to reuse qualitative data (~42%) than respondents from the countries with lower income levels (56-68%). The finding is significant looking at 95% confidence intervals. The rest of the data types are reused less than aforementioned two, thus, fewer fluctuations are seen as well (see Figure 32).

Figure 32. Types of research data reused (by content form) by country group (share of respondents)

Source: own elaboration based on unweighted researchers' survey data, N total = 7,887 N EU14= 5,020, N EU=13= 1,104, N AC1= 1,214, N AC2= 469, N Other =80. Note: Since respondents could choose more than one answer, the percentage is provided as a share of all respondents in a particular country group.

3.2.8. The variation in types of reused data by FOS

Analysing confidence intervals at 95% some findings can be drawn. Firstly, observational data still dominated Social Sciences and Humanities (as in the case for data production), while experimental data is more reused by researchers from other FOS. However, some confidence intervals overlap for Humanities, thus the evidence about Humanities could be considered as weaker. Simulation and software or code data were mainly reused by researchers from Natural Sciences and Engineering and Technology. The reuse of compiled/derived, simulation and software data seemed to be much more common than that of production and was mostly noticed in Natural Sciences, Engineering and Technology and Agricultural Sciences (see Figure 33).

Figure 33. Reused data types by FOS (share of respondents)

Source: own elaboration based on unweighted researchers' survey data, N=10,987. Note: respondents could select multiple answer options; columns illustrate the mean, while bars – confidence intervals in 95% level.

Regarding second-level FOS, notable use of compiled/derived data was seen in economics and business. However, the rest of the fields were much more fragmented in comparison to data production. For instance, a larger share of researchers in mathematics, earth and related environmental sciences and other natural sciences (second level FOS of Natural Sciences) reused observational data, while the rest of second-level FOS researchers mostly reuse experimental data. Similar heterogeneity was noticed in the fields of Engineering and Technology with approximately 27% of second-level FOS respondents choosing observational data and 73% favouring experimental data, Medical and Health Sciences with a 60/40% split and Agricultural Sciences with a 20/80% split accordingly.

When it comes to the type of data used by content, it was mostly researchers in the fields of Natural Sciences, Engineering and Technology, Medical and Health Sciences, Agricultural and Social Sciences that tended to reuse quantitative data more (except for Agricultural biotechnology and Law, two second-level FOS fields that favoured qualitative data more). Meanwhile, a larger share of researchers in Humanities reused qualitative data. Digital image data was also found to be prevalent in reusing data.

Figure 34. Types of research data reused (by content form) by FOS (share of respondents)

Source: own elaboration based on unweighted researchers' survey data, N total = 10,987, N NS= 3,286, N ET= 2,326, N MHS= 1,976, N AS= 612, N SS=2,326, N H=461. Note: Since respondents could choose more than one answer, the percentage is provided as a share of all respondents in the particular FOS group.

3.2.9. Brief summary of the findings

Overall, both in the production and the reuse, experimental and observational data types were the most common, as well as quantitative and qualitative types of data. Regarding simulation, compiled/derived and software data, a key difference was that for production, researchers tended to choose simulation more often and compiled/derived data less often, whereas for reuse researchers tended to choose software more often and simulation data less often.

The majority of respondents (over 60%) store produced data in personal physical data storage or institutional local data storage, regardless of the data type. In the personal physical data storage, researchers store experimental and observational data more often, while the institutional local data storage is more used for simulation, compiled or software/code data. However, only 20-35% (depending on the data type) of researchers deposited data in research data repositories during the current/latest research activity.

Looking into variation by country, in both data production and reuse, researchers from EU14 and Associated Countries with higher R&D spending produced and reused software and code data more often than researchers from EU13 and Associated Countries with lower R&D expenditure. The opposite situation emerged with qualitative data.

With regards to FOS, researchers in Social Sciences and Humanities mostly produced, reused and deposited observational data, while researchers in other FOS mostly worked with experimental data. However, these data types were dominant across all FOS. Software

or code and simulation data were more frequently produced, reused and deposited in Natural Sciences and Engineering and Technology than in the other FOS. Compiled/derived data was more prominent in Social Sciences (35%) and Humanities (48%). By content form, quantitative and qualitative data were dominant in all FOS, but qualitative data was more often produced and reused in Humanities, than quantitative, while the situation was reversed for other FOS.

Finally, researchers mostly reused data referenced in academic publications or the one that they have already used in the past. It was also quite common to stumble upon relevant reusable data while engaging in an open search. Reliance on a particular data source seems to be independent of the type of data.

3.3. DATA STANDARDS: WHAT ARE THE DATA PRODUCTION STANDARDS AND WHAT IS THEIR ROLE?

Box 3-5. Key findings on data standards

- Key standards followed by researchers are methodology standards.
- The key sources of standards are science disciplines and the research community. Here, the type of organisation where researchers work, seems to provide variation.
- More than a half of respondents indicate that they follow community standards either always or sometimes. However, when it comes to decisions about storing their research data in research data repositories or storing their data long-term, about a third of respondents agree that research community norms play a role.
- The stronger impact of repositories' adherence to disciplinary and ethical norms is seen in responses from researchers Humanities, Social Sciences, and Medical and Health Sciences.

3.3.1. Adherence to data standard types

There is a variety of standards related to research data that researchers may follow. In this chapter we look at several specific characteristics of standards:

- their coverage (e.g. methodology, variable, definition, etc.)
- the sources of standards (e.g. how / by whom are they set / determined)
- the role of community standards

What are the followed data standards?

The survey asked researchers to indicate what types of standards they follow. Overall, the key standards that are followed are methodology standards, a response option chosen by over 80%, of respondents. Other types of standards are used to a relatively lesser degree

(each selected by fewer than 50% of respondents). Standards of variable definition were the least frequently chosen option (by less than 30% of respondents). One possible implication of this data is that while methodological standards are followed universally, other standards that are relevant for data reuse (e.g. in terms of how data was processed, variables measured and defined, or data described) are lacking, making it more difficult for potential users of data to understand how the data relates to their research.

Figure 35. Types of standards that respondents or their research teams followed, when producing research data in their current / latest research activity (share of respondents)

Source: own elaboration based on unweighted researchers' survey data, N =7,628. Note: respondents could select multiple answer options.

Data suggests that there is relatively little evidence of significant variation among the researchers with different demographics in terms of age. We have looked at the age groups of respondents, and while there seems to be a decrease in the use of standards with age in most cases, calculating 95% confidence interval suggested the differences are too minor to consider an actual finding instead of noise in the data. Thus, the challenges related to certain standards being less followed are persistent and may require addressing irrespective of researchers' career stage.

There is little variation among the different countries of respondents. Despite there being differences in the means, analysis of confidence intervals at 95% level shows that detailed conclusions on the relevant differences cannot be drawn. However, there are some stronger differences between the first level FOS. In terms of methodology standards, while still scoring above 70%, respondents from Engineering and Technology field indicated using them less often than other FOS, even when confidence intervals were taken into account. Similarly, Humanities tend to score lower in measuring standards and to an extent standards covering variable definition. This may well be due to the fact that Humanities tend to deal more with qualitative data, where specific indicators and measures may be less strictly defined. Therefore, the variation here is not surprising. Yet, it may also suggest a

need to develop an approach to standards that would be more relevant in disciplines where they are currently applied to a lower extent.

Figure 36. Types of standards that respondents or their research teams followed, when producing research data in their current / latest research activity by FOS (share of respondents)

Source: own elaboration based on unweighted researchers' survey data, Total N=7,628, Agricultural Sciences N=381, Engineering and Technology N=1,509, Humanities N=345, Medical and Health Sciences N=1,423, Natural Sciences N=2,374, Social Sciences N=1,596. Note: respondents could select multiple answer options; columns illustrate the mean, while bars – confidence intervals in 95% level.

How are the standards set?

The “sources” of standards can help understand how researchers select standards to be followed. The two key sources of standards used by researchers are the discipline (56% of respondents) and the research community (52% of respondents).

The key source of variation seems to be the type of organisation where a responding researcher works. Standards set by the industry are more important for researchers from the private sector, especially, those working in business enterprises. 39% of those working in large companies, 31% of those working in SMEs, 17% of those working in private hospitals, and 12% of those working in private universities indicated that they follow industry standards. For all other categories of researchers, the share of responses was below 10%. At the same time, researchers from business enterprises tended to choose research community as a source of standards less frequently. Government standards mostly affect hospitals (whether public or private). This is not surprising, given that research in this field deals with human subjects, making it more likely to be regulated by government agencies.

However, small sample sizes for some of the institution types limit the explanatory power of the data. Figure below illustrates the overlaps in 95% level confidence intervals between some groups. Yet, some findings, such as business enterprise reliance on industry's standards or (mostly) the more prominent use of standards set by government in public and private hospitals seem to remain. Nonetheless, some of the groups have limited number of respondents, and therefore the findings should be taken with a grain of salt.

Figure 37. Sources of standards by respondents' primary organisation type (share of respondents)

Source: own elaboration based on unweighted researchers' survey data, Total N=9,712, Public University N=6,629, Public research institute, laboratory, or another public organisation N=1,952, Private university N=304, Public hospital N=305, Private hospital N=41, NGO non-profit organisation N=145, Large company N=61, SME N=110, Other private organization N=52, Other N=112. Note: respondents could select multiple answer options; columns illustrate the mean, while bars – confidence intervals in 95% level.

In terms of country groups, the variation in shares of respondents choosing one or another option is very low. The responses follow similar patterns, with specifics of the discipline and research communities being the most important sources of standards, followed by government bodies, research data repositories and the industry. One of the stand out results is the relatively high reliance on standards set by the industry by respondents from Associated Countries with lower R&D spending. Nonetheless, the analysis of confidence intervals does not rule out that the population mean does not differ from the other country groups.

Of the different FOS, there seem to be several aspects of variation. First, researchers in Engineering and Technology are relying on standards set by the specifics of the discipline relatively less than other fields of science and use more standards set by the industry than other fields of science do. This latter may likely be explained by the clear relevance of research in this field of science for industrial applications. Second, research in Natural Sciences seems to take into account more data repository standards than other fields of science. This is related to the finding that researchers from this field were more likely to deposit their data in research data repositories overall (see section 3.5). Third, researchers in Medical and Health Sciences are the most likely to use standards set by governmental bodies. This can be explained by research in this field involving human subjects. Similar

argument can also apply to social sciences, where research is also often directly relevant for policy and thus government-set standards may be more relevant than in most other fields. Finally, researchers in Humanities tend to adhere to the standards set by the specifics of the discipline to a very large extent (73% of respondents). Overall, it seems that the field of science and the type of organisation are the key factors determining reliance on the specific standards.

Figure 38. Sources of standards by FOS (share of respondents)

Source: own elaboration based on unweighted researchers' survey data, Total N=9,712, Agricultural Sciences N=531; Engineering and Technology N=2,085; Humanities N=401; Medical and Health Sciences N=1,719; Natural Sciences N=2,940; Social Sciences N=2,036. Note: respondents could select multiple answer options; columns illustrate the mean, while bars – confidence intervals in 95% level.

Box 3-6. Insights from free-text data

- Some indicated that standards used follow from a common sense or common research practice (the latter could likely also imply the role of research community)
- Some others have indicated following personal (or own) standards
- There were also references to individual sub-disciplines, e.g. “few standards exist for astronomy, most of them are rather good practices, often each group defines its standard, in most cases using a metastandard to describe it (example: VOTable, FITS tables, HDF5 and so on)”
- One particular response also outlined the problems related to standards and the regulations that are applied and proposing an approach to alleviate the time requirements: “I have over the past years spent a huge amount of time (more unpaid work!) trying to gain an overview of which regulations apply for my research. If regulators do not have the funding, expertise, competence to set up functional

regulatory systems that actually support ethical research rather than creating impossible constraints, and if the highly ranked research university at which I work does not have the funding, expertise, competence and capacity to provide any kind of useful support, I do not see how any individual researcher or department can be expected to navigate this jungle. It has come to a point where the time and resources spent just trying to obtain information about standards and applicable legislation (to be able to describe their data management plan and comply with whatever we are expected to comply with) exceeds the actual paid research time that researchers can hope to get for a project. Personally, I have therefore now opted to follow a more basic approach: devoting time to reflection on ethical implications of my research, and being transparent about my research process to the extent that it's feasible, meaningful and ethical."

Source: researcher survey.

What is the role of community standards?

Among other reasons, the study aimed to understand how the research community affects researchers' practices. Therefore, we looked specifically at prevalence of the community standards. Community standards for data or metadata, relevant to discipline or sub-discipline seem to be used by most researchers at least to an extent. For the whole sample of respondents, 26.8% indicated that they always use such community standards, while an additional 35% responded that they sometimes do so. Only 25.8% of respondents indicated that they never follow community standards. Finally, those who do not know the answer or could not respond to the question made 12.4% of the total respondent sample. The results here suggest that researchers overall tend to follow community standards, at least to an extent. The low share of respondents choosing the 'do not know / cannot answer' option also suggests that researchers are generally aware of community standards (although, it is also probable that some of the respondents who never follow community standards also do not have sufficient knowledge about them). Nonetheless, even if community standards play an overall role, there seems to be room for improvement, especially in promoting standards relating to data description, variable measurement, and data processing.

Looking at the different groups of countries, we see that there is relatively little variation, with differences being small. Thus, it seems that geographically, there is no significant variation in terms of the use of community standards. In terms of the fields of science, it seems that researchers in Humanities tend to be more prone to using community standards (the only field where 'always' was chosen more often than 'sometimes'), followed by Natural Sciences. Yet, the variation between the different fields of science is not too large and we cannot ascertain that these differences indeed come from the FOS characteristics.

Figure 39. Frequency of using community standards for data or metadata, relevant to respondents' discipline or sub-discipline by FOS (number of respondents)

Source: own elaboration based on unweighted researchers' survey data, Total N=10,181. Note: respondents could select multiple answer options.

3.3.2. How do standards and norms affect researchers' decisions?

Given the possibility of variation in researchers' practices, it may also be that (non)adherence to specific standards or norms play a role in determining how a researcher behaves. This section looks into this issue from exactly this perspective:

- identifiable variation in researchers' practices depending on the standards they follow
- researchers' perception on how much the norms of research communities affect their decisions relating to storing data

Overall, less than a third of researchers consider that norms of the research community contribute to their decisions to store research data in research data repositories (31%) or store data for long term (over 5 years) (33%). Only slightly more than a third of respondents (36%) indicate that when choosing the research data repository, they take into account repository's respect for disciplinary and ethical norms and meeting the legal requirements needed by the respondent or their research team.

Thus, even if more researchers tend to indicate that they follow community standards, the norms of a research community play a less important role when making decisions about data depositing. This has two possible implications. First, that the research community as a channel as a limited role in forming researchers' practices. However, this point is somewhat contradicted by researchers' use of research community standards. Data shows that they

research community is an important source of them. Second, that normalisation of depositing practices within research communities is still ongoing and requires more time or more awareness raising / support for adoption. While, collected data does not allow to clearly state that this is the case, this explanation is plausible.

In terms of the fields of science, researchers Humanities, Social Sciences, and Medical and Health Sciences indicate stronger impact of repositories' adherence to disciplinary and ethical norms. Researchers in Humanities are also more likely to consider community norms when deciding on a long-term storage of research data compared to researchers in other fields of science, with largest differences from researchers in Agricultural Sciences and Engineering and Technology. Overall, the responses from researchers whose primary work is in this latter field, community norms seem to play a less important role in all considered cases.

3.3.3. Brief summary of the findings

Key standards followed by researchers are methodology standards. Researchers in Engineering and Technology note using methodology standards less frequently than researchers from other fields of science. Humanities score lower in terms of measuring standards and standards covering variable definition. Overall, less frequent use of standards relating to data may imply that it is more difficult for potential users of data to understand how the data relates to their research, thus, decreasing the likelihood of reuse (17% of respondents also indicated that they are concerned about possible misinterpretation or misuse of the research data they produced). The key sources of standards are science disciplines and the research community. Here, the type of organisation where researchers work seem to provide variation. Standards set by the industry are more important for researchers working in business enterprises, while standards set by government are most often followed by researchers working in hospitals.

More than a half of respondents indicate that they follow community standards either always or sometimes. Nonetheless, even if community standards play an overall role, there is room for improvement, for example, in terms of following standards relating to data handling. Furthermore, when it comes to decisions about storing their research data in research data repositories or storing their data long-term, about a third of respondents agree that research community norms play a role. The role of research data repository's adherence to ethical norms and legal requirements was also indicated by around a third of researchers in relation to their choice of research data repositories. Therefore, communities could conceivably do more in 'normalising' research data depositing, making a more frequent practice. The stronger impact of repositories' adherence to disciplinary and ethical norms is seen in responses from researchers Humanities, Social Sciences, and Medical and Health Sciences. Humanities researchers are also more likely to consider community norms when deciding on a long-term storage of research data compared to researchers in other fields of science, especially those in Agricultural Sciences and Engineering and Technology.

3.4. CONDITIONS FOR ACCESSING, SHARING, AND REUSE OF RESEARCH DATA

Box 3-7. Key findings on access, sharing, and reuse conditions

- There seems to be little consideration of access and reuse conditions, when deciding on whether to use or not use a particular research dataset or a research data repository, with this lack being especially prominent when it comes to research datasets.
- When reusing research data, two thirds of respondents indicated using data that was publicly available without restrictions
- When setting restrictions for their own research data, around three fourths of researchers indicated making or planning to make their data publicly accessible free of charge.
- Research data is owned mostly either by researchers (their teams) or by their institutions. Here, geographic breakdown reveals variation in research practices. Ownership by researchers is more prominent in the Associated Countries, especially those with lower R&D spending, while employers' ownership is stronger in EU countries, especially in EU13.
- When setting licences for research data, researchers tend to require attribution, but even this was indicated only by slightly more than a fourth of respondents.
- The main reasons for setting restrictions on produced research data are researchers' plans to use the data in their own further publications and data protection requirements they have to meet.

3.4.1. Access and reuse conditions

Access and reuse conditions may affect researchers' practices, such as willingness to use or not use specific datasets or research data repositories. Therefore, this section looks into the perceptions of researchers in terms of how affected their choices are.

When responding on the effects of access and reuse conditions on the choice to use a specific research data repository or a research dataset, there emerged a relatively large difference in terms of those who agree that their choice is affected. For research data repositories the share of respondents indicating the effect is 33%, while the share for datasets is only 15.8%. Similarly, more respondents could not answer the question on datasets than on research data repositories, suggesting their possible lack of knowledge of access and reuse conditions for individual research datasets. Indeed, even taking into account the confidence intervals the differences seem to remain. Thus, it is more likely that a researcher will consider the general conditions associated with the medium, where the research data is deposited, rather than with an individual dataset.

The lack of knowledge about the impact of access and reuse conditions has two possible implications. First, researchers do not know or do not consider the conditions attached to research repositories and/or especially research datasets significant relevance. Second, they do not consciously consider the conditions, but give priority to other characteristics (likely, such as the relevance of the data to their own research). In this case raising awareness about the importance of access and reuse conditions could help improve understanding of the research data management procedures.

Figure 40. Share of respondents indicating that access and reuse conditions affected (did not affect) their choice to use a research dataset / research data repository

Source: own elaboration based on unweighted researchers' survey data, N repositories – 7,733; N datasets – 6,175; columns illustrate the mean, while bars – confidence intervals in 95% level.

Distributions of responses across the different country groups and fields of science tend to be quite similar, with no clear differences in proportions when confidence intervals are considered. For research datasets, researchers from Natural Sciences seem to take into account the access and reuse conditions to a somewhat lower extent, though we cannot clearly state that the difference from other groups is very strong. On the other hand, data indicates that researchers from Medical and Health Sciences as well as Agricultural Sciences indicate they take access and reuse conditions to a lower extent when choosing research data repositories (28%), which seems to be more prominent in the former FOS, if confidence intervals are taken into account. While researchers in Humanities do it to the highest extent among the FOS (38%), we cannot state that difference is strong, due to the margin of error.

Overall, for decisions to use or not use a research dataset, the variation is even lower than for research data repositories. The low proportions of researchers indicating taking into account access and reuse conditions for research datasets, the data suggests that research and access condition are not taken into account much, when dealing with individual datasets. The high share of respondents choosing a 'do not know / cannot answer' option suggest a lack of awareness, especially in relation to research datasets.

3.4.2. Restrictions in reused data

When reusing the data, by far the dominant choice was to use research data that was publicly available without restrictions, as indicated by 68% of respondents. Respondents indicated that they encountered other types of restrictions less often. Among these other types, the key was data availability for academic non-commercial use (chosen by 35% of respondents). Some types of restrictions were selected considerably less frequently than others. They include requirement to demonstrate ethical approval (5%) and requirement to pay for accessing and using data (6%).

Figure 41. Restriction levels of data reused in respondents' current / latest research activity (share of respondents)

Source: own elaboration based on unweighted researchers' survey data, N=7,738. Note: respondents could select multiple answer options.

Researchers from public and private hospitals seem to differ somewhat from the other types. First, they tend to rely on publicly available data less often (both in general, and if registration was required). This also applies to commercially available data. They also seem to have needed to provide ethical approval more often. As they deal with human subject this is an expected finding.

Looking at the different country groups, there emerge no large differences except that it seems that researchers from Associated Countries with lower R&D spending and EU13 countries tend to use publicly available data that does not have specific restrictions set

more often than researchers from Associated Countries with higher R&D spending and EU14. However, at higher granularity the G1 (Northern Europe) group showed a somewhat lower use of publicly available data.

Figure 42. Share of respondents reusing publicly available data, provided without any restrictions by country group

Source: own elaboration based on unweighted researchers' survey data, Total N=7,738, AC1 N=763, AC2 N=466, EU13 N=1,076, EU14 N=4,927, Other N=75, UK N=431. Note: columns illustrate the mean, while bars – confidence intervals in 95% level.

In terms of the first level fields of science, data available publicly without restrictions varied from 74% in Natural Sciences to 57% in Medical and Health Sciences. The Creative Commons licence seems to be the most widely applied in datasets reused among respondents from Humanities (44%), with difference remaining when 95% confidence interval is considered. Medical and Health Sciences seem to lag behind others (18%), possibly because research there tends to involve human subjects, which makes such data less fit for sharing with few restrictions. Agricultural and Social Sciences also seem to be behind other fields of science in terms of respondents reusing datasets with Creative Commons licence. At the same time, researchers in Health and Medical Sciences need to demonstrate ethical approval to be able to access the data, which was also more often the case in Social Sciences (13% and 7% respectively compared to less than 5% in other fields of science). The difference for Health and Medical Sciences from other fields remains even when considering 95% confidence intervals. Finally, researchers in Humanities and Social Sciences use commercially available data more often than researchers in other fields (11% and 8% compared to 6% and less in other fields of science). This to an extent remains true even when 95% confidence intervals are assessed (those there are some small overlaps).

Table 8. Restrictions to reused data by respondents' FOS

Restrictions	AGR	ENG	HUM	MED	NAT	SOC
Research data was publicly available, without any restrictions	68.10%	69.20%	67.00%	57.40%	73.60%	64.70%
Research data used Creative Commons licence	21.70%	31.30%	43.70%	18.40%	33.50%	21.90%
Research data used Open Data Commons Open Database Licence	23.20%	21.10%	20.90%	14.70%	18.80%	16.20%
Data was available, but I had to register (free of charge)	25.30%	24.90%	26.30%	20.40%	27.00%	32.90%
Data was available, but only for academic and/or non-commercial use	33.10%	34.30%	41.00%	33.20%	33.20%	36.80%
Data was available without restrictions to my research group / project team but with restrictions to others	17.80%	16.60%	13.70%	18.00%	17.90%	13.40%
Data was available without restrictions to members of my institution but with restrictions to members outside of my institution	12.30%	8.60%	12.30%	9.40%	8.40%	8.60%
Research data was available upon request	26.20%	26.40%	24.70%	28.40%	29.20%	26.30%
Data was available, but I had to demonstrate ethical approval to access	3.00%	3.30%	4.60%	12.60%	2.70%	7.20%
Data was commercial (i.e. a payment had to be made to access the data)	4.80%	6.10%	10.50%	3.70%	4.70%	8.40%
Other	1.20%	1.90%	2.10%	3.50%	3.00%	2.60%
Do not know/cannot answer	6.00%	4.20%	5.90%	3.80%	3.90%	3.40%
Total N	332	1762	373	1092	2660	1519

Source: own elaboration based on unweighted researchers' survey data. Note: respondents could select multiple answer options. Note: AGR - Agricultural Sciences, ENG - Engineering and Technology, HUM - Humanities, MED - Medical and Health Sciences, NAT - Natural Sciences, SOC - Social Sciences.

Restrictions are mostly felt in the Medical and Health Sciences, this relates to public availability, the use of Creative Commons or Open Data Commons licences, or free but with registration. On the other hand, more data required demonstrated ethical approval to access. This option was selected by 13% of respondents. Otherwise, ethical approval requirement was indicated by less than 10% of respondents in other FOS. The overall low ethical requirements, while not necessarily equally important for all research, indicates a potential challenge relating to awareness of research ethics.

3.4.3. Restrictions set for produced data

We look at restrictions for produced data from several perspectives:

- level of access that respondents either provide or plan to provide to the research data produced in their latest research activities;
- right ownership and decisions on the access to be provided
- specific licencing conditions and the reasons behind the choice

Level of access provided

Overall, researchers responding to the question on the level of access (to be) provided for data in their current / latest research activities suggest that the majority aim to make it publicly accessible (even if registration may be required). This option was chosen by 74% of researchers, which is a high proportion. Meanwhile, 36% of respondents also indicated that data will be available only for specific purposes (e.g. non-commercial research) and/or to specific groups (e.g. institutional partners), while 12% will require ethical approval before granting access. Finally, only 4% of respondents planned to request payment for access and reuse of their data, suggesting limited aims of using research data for commercial purposes.

Figure 43. Level of access that respondents provided or plan to provide for their data from current / latest research activity (share of respondents)

Source: own elaboration based on unweighted researchers' survey data, N = 7,384. Note: respondents could select multiple answer options.

Geographically, the variation is minimum, especially when taking confidence intervals into account. There is more variation, when it comes to the fields of science. Comparable to the data from the survey questions on restrictions in reused data, researchers in Medical and Health Sciences are less likely to provide public, open and free access to their research

data, while being more likely to require ethical approval. Medical researchers are also more likely to limit access to their data by purpose and / or groups. These differences are strong and hold if confidence intervals are considered.

Similar tendencies can be seen in Social Sciences researchers' responses, though to a lower extent than in the Medical and Health Sciences field. Meanwhile, the fields with the most researchers indicating that their data will be publicly and openly accessible free of charge are Natural Sciences (83%) and Humanities (82%), with difference of Natural Sciences from other groups being especially clear.

Figure 44. Level of access that respondents provided or plan to provide for their data from current / latest research activity by FOS (share of respondents)

Source: own elaboration based on unweighted researchers' survey data, Total N=7,384, Agricultural Sciences N=415, Engineering and Technology N=1,512, Humanities N=351, Medical and Health Sciences N=1,258, Natural Sciences N=2,553, Social Sciences N=1,295. Note: respondents could select multiple answer options; columns illustrate the mean, while bars – confidence intervals in 95% level.

Box 3-8. Insights from free-text data

- Making data available upon request, including sometimes making additional communication with access requesters, for example, “as I would need to explain how the data is collected and organized”
- There can also be interest to ‘safeguard’ own PhD level work: “after a period to protect PhD work”
- Some researchers stressed that it all depends on the specifics of an individual project, in one particular instance the respondent noted that “it depends on the project type. EU-funded are publicly available”
- There are also doubts about the relevance of produced data for other researchers, and the environmental footprint of storing the data

Source: researcher survey.

Rights of ownership

When it comes the rights of ownership of the produced data, most researchers indicate that they are owned either by researchers (their teams) themselves (64%) or their employers (53%). Other possible options were each selected by fewer than 15% of respondents.

Figure 45. Share of respondents indicating ownership of the rights to the data produced in their or their teams' current / latest research activity

Source: own elaboration based on unweighted researchers' survey data, N=10,921. Note: respondents could select multiple answer options. Note: respondents could select multiple answer options.

What can be seen geographically, direct ownership by researchers or their teams is the most prevalent in Associated Countries with lower R&D spending (75%), while the extent of employer ownership in these same countries is lower than in other groups (45%), though the latter difference from other groups is less certain. Still, such findings may indicate a lower development of institutional data rights management in Associated Countries with lower R&D intensity.

Figure 46. Share of respondents indicating ownership of the rights to the data produced in their or their teams' current / latest research activity by country group

Source: own elaboration based on unweighted researchers' survey data, Total N=10,921, AC1 N=1,217, AC2 N=604, EU13 N=1,591, EU14 N=6,783, Other N=104, UK N=622. Note: respondents could select multiple answer options; columns illustrate the mean, while bars – confidence intervals in 95% level.

Within the EU some differences can also be noted, with respondents from EU13 countries being more likely to indicate institutional ownership was (62.% of respondents), similar to the personal / team ownership. Meanwhile, in EU14, the share of respondents indicating institutional ownership was 52%. Using a more detailed geographic breakdown, we see that respondents from North Western Europe (G2) indicate lower ownership by researchers/their teams (52%) and higher by employers (68%) than other groups within the EU. Meanwhile, researchers from South Western Europe (G3) and South Eastern Europe (G5) indicate higher personal/team ownership of research data (68% and 70% respectively). Respondents from South Western Europe (G3) also indicated institutional ownership to a lower extent than other EU country groups (43%).

Figure 47. Ownership of the rights to the data produced in their or their teams' current / latest research activity by country group (share of respondents)

Source: own elaboration based on unweighted researchers' survey data, Total N=10,921, AC1 N=1,839, AC2 N=604, G1 N=851, G2 N=1,444, G3 N=3,062, G4 N=2,299, G5 N=718, Other N=104. Note: respondents could select multiple answer options; columns illustrate the mean, while bars – confidence intervals in 95% level.

In terms of the different FOS, personal or team ownership is the most prevalent in Humanities and Social Sciences (over 70% in both cases). On the other hand, institutional ownership seems to be more frequent in the four other fields of science. One possible explanation could be higher reliance of non-SSH fields of science on institutional infrastructure. However, more data would be needed to take this into account. It also seems that researchers in Agriculture and Engineering and Technology more often produce research data that is owned by the funder, possibly due to contract research.

Figure 48. Ownership of the rights to the data produced in their or their teams' current / latest research activity by FOS (share of respondents)

Source: own elaboration based on unweighted researchers' survey data, Total N=10,921, Agricultural Sciences N=609, Engineering and Technology N=2,316, Humanities N=459, Medical and Health Sciences N=1,964, Natural Sciences N=3,261, Social Sciences N=2,312. Note: respondents could select multiple answer options; columns illustrate the mean, while bars – confidence intervals in 95% level.

Conditions set in licences

The most common type of requirement is the attribution requirement, indicated by 28% of respondents. In terms of country groups, it is more prevalent in the UK than in other groups (except for Other, but there the sample size is small). In general, confidence interval analysis does not allow to identify significant differences. Meanwhile, researchers from Associated Countries with lower income level are more likely to not set licensing at all than respondents from other groups (except for Other). The relatively large share of respondents choosing the 'do not know / cannot answer' option may also suggest lower awareness of licensing of research data overall.

Figure 49. Conditions set by respondents or their research teams with their research data licences in their current / latest activity (share of respondents)

Source: own elaboration based on unweighted researchers' survey data, N=7,381. Note: respondents could select multiple answer options.

Considering the different FOS, a couple of points are worth mentioning in relation to licencing. First, in accordance with the data from previous questions, researchers in Medical and Health sciences indicate more often on not being able to set licencing due to them not owning the data. However, using confidence intervals, this evidence is not very strong. They also tended to choose non-commercial licencing less frequently, whereas Engineering and Technology as well as Humanities researchers chose this option more often than did those from other fields of science, with evidence showing a strong difference for respondents from Engineering and Technology. Researchers in Humanities also chose the attribution requirement the most often.

Figure 50. Conditions set by respondents or their research teams with their research data licences in their current / latest activity by FOS (share of respondents)

Source: own elaboration based on unweighted researchers' survey data, Total N=7,381, Agricultural Sciences N=415, Engineering and Technology N=1,512, Humanities N=350, Medical and Health Sciences N=1,256, Natural Sciences N=2,553, Social Sciences N=1,295. Note: respondents could select multiple answer options; columns illustrate the mean, while bars – confidence intervals in 95% level.

Reasons for setting specific licencing

The key reason behind setting restrictions is planning to use the data for further publications, thus first working through it most thoroughly by the same researcher / team. The second key limitation to data sharing is the data protection requirements (such as GDPR), making researchers unable to share their research data. Other reasons seem to play a less prominent role. While it is unlikely that any specific recommendations can (or should) reduce the obstacle of using the data for further publications, a high number of respondents selecting data protection requirements could also mean that they tend to err on the side of caution and rather not share data if there is uncertainty about breaking the requirement.

Figure 51. Reasons behind setting specific restrictions in respondents' current / latest research activity (share of respondents)

Source: own elaboration based on unweighted researchers' survey data, N = 3,494.

Nonetheless, reducing even the reasons less often indicated by researchers may increase data sharing. Time needed for depositing data may be one such area (most respondents indicated that they need up to 5 days to prepare data for depositing, see Section 3.5 for more details). Another area for improvement is the perceived likelihood of data misuse and/or misinterpretation. This possibly relates to the relative lack of attention given to data-related standards (see section 3.3). Improving adherence to them could possibly reduce of hesitation to share the data due to there being less room for misinterpretation and/or misuse. Finally, lack of awareness regarding where to upload data for sharing can also be remedied, even if only 9% of respondents selected it as a reason.

In terms of different country groups, responses from Associated Countries with lower income level show lower relevance of data protection requirements and commercial sensitivity of the data. Researchers from these countries also more often tend to 'save' their data for future publications, though there is more overlap if confidence intervals are considered. Certainly, specific aspects (e.g. relating to GDPR) may be less sensitive in non-EU countries due to the differences in legal frameworks.

Figure 52. Reasons behind setting specific restrictions in respondents' current / latest research activity by country group (share of respondents)

Source: own elaboration based on unweighted researchers' survey data, Total N=3,494, AC1 N=377, AC2 N=190, EU13 N=486, EU14 N=2,213, Other N=47, UK N=181. Note: respondents could select multiple answer options; columns illustrate the mean, while bars – confidence intervals in 95% level.

In terms of the different FOS, unsurprisingly, data protection requirements are the most prominent in Medical and Health Sciences and Social Sciences, which often involve human subjects. The difference is especially clear for medical and health research. On the other hand, less than a fourth of researchers in Natural Sciences indicate this reason for setting specific restrictions. For them (and for Agricultural Sciences) the opportunity to reuse for own further publications are however relatively more important than for other fields of science. Finally, research data in Natural Sciences and Agricultural Sciences seems to have the most commercially valuable data, as these fields of science tend to indicate it as the reason behind the restrictions more often than others. Researchers in these fields also indicate the commercial sensitivity of their data more often. In both cases, confidence interval assessment suggests actual difference among FOS.

Figure 53. Reasons behind setting specific restrictions in respondents' current / latest research activity by FOS (share of respondents)

Source: own elaboration based on unweighted researchers' survey data, Total N=3,494, Agricultural Sciences N=215, Engineering and Technology N=747, Humanities N=144, Medical and Health Sciences N=777, Natural Sciences N=946, Social Sciences N=665. Note: respondents could select multiple answer options; columns illustrate the mean, while bars – confidence intervals in 95% level.

Box 3-9. Insights from free-text data

When responding to the question on reasons behind setting restrictions, researchers also noted that:

- Confidentiality is a very important consideration, as are the ethical reasons
- Discipline and sub-discipline specifics can affect the level of research data accessibility, as noted by one respondent, data needed to be restricted “to protect endangered species”

Still others see the process of making data available as challenging or having limited benefits when considering opportunity costs:

- There are (regrettably many) cases where our team would love to share the data, public domain and no questions asked, but resigns in front of a quagmire of funding/stakeholder/metadata-ISO/GDPR/intellectual property/thesaurus/andwhatnot ramifications. At a given point, we just shove the data over to fellow groups' Dropbox under a 'with friendly permission' clause”
- “The effort in collecting good quality data, needs to be considered. We share data with research groups we trust and for shared objectives.”

Another respondent noted an imbalance between private and public sector data:

- “We need data from the private sector, that we do not get. The other way they use our public data. This is a problem. Respective ways so solve this in an easy way are unknown to scientists (licences, rights, etc)”

Source: researcher survey.

Who decides on the level of access?

Mostly, it is either researcher themselves or the team lead who decides on the level of access to be provided for the produced research data. There is also little variation among the different country groups, with researcher funder or legal requirements playing a less prominent role there. Otherwise, responses by researchers from different country groups are mostly similar.

Figure 54. Setters of the level of access of the data produced by respondents or their research teams in their current / latest research activity (share of respondents)

Source: own elaboration based on unweighted researchers' survey data, N = 9,711. Note: respondents could select multiple answer options.

3.4.4. Brief summary of the findings

There seems to be little consideration of access and reuse conditions, when deciding on whether to use or not use a particular research dataset or a research data repository, with this lack being especially prominent when it comes to research datasets. However, especially for the research datasets, over 40% of respondents indicated that they do not know or cannot answer the question, possibly suggesting a lack of awareness of the access and reuse conditions associated with individual datasets. The lack of knowledge about the impact of access and reuse conditions may imply that researchers consciously consider the conditions, but give priority to other characteristics (likely, such as the relevance of the data to their own research). In this case, raising awareness about the importance of access and reuse conditions could help improve understanding of the research data management procedures.

When reusing research data, two thirds of respondents indicated using data that was publicly available without restrictions. One difference that emerged was the less frequent use of publicly available data and more frequent need to provide ethical approval when asking to access data, by researchers working at private and public hospitals. This is also seen when looking at the field of science breakdown, where researchers from Medical and Health Sciences more often indicate the need to provide ethical approval than researchers from other fields.

When setting restrictions for their own (or their teams') research data, around three fourths of researchers indicated making or planning to make their data publicly accessible free of charge. As in the case of data reuse, researchers from Medical and Health Sciences indicate that they will require ethical approval more often than researchers from other fields. Researchers in Medical and Health Science also tend to make their data accessible only to specific groups or for specific purposes.

Research data is owned mostly either by researchers (their teams) or by their institutions. Here, geographic breakdown reveals variation in research practices. Ownership by researchers is more prominent in the Associated Countries, especially those with lower R&D spending, while employer's ownership is stronger in EU countries, especially in EU13. There are also differences in the EU, since researchers from South Western and Southern Eastern Europe indicate more frequent ownership of data by researchers, while researchers from North Western Europe indicated ownership by employers more frequently.

When setting licences for research data, researchers tend to require attribution, but even this was indicated only by slightly more than a fourth of respondents. This requirement seems to be especially prominent in Humanities.

The main reasons for setting restrictions on produced research data are researchers' plans to use the data in their own further publications and data protection requirements they have to meet. This latter reason, however, seems to be of lower importance in Associated Countries with lower R&D spending, possibly because they are less affected by data protection regulation that is relevant within the EU.

3.5. DATA DEPOSITING AND PRESERVATION

Box 3-10. Key findings on data depositing and preservation

- 40% of researchers occasionally stored data in research data repositories, while 22% respondents did that during the current/latest research activity.

- Research data repositories are not the most common destination for storing usable research data. Researchers usually stored data in personal physical data storage⁵ or institutional local data storage. Incentive to store data in repositories is related to the support for open science values rather than meeting policy requirements.
- Researchers usually store data to repositories after completion of the project or after the publication that uses the data is accepted (whichever comes first) (selected by 66% of researchers).
- The majority (57%) of surveyed researchers do not update the data deposited to repositories. They upload only the final dataset versions that are not updated afterwards. Less than a third (28%) of respondents update the deposited data with each new update of data.
- There is a clear tendency that researchers who deposit data in research data repositories intend to keep the deposited data for more than 10 years (74% of respondents).
- The majority of researchers (77%) reported that there were no costs associated with depositing the data to repositories.
- The majority of researchers spend up to five person days on average to prepare a dataset for depositing in a repository.

3.5.1. Researchers' awareness of research data repositories

Slightly over a fifth (22%) of respondents or their teams stored data in research data repositories during their current/latest research activity. However, there are researchers who have not stored data in research data repositories during the current/latest research activity, but did so in their earlier work. Hence, in total, 40% of researchers have stored data in the research data repositories. This shows that even researchers who deposit data in repositories are doing so occasionally and not in all of their research activities. To put these numbers into context, EOSC association's strategic innovation agenda has the target of 50% of research data from EOSC Association members should be deposited in repositories that is made as open as possible by 2025⁶.

The share of researchers depositing data in repositories varies by the familiarity with FAIR principles (see Figure 55 and Figure 56 below). Researchers who are familiar with FAIR and put them into practice deposit research data in repositories more often. However, awareness about FAIR does not necessarily increase the depositing in repositories, as the share of researchers depositing data does not differ significantly between researchers who

⁵ Data server, internal hard drive, flash drive, external hard drive, etc.

⁶ https://www.eosc.eu/sites/default/files/EOSC-SRIA-V1.0_15Feb2021.pdf

heard about FAIR principles, but do not put them into practise and researchers who are not aware of FAIR principles.

Figure 55. Share of those respondents who stored (or their teams stored) data in research data repositories during the current/latest research activity by familiarity with FAIR

Source: own elaboration based on unweighted researchers' survey data. Total N=10,914, I have never heard of the FAIR principles before now N=3,245, I have heard of the FAIR principles, but I am not very familiar with what they mean in a practical sense of them N=2,672, I am familiar with the FAIR principles and put them into practice N=1,499, I am familiar with them but do currently not put them into practice N=1,091

Figure 56. Share of those respondents who stored data in research data repositories at least once by familiarity with FAIR

Source: own elaboration based on unweighted researchers' survey data. Total N=10,914, I have never heard of the FAIR principles before now N=3,245, I have heard of the FAIR principles, but I am not very familiar with what they mean in a practical sense of them N=2,672, I am familiar with the FAIR principles and put them into practice N=1,499, I am familiar with them but do currently not put them into practice N=1,091

The practice of depositing data in repositories differs between the country groups. Larger share of researchers affiliated to institutions in EU14 and Associated Countries with higher

R&D spending (AC1) are storing data in repositories compared to other groups (see Figure 57 and Figure 58). In addition, while comparing the results in the EU countries, more researchers from North Western Europe (G2) and fewer researchers from South Eastern Europe (G5) store data in repositories. Both of these differences are confirmed by analysis of confidence intervals at 95% level.

Figure 57. Share of respondents who stored (or their teams stored) data in research data repositories during the current/latest research activity by country group

Source: own elaboration based on unweighted researchers' survey data. Total N=10,914, I have never heard of the FAIR principles before now N=3,245, I have heard of the FAIR principles, but I am not very familiar with what they mean in a practical sense of them N=2,672, I am familiar with the FAIR principles and put them into practice N=1,499, I am familiar with them but do currently not put them into practice N=1,091. Note: columns illustrate the mean, while bars – confidence intervals in 95% level.

Figure 58. Share of respondents who stored data in research data repositories at least once by country group

Source: own elaboration based on unweighted researchers' survey data. Total N=10,914, I have never heard of the FAIR principles before now N=3,245, I have heard of the FAIR principles, but I am not very familiar with what they mean in a practical sense of them N=2,672, I am familiar with the FAIR principles and put them into practice N=1,499, I am familiar with them but do currently not put them into practice N=1,091. Note: columns illustrate the mean, while bars – confidence intervals in 95% level.

The differences among countries could be related to more support and encouragement from research institutions. For example, the Netherlands are one of the few countries that has data stewards and is the country with one of the largest shares of respondents who deposit data to repositories (35% and 55%) together with Switzerland (40% and 57%) and the UK (33% and 53%). In addition, EU-14 and Western European research institutions are

usually ranked higher than EU-13 and Eastern European institutions ⁷. However, this hypothesis requires further analysis to be confirmed. Finally, the larger share of researchers depositing data might be related to overall digital performance of a country. We have looked into it by correlating values of DESI index values and the share of respondents who deposit data in repositories across EU countries with more than 50 responses⁸ (see Figure 59 and Figure 60 below). The results show positive, but weak correlation (Pearson correlation of 0.53-0.54), thus we cannot confidently say that digital performance has an impact on data depositing practices.

Figure 59. Correlation between DESI index and share of respondents who stored (or their teams stored) data in research data repositories during the current/latest

Source: own elaboration based on unweighted researchers' survey data and DESI index.

Figure 60. Correlation between DESI index and share of respondents who stored (or their teams stored) data in research data repositories at least once

7 E.g. top 20 European universities in the QS rankings are from UK, Switzerland, France, Germany, Netherlands, Belgium

8 We received fewer than 50 responses in the following EU countries: Cyprus, Luxembourg and Malta

Source: own elaboration based on unweighted researchers' survey data and DESI index.

The practise to deposit data in repositories also varies across FOS. Larger share of researchers working in Natural Sciences (especially in biological sciences, earth and related environmental sciences as well as computer and information sciences) and Humanities (especially in history and archaeology) store data in repositories (see Figure 61 and Figure 62). The difference remains after analysis of confidence intervals at 95% level.

Figure 61. Share of respondents who stored (or their teams stored) data in research data repositories during the current/latest research activity by FOS

Source: own elaboration based on unweighted researchers' survey data. Total N=10,914, Agricultural Sciences N=609, Engineering and Technology N=2,315, Humanities N=459, Medical and Health Sciences N=1,962, Natural Sciences N=3,258.

Figure 62. Share of respondents who stored data in research data repositories at least once by FOS

Source: own elaboration based on unweighted researchers' survey data. Total N=10,914, Agricultural Sciences N=609, Engineering and Technology N=2,315, Humanities N=459, Medical and Health Sciences N=1,962, Natural Sciences N=3,258.

In addition, the higher the research career stage, the larger the share of researchers who deposit data in repositories. The difference between first stage researchers and recognised, established, leading researchers is especially large (see more details in Figure 63 and Figure 64). The analysis of confidence intervals at 95% level shows that the differences exist only between first stage researchers and other career stages, as confidence intervals of other three career stages overlay. The reasons for these differences are explored in the later chapters on costs of depositing below.

Figure 63. Share of respondents who stored (or their teams stored) data in research data repositories during the current/latest research activity by career stage

Source: own elaboration based on unweighted researchers' survey data. Total N=10,914, First stage researcher (R1) N=986, Recognised researcher (R2) N=1,709, Established researcher (R3) N=3,553, Leading researcher (R4) N=3,682, Do not know/cannot answer N=155.

Figure 64. Share of respondents who stored data in research data repositories at least once by career stage

Source: own elaboration based on unweighted researchers' survey data. Total N=10,914, First stage researcher (R1) N=986, Recognised researcher (R2) N=1,709, Established researcher (R3) N=3,553, Leading researcher (R4) N=3,682, Do not know/cannot answer N=155.

Finally, public organisations⁹ are more inclined to store data in research data repositories compared to private organisations¹⁰. Companies are even less inclined to store data in the repositories (see more details in Figure 65 and Figure 66). These differences are confirmed after analysis of confidence intervals at 95% level. This could be related to the fact that companies and private institutions more often produce data that could be used for commercial purposes and thus is considered confidential.

Figure 65. Share of respondents who stored (or their teams stored) data in research data repositories during the current/latest research activity by sector of organisation

Source: own elaboration based on unweighted researchers' survey data. Total N=10,914, Private organisations (excluding companies) N=456, Public organisations N=9,971, Companies N=198.

⁹ Public universities, public hospitals, public research institutes, laboratories, or another public organisations.

¹⁰ Private universities, private hospitals, other private organisations (e.g. private laboratories).

Figure 66. Share of respondents who stored data in research data repositories at least once by sector of organisation

Source: own elaboration based on unweighted researchers' survey data. Total N=10,914, Private organisations (excluding companies) N=456, Public organisations N=9,971, Companies N=198.

It must be noted that research data repositories are not the most common destination for storing usable research data. Most researchers stored research data in personal physical data storage¹¹ or institutional local data storage¹². Storing data in institutional or personal cloud storage is less common, but still more common than storing data in research data repositories (see more details in Figure 67). These results are in line with the European University Association open science survey¹³ that shows that most surveyed institutions mostly use internal research data infrastructure. The data from a limited sample of this survey shows that members and observers of EOSC (26 respondents) more often have combined (combination of internal, external and/or shared) infrastructure for data storage. Thus, facilitating the engagement of research institutions with EOSC could increase the practice to share data at the institutional level and as a result could also encourage researchers to more often deposit data in research data repositories.

11 Data server, internal hard drive, flash drive, external hard drive, etc.

12 Data server, internal hard drive, flash drive, external hard drive

13 <https://www.eua.eu/downloads/publications/research%20data%20follow-up%20report.pdf>

Figure 67. Data storage locations of respondents or their research teams in their current / latest research activity (share of respondents)

Source: own elaboration based on unweighted researchers' survey data. Total N=10,914. Note: respondents could select multiple answer options.

The main reasons contributing to the decision to store data in repositories relates to the following:

- acceleration of scientific research / public benefit
- dissemination and continuous higher impact of your research
- personal support for openness in science

Other reasons (see Figure 68 for more details) were selected by less than half of researchers. The following differences (confirmed by analysis of confidence intervals at 95% level) were observed across different countries, FOS and research career stage (see Annex for more detail):

- More researchers from Associated Countries with a higher R&D spending (AC1) compared to other country groups were motivated by funder's policy requirement.
- Less researchers from Associated Countries with lower R&D spending (AC2) compared to other country groups were motivated by funder's policy requirement.
- Fewer researchers working in Engineering and Technology (especially mechanic and civil engineering) compared to other FOS were motivated by norms of the research community.
- Fewer researchers working in Engineering and Technology (especially in electrical engineering, electronic engineering, information engineering) and Humanities compared to other FOS were motivated by publisher's policy requirements.

- Fewer first stage researchers compared to other career stages were motivated by requests for access to data from other researchers.

The reasons behind these differences are not clear and could be analysed further in future research, as this does not fall under the scope of this study. However, the findings above show that the incentive to store data in repositories is related to the support for open science values rather than meeting policy requirements. The challenge is to align these values with practices. Policy requirements could be an option to increase the practise of depositing data in repositories, as in theory they should not be perceived negatively by researchers with the open science mindset.

Figure 68. Factors contributing to researchers' decision to store the data in research data repositories (share of respondents)

Source: own elaboration based on unweighted researchers' survey data. Total N=3,965. Note: respondents could select multiple answer options.

The respondents who stored data in the repository during the current/latest research activity usually used institutional research data repositories. International research data repositories and community databases/ repositories were also used by approximately a third of respondents. Other repository types were less popular (see Figure 69 for more details). Researchers affiliated to organisations from Associated Countries with lower R&D spending (AC2) used public research data repositories more often compared to other countries (this

is confirmed after looking at 95% level confidence intervals). No other significant differences were observed across different countries, FOS and research career stage.

Figure 69. Types of repositories used by researchers (share of respondents from those who indicated storing their usable data in research data repositories in their current / latest research activity)

Source: own elaboration based on unweighted researchers' survey data. Total N=2,397. Note: respondents could select multiple answer options.

The most important factor (chosen by almost half of respondents) for researchers while choosing a specific research data repository is its free of charge services. Presence of the continuity plan, certification, enabling users to discover the data and refer to them in a persistent way, respect for disciplinary and ethical norms as well as legal requirements relevant for researchers were also considered important when choosing repository by more than a third of respondents (see more details in Figure 70). The factors do not differ significantly across different countries, FOS or career stage.

Figure 70. Factors that contributed to choosing a specific research data repository (share of respondents)

Source: own elaboration based on unweighted researchers' survey data. Total N=3,964. Note: respondents could select multiple answer options.

3.5.2. Characteristics of the deposited data

Researchers usually store data to repositories after completion of the project or after the publication that uses the data is accepted (whichever comes first). This option was selected by 66% of researchers. Some researchers store data immediately (e.g. within a month) after production of data (selected by 21%) or after an embargo period (selected by 7%). Researchers noted that embargo period tends to last from less than one year to five years. The average embargo period mentioned by researchers was 1.93 years. Researchers working in natural sciences more often deposited data after the completion of the project compared to other FOS (confirmed by the analysis of confidence intervals). Otherwise, we did not observe significant differences between FOS both in terms of stage when data is depositing and the length of embargo period. The following differences between different country groups and career stages were observed:

- More researchers from EU13, Associated Countries with lower R&D spending and South Eastern Europe stored data to repositories immediately after the production of data compared to other country groups. While differences can be observed, confidence intervals do not confirm them.

- Fewer researchers from Associated Countries with lower R&D spending stored data to repositories after completion of the project. Although difference can be observed, it is not strongly supported by the confidence intervals.
- First stage researchers were more likely to store data immediately after the production of it and less likely to store data after completion of the project (this difference is confirmed by confidence interval analysis).

The reasons behind these differences are not clear and could be analysed further in future research, as this does not fall under the scope of this study.

The majority (57%) of surveyed researchers do not update the data deposited to repositories. They upload only the final dataset versions that are not updated afterwards. Less than a third of respondents update the deposited data with each new update of data (see more details in Figure 71). We did not collect data on whether the data deposited by researchers is longitudinal or not, but the finding about the frequency of updating data shows that it is likely that the majority of data is not longitudinal. That would explain why the majority of researchers do not update it in repositories.

More first stage researchers compared with other research stages update the data with each new update to the deposited data (difference confirmed by analysis of confidence intervals). No other significant differences were observed by country group, FOS and career stage.

Figure 71. Frequency of researchers or their research team updating (or intending to update) the data they uploaded to repositories in their current / latest research activities (share of respondents)

Source: own elaboration based on unweighted researchers' survey data. Total N=3,961.

There is a clear tendency that researchers who deposit data in research data repositories intend to keep the deposited data for more than 10 years (74% of respondents). Researchers working in natural sciences tend to do it even more often compared to other FOS (81%). Although a difference can be observed, it is not confirmed while looking at the confidence intervals. In addition, more researchers from EU14 and Associated Countries with higher R&D spending intend to keep their data for more than 10 years compared to EU13 and Associated Countries with lower R&D spending (differences confirmed by analysing confidence intervals). Researchers from South Eastern Europe (Slovenia,

Romania, Greece, Cyprus, Croatia, Bulgaria) intend to keep the data for more than 10 years less often than other country groups. However, this is not confirmed while analysing confidence intervals.

The main factors behind the decision to keep data for five years or more are in line with the factors motivating researchers to store data in research data repositories:

- acceleration of scientific research/ public benefit
- dissemination and continuous higher impact of their research
- personal support for openness in science

Other less motivating reasons do not fully follow the factors motivating researchers to store data in research data repositories (see Figure 72). There are also differences with regard to these factors across different countries, FOS and research career stage:

- Fewer researchers from EU14 compared to other county groups were motivated by research community norms. However, this is not confirmed while analysing confidence intervals.
- More researchers from Associated Countries with lower R&D spending were motivated by scientific society's policy or national policy requirements compared to other country groups. This is confirmed by confidence intervals.
- More researchers from Associated Countries with higher R&D spending compared to other country groups were motivated by funder's policy requirement. However, the difference not confirmed by confidence intervals.
- Researchers in agricultural sciences compared to other FOS were more motivated by publisher's policy requirement. While it is the opposite for researchers working in engineering and technology. However, although differences exist, they are not confirmed while analysing confidence intervals.
- Researchers working in humanities were more motivated by scientific society's policy compared to researchers in other FOS. However, although difference exists, it is not confirmed while analysing confidence intervals.

The reasons behind these differences are not clear and could be analysed further in future research, as this does not fall under the scope of this study.

Figure 72. Factors that contributed to the decision to store data for a long period of time (over 5 years) (share of respondents)

Source: own elaboration based on unweighted researchers' survey data. Total N=3,170. Note: respondents could select multiple answer options.

3.5.3. The costs of research data depositing

The majority of researchers (77%) reported that there were no costs associated with depositing data to repositories. This is the case for researchers affiliated to organisations in different country groups, FOS and career stage, as we found no significant differences among these groups of respondents. It must be noted that although the question was asked in the context of depositing data in research data repositories, some respondents could have interpreted that the question is not only about research data repositories, but about data depositing data (e.g. in personal or institutional storage) in general.

Respondents who had costs in depositing data are usually not aware whether these are one-time costs of depositing or recurring cost. One-time costs were slightly more common among the respondents who had costs in depositing data (see Figure 73 for more details). One-time costs ranged from 20 to 30 thousand euros. Recurring costs ranged from 1 to 100,000 euros. There are too few responses to compare values across different countries, FOS or career stage. The fact that many researchers did not know the costs is an interesting phenomenon. It might be the case that the costs part of depositing data is taken care of not by researchers themselves (e.g. by their institutions). This is something to be analysed in the future research.

Figure 73. Type of cost associated with depositing the data in respondents' current / latest research activity (share of respondents)

Source: own elaboration based on unweighted researchers' survey data. Total N=521. Note: respondents could select multiple answer options.

The costs of data depositing in a research data repository for the respondents who had these costs were usually covered by grants for research projects where data is produced or respondent's institution (see more details in Figure 74). Differences were observed while looking at different career stages. More first stage researchers selected that they themselves covered the costs of depositing. However, although the difference is observed, it is not confirmed while looking at the confidence intervals (see more details in Figure 74). The data also shows that the later the career stage the more likely that the costs of depositing were covered by grants for research projects (again these differences are not confirmed by confidence interval analysis, as it confirms the difference to be significant only between first stage researchers and leading researchers). In addition, researchers' institutions more often covered costs for data depositing for established and leading researchers (these differences are also not confirmed by confidence interval analysis). This could be related to awareness about opportunities to cover depositing costs. This could also be one of the reasons why less first stage researchers deposit data in research data repositories. It is important to further investigate this issue and ensure that first stage researchers would be well aware about the opportunities to deposit data in repositories and covering the costs of depositing data.

The sample size for this question is too small to compare the responses between countries and FOS, since many categories have less than 100 responses and some even less than 50 responses.

Figure 74. Ways to cover the costs of depositing data in a repository for respondents' or their research teams in current / latest research activity (share of respondents)

Source: own elaboration based on unweighted researchers' survey data. Total N=562. Note: respondents could select multiple answer options.

Figure 75. Ways to cover the costs of data depositing in a repository for respondents' or their research teams in current / latest research activity by career stage (share of respondents)

Source: own elaboration based on unweighted researchers' survey data. Total N=538, First stage researcher (R1) N=52, Recognised researcher (R2) N=83, Established researcher (R3) N=147, Leading researcher (R4) N=248, Do not know/cannot answer N=8. Note: respondents could select multiple answer options.

3.5.4. Time it takes to prepare research data for storage in a research data depository

Slightly more than half of researchers spend up to five person days on average to prepare a dataset for depositing in a repository. Almost a quarter of researchers did not know or

cannot answer this question. This was especially common for humanities researchers (although the difference in not knowing is observed, it is not confirmed by confidence intervals analysis), resulting in the situation where less of them spend 1-2 person days in preparing data compared to other FOS (supported by confidence intervals analysis). There are no significant differences between country groups, career.

Figure 76. Average time respondents or their research team members need to prepare a dataset for depositing in a repository (share of respondents)

Source: own elaboration based on unweighted researchers' survey data. Total N=3,962, Agricultural Sciences N=209, Engineering and Technology N=717, Humanities N=194, Medical and Health Sciences N=600, Natural Sciences N=1565, Social Sciences N=677. Note: columns illustrate the mean, while bars – confidence intervals in 95% level.

With regard to time needed to maintain a dataset in repository, most of the respondents either responded that no time is needed (41%) or did not know the time needed (45%). This is the line with the fact that 57% of respondents do not update data after uploading it to research data repository. It must also be noted that large share of respondents did not know the time needed to prepare dataset. While 'I do not know' responses are excluded, more researchers from Engineering and Technology (difference confirmed by analysing confidence intervals) as well as Medical and Health Sciences (difference observed, but not confirmed while analysing confidence intervals) compared to other FOS noted that they spent time to maintain datasets in repositories.

The number of days needed to maintain a dataset in repository indicated by researchers ranged from 1 to 365, with the average of 19 days and the median of 10 days¹⁴. However,

14 Assumptions while converting some responses to days, so they can be compared with other responses: (1) one day consist of 8 hours, (2) one week consist of 5 days, (3) one month consist of 21 days, (4) one year consist of 12 months.

the majority (66%) of researchers spent 10 days or less for maintaining the datasets (see Figure 77 below). The sample size is too small to break this down by different countries, FOS or career stage.

Figure 77. Time necessary for maintaining a dataset in a repository over a year by FOS (excluding I do not know answer option) (share of respondents)

Source: own elaboration based on unweighted researchers' survey data. Total N=547.

3.5.5. Brief summary of the findings

Two fifths of researchers occasionally stored data in research data repositories, while 22% of respondents did that during the current/latest research activity. The share of researchers depositing data in repositories vary by the familiarity with FAIR principles. Researchers who are familiar with FAIR and put them into practice deposit research data in repositories more often. However, awareness about FAIR does not necessarily increase the depositing in repositories, as the share of researchers depositing data does not differ between researchers who heard about FAIR principles, but do not put them into practise and researchers who are not aware of FAIR principles. Data is more often stored by researchers from EU14, Associated Countries with higher R&D spending, researchers working in Natural Sciences and Humanities, as well as researchers from public organisations. The differences among countries could be related to country digital performance, more support and encouragement from research institutions and the performance of research institutions in general. However, these relationships should be explored in other studies in order to confirm or reject them. In addition, the higher the research career stage, the larger the share of researchers' deposit data in repositories. Research data repositories are not the most common destination for storing usable research data. Researchers usually stored data in personal physical data storage or institutional local data storage. Incentive to store data in repositories is related to the support for open science values rather than meeting policy requirements.

Researchers usually stored data in institutional research data repositories, international research data repositories and community databases/ repositories. The most important factor (chosen by almost half of respondents) while choosing a specific research data repository is its free of charge services. Hence, ensuring that repositories are free of charge for researchers (e.g. by funding their operational costs) could contribute to more researchers depositing data in repositories. Presence of the continuity plan, certification, enabling users to discover the data and refer to them in a persistent way, respect for disciplinary and ethical norms as well as legal requirements were also considered important by more than a third of respondents.

Researchers usually store data to repositories after completion of the project or after the publication that uses the data is accepted (whichever comes first) (selected by 66% of researchers). The majority (57%) of surveyed researchers do not update the data deposited to repositories. They upload only the final dataset versions that are not updated afterwards. Less than a third (28%) of respondents update the deposited data with each new update of data. As a result, most of the respondent either responded that no time is needed (41%) or did not know the time needed (45%) to maintain a dataset in research data repository. Out of the researchers who do need time to maintain data in repository (14%), the majority (61%) spent 10 days or less for maintaining the datasets.

There is a clear tendency that researchers who deposit data in research data repositories intend to keep the deposited data for more than 10 years (74% of respondents). Researchers working in Natural Sciences tend to do it even more often compared to other FOS, while researchers from EU13, Associated Countries with lower R&D spending and South Eastern Europe (Slovenia, Romania, Greece, Cyprus, Croatia, Bulgaria) intend to keep the data for more than 10 years less often.

The majority of researchers (77%) reported that there were no costs associated with depositing the data to repositories. Researchers from Associated Countries with lower R&D spending and South Eastern Europe (Slovenia, Romania, Greece, Cyprus, Croatia, Bulgaria) more often had costs associated with depositing the data to repositories. Respondents who had costs in depositing data are usually not aware whether these are one-time costs of depositing or recurring cost. The costs of data depositing in a research data repository for the respondents who had these costs were usually covered by grants for research projects or respondent's institution. However, first stage researchers more often compared to researchers in other career stages covered the costs of depositing themselves. This could be one of the reasons why less first stage researchers deposit data in research data repositories. It is important to further investigate this issue and ensure that first stage researchers would be well aware about the opportunities to deposit data in repositories and covering the costs of depositing data.

The majority of researchers spend up to five person days on average to prepare a dataset for depositing in a repository. Almost a quarter of researchers did not know or cannot answer this question (especially common for humanities researchers, resulting in the

situation where less of them spend up to five days in preparing data compared to other FOS).

3.6. RECOMMENDATIONS

Finding: there is a need to raise general awareness about research data

Researcher survey results show that there is a limited awareness in terms of data production or access and reuse conditions associated with research datasets. Over half of the respondents could not say the size of typical datasets they produced or reused in their latest research activities, and around a third could not define the total volumes of research data that they work with. The lack of awareness of research data access and reuse conditions is also potentially challenging in terms of responsible research practices.

Possible actions:

Increased use of data stewardship and possibly requirements set by institutional review boards could help encourage researchers to consider the questions related to the data they work with. Support for data management planning would help researchers to better understand their own data and its management needs.

- Providing good practice examples related to research data management and data management planning, stressing the results of such activities, since researchers tend to be the most attracted to scientific and societal benefits.
- Embed practices (e.g. through setting up internal review boards) for checking for the ethical approval of data production, reuse, and sharing, ensuring that this also becomes embedded in researchers' minds.
- Monitor the change of researchers practices to identify the key gaps in the system, which could then be targeted.

Finding: data sharing is still below the EOSC targets

The main reasons contributing to the decision to store data in repositories relates to support for open science values rather than meeting policy requirements. The challenge is to align these values with practice. The share of researchers who store data in research data repositories is still low. Only around 40% of researchers occasionally stored data in research data repositories, while less than a fourth of respondents did that during the current / latest research activity. It is still below the aim of EOSC members in the EOSC association's strategic innovation agenda, suggesting a need for a change in current researchers' practices. The role of community in shaping researchers' practices is limited. Only a relatively low share of researchers indicate that research community norms encourage them to deposit research data, suggesting a possible path towards making them more open to sharing the data.

The most important factor (chosen by almost half of respondents) for researchers while choosing a specific research data repository is its free of charge services. More first stage researchers selected that they themselves covered the costs of depositing. The data also shows that the later the career stage the more likely that the costs of depositing were covered by grants for research projects. In addition, researchers' institutions more often covered costs for data depositing for established and leading researchers.

Researchers have indicated a number of reasons why they are less willing to make their data available, including data protection requirements, lack of time to prepare the data, and fear of misinterpretation or misuse. While these options were selected by fewer than a half of researchers, they still suggest areas that need improvement. Some of the obstacles may also be linked to the lower use of standards related to data handling.

Possible actions:

Support for data stewardship and awareness raising campaigns at national and institutional levels. Where there is institutional capacity, consider pooling resources at a higher level.

Support for the development networks of national or regional data stewards and competence centres where limited resources can be pooled and made available to support local support provision. This would allow institutions with lesser capacities to engage in data stewardship activities.

4. RESEARCH DATA FAIRNESS

Findable, accessible, interoperable, and reusable (FAIR) is not a binary concept and the process of making data FAIR must be viewed as a journey as well as a destination. Decisions taken by researchers over the entire research lifecycle have an impact on whether the resulting data can be made FAIR and available for future use. In this chapter, we explore the maturity of FAIR data practices to determine if there are trends emerging, commonalities or major disparities across different fields of science, career stages and in different countries or regions.

4.1. AWARENESS AND IMPORTANCE OF FAIR

To evaluate the overall awareness of the FAIR principles and their importance to researchers, we asked two questions. One question asked about respondents' familiarity with the FAIR Principles and the other asked respondents to rate how important the concepts underpinning the FAIR Principles are in relation to their research.

Box 4-1. Key findings on awareness and importance of FAIR

- More than a third of respondents have never heard of the FAIR Principles but the concepts underpinning the FAIR Principles resonate strongly with respondents

- Of those currently putting FAIR into practice, most are based in Associated Countries with higher R&D spending and Northern and North Western Europe
- Respondents from the Humanities and Natural Sciences report putting FAIR into practice slightly more frequently than in other disciplines
- Leading Researchers put FAIR into practice more than those at earlier stages of their careers
- The role most active in putting FAIR into practice are Research Software Engineers

4.1.1. Awareness of FAIR

Most respondents indicate at least some level of familiarity with the FAIR Principles (63%). Familiarity ranges from those who have just heard of the principles to those who currently put them into practice. These results are broadly comparable with the findings of the recent State of Open Data 2021¹⁵ which found that 66% of respondents had heard of the FAIR Principles. The State of Open Data surveys aim to assess researchers' data practices on a global level, with roughly a third of respondents to the 2021 survey from Europe. The results offer a useful comparison for benchmarking European researchers' practices.

While general awareness of the principles may be high amongst respondents, almost a third say they are not very familiar with what they actually mean, suggesting more work is needed to ensure that researchers and research support staff know what putting FAIR into practice actually entails. In addition, more than a third of respondents report that they have never heard of the FAIR principles before (38%).

Figure 78. Familiarity with the FAIR principles in relation to managing and sharing data (share of respondents)

Source: own elaboration based on unweighted researchers' survey data, N=11,849.

Almost a third of respondents (31%) say that they are familiar with the principles and 18% of these currently put them into practice with 13% saying they are familiar with them but do

¹⁵ Science, Digital; Simons, Natasha; Goodey, Greg; Hardeman, Megan; Clare, Connie; Gonzales, Sara; et al. (2021): The State of Open Data 2021. Digital Science. Report. <https://doi.org/10.6084/m9.figshare.17061347.v1>

not currently put them into practice. This tallies with the findings in the State of Open Data 2021 survey which reports that 28% of respondents are familiar with the principles. This is the highest proportion of researchers reporting familiarity with the principles since this question was first asked in the State of Open Data survey in 2018.

When looking at awareness of FAIR in different country types, the distribution is similar to the overall findings. The highest share of respondents indicating that they are familiar with FAIR and putting them into practice (20%) are based in Associated Countries with a higher R&D spending (AC1) and EU14 countries (18%). On an individual country level, respondents based in the Netherlands (35%), and Switzerland (29%) are well above average in terms of being familiar with and putting FAIR into practice¹⁶ which may suggest that data policies and guidance put in place by national funders such as the Dutch Research Council (NWO)¹⁷ and Swiss National Science Foundation (SNSF)¹⁸ are helping to increase both awareness and capabilities for implementing FAIR.

Figure 79. FAIR awareness by country group (share of respondents)

Source: own elaboration based on unweighted researchers' survey data, N=11849. Responses for all options are: n=7326 (EU14), n=1714 (EU13), n=1991 (AC1), n=695 (AC2), n=123 (other).

With regard to awareness levels across regional groupings, respondents working in North Western Europe (G2), Associated Countries with higher R&D spending (AC1), and Central Europe (G4) are the groups most familiar with FAIR principles and put them into practice. The shares of respondents choosing this option were 23%, 20% and 19% respectively. About 15% of respondents working in organisations based in South Eastern Europe (G5),

16 Only countries with more than 100 respondents to the question are listed here. Netherlands (n=123 of 351 responses), Switzerland (102 out of 353 responses).

17 <https://www.nwo.nl/en/research-data-management>

18 <https://www.snf.ch/en/dMILj9t4LNk8NwyR/topic/open-research-data>

South Western Europe (G3), and Associated Countries with lower R&D spending (AC2) indicate that they are both familiar with FAIR and put the principles into practice. While it is encouraging to see there is both familiarity with the principles and respondents who are putting them into practice, more than a third of respondents from all country types and groupings indicate they have never heard of the FAIR Principles. The largest share of respondents who have never heard of FAIR are respondents based in 'other' countries (48%) followed by respondents based in South Western Europe (G3) (41%). The lowest share of respondents indicating they have never heard of the principles are respondents based in North Western Europe (G2) (33%). The share of those who have never heard of the principles is highest among respondents from 'Other' countries which may suggest that efforts to increase the overall awareness of the FAIR Principles in Europe and Associated Countries is yielding results. Indeed, when asked if they were aware of the EU's Open Science policy, the majority of respondents indicate that they are aware of it to some extent (73%). However, the respondents from 'Other' countries are a small group (n=153) so this finding would benefit from investigation in future studies.

Figure 80. FAIR awareness by country group (share of respondents)

Source: own elaboration based on unweighted researchers' survey data, N=11726. Responses for all options are: n=917 (Group 1), n=1579 (Group 2), n=3332 (Group 3), n=2444 (Group 4), n=768 (Group 5), n=1991 (Group 6), n=695 (Group 7).

When looking across different FOS, levels of familiarity with the FAIR Principles are broadly like the overall distribution except for those reporting familiarity with the principles and putting them into practice. The share of respondents from the Humanities and Natural Sciences reports slightly higher levels of putting FAIR into practice than those from other FOS (26% and 22% respectively compared with a share of between 15-16% for other FOS).

Figure 81. FAIR awareness by first level FOS (share of respondents)

Source: own elaboration based on unweighted researchers' survey data, N=10910. Responses for all options are: n=2494 (Social Sciences), n=3649 (Natural Sciences), n=1946 (Medical and Health Sciences), n=496 (Humanities), n=2650 (Engineering and Technology), n=614 (Agricultural Sciences).

When looking at awareness of FAIR at the level of the secondary FOS, the pattern within sub-domains is broadly similar to that seen in the first field of science. Among those putting FAIR into practice, the highest shares are seen among the 120 respondents from History and Archaeology in the Humanities (30%) and the 738 respondents from Earth and related environmental sciences in the Natural Sciences (28%). The number of respondents varies significantly across the second fields of science so these findings should not be considered conclusive but rather indicative of where further study may be beneficial. Visualisations of the findings for the first and second fields of science are included in the Annex.

There is very little variation in awareness of the FAIR principles among the first three career stages (R1-R3). Leading Researchers (R4) indicate that they put FAIR into practice slightly more than their more junior counterparts (21% compared with 16% for each of the other stages). Leading researchers are more likely to lead on funded projects and accordingly may have had more exposure to funding body expectations for research data management and the production of FAIR data. This seems to be borne out in Figure 83 which shows that Principal Investigators report putting FAIR into practice more than Researchers (20% compared with 16%).

Figure 82. FAIR awareness by career stage (share of respondents)

Source: own elaboration based on unweighted researchers' survey data. N=11516. Responses for all options are: n=1146 (First Stage Researcher (R1)), n=1986 (Recognised Researcher (R2)), n=4138 (Established Researcher (R3)), n=4246 (Leading Research (R4)).

Looking at awareness of FAIR across different roles, the pattern is again very similar to the overall distribution except when it comes to those researchers who tend to work predominantly on their own. This group appears to be the least familiar with FAIR (52% of whom have never heard of the principles) and are well below average when it comes to putting FAIR into practice (9%). Those who are most familiar with the principles are Research Software Engineers with just over a quarter indicating that they also put FAIR into practice. However, those who identify their role as Research Software Engineers are a small portion of the overall respondents (n=501, 4%) so a more in-depth study of this particular group might be worthwhile.

Figure 83. FAIR awareness by role (share of respondents)

Source: own elaboration based on unweighted researchers' survey data. N=18808. Please note respondents could choose more than one option. Responses for each option are: n=6975 (Researcher), n=4556 (Research Manager), n=5492 (Principal Investigator), n=600 (Technical Staff), n=501 (Research Software Engineer), n=684 (Work Individually).

Some of the free text options provided by survey respondents state that there are lingering misconceptions around the meaning of FAIR. One respondent indicated that, as they work with sensitive data, they cannot share or make their data FAIR. Others questioned whether the FAIR principles apply to all fields of science. These misconceptions were also highlighted in a report from the EOSC Working Group on FAIR¹⁹. This suggests that there is still a need for more general awareness raising to reinforce the relevance of the FAIR principles across all disciplines and to dispel misconceptions that FAIR data must also be open data. While the study findings show that general awareness of the EU's Open Science policy is relatively high, a number of free text comments were provided stating that such policies can be seen as burdensome by researchers and that they distract researchers from doing their actual research. As shown in Chapter 3, policy compliance is not the main reason that researchers share their data. Instead, accelerating scientific research and realising public good are the key drivers for researchers.

Box 4-2. Misconception of FAIR from free-text data

- Some qualitative data cannot be shared...this is not a matter of not adhering to FAIR principles, it is that FAIR principles have not correctly understood and taken into account the sensitivity and nature of all sorts of data.

19 Chue Hong, Neil, Cozzini, Stefano, Genova, Françoise, Hoffman-Sommer, Marta, Hooft, Rob, Lembinen, Liisi, Marttila, Juuso, & Teperek, Marta. (2020). Six Recommendations for Implementation of FAIR Practice (Final, pre-typesetting). Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.4065549>

- The principles of open research data are prejudicial to qualitative research with vulnerable participants. Protecting the confidentiality of those participants has to take precedence of the needs of open science.
- I am not sure that FAIR corresponds to anthropological research.

Source: researcher survey.

4.1.2. Importance of being FAIR

The survey aims to identify levels of self-reported FAIR awareness and current maturity of FAIR practice but also to gain insights into how researchers feel about making their data FAIR. About two thirds of respondents say that it is important to them that other researchers are able to **find** their data (70%), **access** their data (64%), and that other researchers are able to **connect** to their data (62%). Interestingly, a slightly lower share of respondents say it is important to them that their data is **reusable** (57%) suggesting that the potential to have their data found and cited may be a more powerful driver than reuse. However, as more than two thirds of those researchers who deposit data with a repository say they do so to support the acceleration of scientific research/public benefit, one might expect the importance of reusability to have been rated more highly than it is. It is worth noting that for all factors shown in Figure 84, only a small minority of respondents considered the issues to be 'not important'. This suggests that while many may not have heard of the FAIR Principles before, the concepts behind them resonate with many respondents.

Figure 84. Importance of findable, accessible, interoperable and reusable data (share of respondents)

Source: own elaboration based on unweighted researchers' survey data, N=10900-10910 depending on the option.

As shown in Table 9, the importance of being FAIR across different country types shows a similar pattern to the overall distribution with all types indicating that the findability of their data is most important (ranging from 66% of EU13 respondents choosing this option to 81% of those based in 'other countries'). Accessibility was seen as the second most important factor among the different country types. The third most important factor is to enable other researchers to connect their research data to the respondent's data and the least important

factor is data reusability. Only respondents from Associated Countries with a lower R&D spending (AC2) rated the ability to connect data as being the second most important factor (69%). A very small minority of respondents from all country types feel that any of these factors are 'not important' (<10%).

Table 9. Importance of FAIR data by country type (% of respondents from each country type selecting the option 'important' for each factor)

Country Type	Findability is important	Accessibility is important	Being able to connect is important	Reusability is important
EU14	71%	65%	63%	58%
EU13	66%	58%	57%	51%
AC1	68%	63%	58%	56%
AC2	74%	67%	69%	62%
Other	81%	72%	67%	67%

Source: own elaboration based on unweighted researchers' survey data, N=10900-10910. Range of responses for all options are: n=6734-6737 (EU14), n=1579-1584 (EU13), n=1819-1821 (AC1), n=651-655 (AC2), n=115 (other). Note: The highest rated factor is shaded violet and the lowest rated is shaded green.

The overall pattern remains constant at the regional level. However, respondents based in Northern and Central European countries (Groups 1 and 4) chose 'neutral' and 'not important' for each factor more often than those in other regions. However, it should be noted that more than half of the respondents from these regions still said that all of the factors were 'important'.

Table 10. Importance of FAIR data by region (combined % of respondents from each group selecting the options 'not important' and 'neutral')

Region	Findability - neutral or not important	Accessibility - neutral or not important	Being able to connect- neutral or not important	Reusability - neutral or not important
Northern Europe (Group 1)	35%	40%	41%	44%
North Western Europe (Group 2)	26%	30%	34%	37%
South Western Europe (Group 3)	25%	30%	26%	36%
Central Europe (Group 4)	31%	39%	44%	47%
South Eastern Europe (Group 5)	25%	30%	26%	35%
Associated Countries with higher R&D spending (Group 6)	29%	33%	36%	39%
Associated Countries with lower R&D spending (Group 7)	22%	28%	26%	32%

Source: own elaboration based on unweighted researchers' survey data, N=10785-10795. Responses for all options are: n=850-852 (Group 1), n=1440-1442 (Group 2), n=3041-3042 (Group 3), n=2261-2265 (Group 4), n=720-722 (Group 5), n=1819-1821 (Group 6), n=651-655 (Group 7). Note: The highest rated factor is shaded violet and the lowest rated is shaded green.

When exploring the importance of being FAIR by field of science, a similar pattern to the overall distribution emerges. The majority of respondents from all disciplines think that it is most important that other researchers can **find** their data. The share of respondents indicating that data findability is important is lowest among the Social Sciences (57%) who

also have the highest share of respondents who say that the findability of their data is not important (10%). Given the relatively long history of using data repositories in the Social Sciences, this is somewhat surprising. There is a slight deviation from the pattern among the responses from the Agricultural Sciences and Medical and Health Sciences who both indicate that others being able to connect is the second most important factor compared with accessibility of data which was rated second most important by all other fields of science.

Table 11. Importance of FAIR data by primary FOS (% of respondents from each FOS selecting the option ‘important’ for each factor)

Field of Science	Findability is important	Accessibility is important	Being able to connect is important	Reusability is important
Agricultural Sciences	74%	65%	69%	55%
Engineering and Technology	69%	62%	59%	58%
Humanities	78%	72%	70%	65%
Medical and Health Sciences	69%	61%	65%	52%
Natural Sciences	77%	73%	65%	64%
Social Sciences	57%	53%	53%	48%

Source: own elaboration based on unweighted researchers’ survey data. N=10785-10795. Responses for all options are: n=850-852 (Group 1), n=1440-1442 (Group 2), n=3041-3042 (Group 3), n=2261-2265 (Group 4), n=720-722 (Group 5), n=1819-1821 (Group 6), n=651-655 (Group 7). Note: The highest rated factor is shaded violet and the lowest rated is shaded green.

4.1.3. Brief summary of the findings

When looking at awareness with the FAIR principles by country type, region, first field of science, career stage, and role, there is very little variation from the overall distribution. Just under a fifth are aware and currently put FAIR into practice (average is 18% across all breakdowns). The highest levels of putting FAIR into practice are to be seen in respondents based in Associated Countries with higher R&D spending. Of those putting FAIR into practice, respondents in the Humanities and Natural Sciences are slightly more active than other FOS. There is little variation in awareness levels across the first three career stages, however respondents who are Leading Researchers indicate slightly more often that they are familiar with FAIR and put the principles into practice. While it is encouraging to see that awareness of the FAIR principles and putting them into practice is increasing, the fact that more than two thirds of respondents have not heard of the FAIR principles or do not fully understand what they mean suggests that efforts to raise awareness and general training on FAIR is still very necessary. The concepts underpinning the FAIR principles resonate deeply with the majority of respondents and there is also a strong desire among respondents to make their data available to support the acceleration of science and for public benefit rather than to simply comply with funding body mandates. As such, any future efforts to raise awareness about FAIR data sharing should emphasise how FAIR-aligned practices support the acceleration of science and public benefit.

4.2. FAIR PRACTICES

The survey asked respondents to indicate how common it is for them to undertake practical activities related to making data FAIR. This question deliberately avoided referencing the FAIR Principles and presented respondents with a matrix of nine FAIR-aligned practices.

Box 4-3. Key findings on awareness and importance of FAIR

- Looking for data to reuse is the most common FAIR-aligned practice
- Almost three quarters of respondents develop DMPs at least some of the time. However as other FAIR-aligned activities are less common there may be a disconnect between what is planned at the outset of research and what is actually carried out.
- More than two thirds of respondents make use of researcher identifiers such as ORCIDs
- About a third of respondents never deposit their data with a repository. Of those who do use repositories, the highest shares are among respondents from the Natural Sciences and Humanities
- Assigning licences to datasets is less common than other practices
- Allocating persistent identifiers to software is the least frequent FAIR-aligned practice

It appears that FAIR-aligned practices are becoming more common with more than half of respondents indicating that they 'sometimes' or 'always' carry out seven of the nine activities listed. Bucking this trend, fewer than half of respondents indicate that they assign a licence to their datasets and just under a third acquire persistent identifiers (PIDs) for software. For the latter, more than half of respondents indicate that they never acquire a PID for their software.

Figure 85. Frequency of carrying out specific FAIR-related activities

Source: own elaboration based on unweighted researchers' survey data, N=10,868-10,889, depending on option.

In the next section, we provide a deeper exploration of each of the FAIR-aligned activities shown in Figure 85. The activities have been grouped below to reflect their relation to the FAIR Principles.'

4.2.1. Planning for FAIR data

Good data management is crucial for ensuring that FAIR data is produced and is best realised through the development and updating of data management plans. Almost three quarters of respondents indicate that they develop data management plans when starting their research (42% of respondents sometimes develop DMPs and 31% always develop DMPs). This is higher than expected – second only to searching for data to reuse which is the most common FAIR-aligned practice – and seems to suggest that attitudes towards DMPs are becoming more positive. This tallies with the findings of a recent EC study which found that 82% of those who created DMPs for their H2020 project found developing DMPs useful or somewhat useful beyond it being an EC requirement²⁰.

²⁰ Spichtinger D. Data Management Plans in Horizon 2020: what beneficiaries think and what we can learn from their experience [version 1; peer review:2 approved, 1 approved with reservations] Open Research Europe 2021,1:42. <https://doi.org/10.12688/openreseurope.13342.1>

Table 12. Frequency of developing DMPs (rounded averages are shown for each breakdown)

Breakdown of respondents	Never	Sometimes	Always	Don't know / cannot answer
Full cohort (n=15066)	23%	42%	31%	4%
Country Type (n=15066)	17%	41%	38%	4%
Regional Groupings (n=15066)	21%	42%	34%	4%
Field of Science (n=15066)	22%	41%	33%	4%
Career Stage (n=11516)	21%	41%	32%	4%

Source: own elaboration based on unweighted researchers' survey data.

The overall pattern is similar when looking at the respondents by country group however, the share of respondents from EU14 countries appears to be slightly less active than respondents based in other country types. More than a quarter of respondents based in EU14 countries say they never develop a DMP (27% compared with 9%-20% of respondents based in other country types). For the majority of individual countries, the highest share of respondents indicate that they develop DMPs 'sometimes'. For eight countries though the share of respondents indicating that they 'always' develop DMP was higher than for any of the other options²¹. These include Romania, Turkey, Ukraine, Finland, the UK, the Netherlands, Greece and those based in 'other' countries. This may be due to the fact that most of these countries have national Open Science initiatives, strategies and/or national funding body mandates for producing data management plans. However, other countries which also have national Open Science strategies, initiatives and/or funding body mandates report lower shares of respondents who always develop DMPs. Respondents based in France, Germany, and Italy reported among the lowest shares of those who 'always' develop DMPs (20%, 21% and 26% respectively). A landscape survey carried out by EOSC Pillar found that Universities in France, Germany and Italy tended to have few formal policies for research data which may suggest that local

²¹ Please note that only countries with more than 100 respondents were included in this list.

policies and related support is as important when it comes to translating national policies into research practice²².

Figure 86. Frequency of developing a data management plan (DMP) by country group (share of respondents)

Source: own elaboration based on unweighted researchers' survey data, N=10,888.

There is little variation from the overall distribution when looking at the development of data management plans across the different FOS. Respondents from the Natural Sciences develop DMPs slightly less often than their peers in other FOS (67% sometimes or always develop DMPs compared with 71%-78% in other fields). Those from Natural Sciences also had the highest share of saying that they never develop a DMP (28%).

Figure 87. Frequency of developing a data management plan (DMP) across FOS (share of respondents)

Source: own elaboration based on unweighted researchers' survey data, N=10,888.

22 Bodlos, Anita, Hönegger, Lisa, Kaczmirek, Lars, Beckmann, Volker, Breton, Vincent, Romier, Geneviève, van Wezel, Jos, Streit, Achim, Stevanovic, Uros, Galeazzi, Fulvio, Tanlongo, Federica, & Van Nieuwerburgh, Inge. (2020). EOSC-Pillar D3.1 Summary report of the EOSC-Pillar National Initiatives Survey. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.3937318>

There is little variation when it comes to developing data management plans across the different career stages however, those who identify as Leading Researchers (R4) are slightly more likely to develop DMPs than researchers at other career stages (75% always or sometimes develop DMPs compared with 71%-72% of researchers at other stages of their career). As noted in the previous section, this may be due to the fact that Leading Researchers tend to be those who lead on funded projects and may have greater exposure to the requirements of funding bodies and institutions.

4.2.2. Findable and accessible data

The use of repositories and persistent identifiers are crucial for ensuring that research outputs can be found and, where appropriate, accessed. The choices researchers make about where to deposit their data also plays a vital role in ensuring that data can be kept FAIR over time and directly influences the availability of FAIR data products for consumption.

Depositing data with repositories

When it comes to depositing data with a repository, just under a fifth of all respondents state that they always deposit their data with a repository (18%) and about a third indicate that they never deposit their data with a repository (34%), suggesting that the pool of research data currently available to find for potential reuse is far less than it should be. The overall pattern is consistent across different country types, regional groupings, fields of science and career stages.

Table 13. Frequency of depositing data with a repository (share of respondents, rounded averages are shown for each breakdown)

Breakdown of respondents	Never	Sometimes	Always	Don't know / cannot answer
Full cohort (n=15066)	34%	40%	18%	8%
Country Type (n=15066)	35%	38%	16%	11%
Regional Groupings (n=15066)	34%	39%	18%	9%
Field of Science (n=15066)	34%	40%	18%	8%
Career Stage (n=11516)	35%	39%	18%	9%

Source: own elaboration based on unweighted researchers' survey data.

When looking at the use of repositories within the different country types, respondents based in EU13 countries had the highest share of those saying that they never deposit their data (41%). This group was also below average with regard to the share of respondents saying that they always deposit their data with a repository (12% compared to the average of 16%). The share of respondents based in EU14, Associated Countries with higher R&D spending, and Associated Countries with a lower R&D spending were above average when it comes to always depositing their data with a repository (18%, 21% and 19% respectively). Regionally, those based in North Western Europe and Associated Countries with higher R&D spending had the highest shares of those who always deposit their data with repositories (21% each compared with a regional average of 18%). Respondents based in Northern Europe, South Eastern Europe and South Western Europe were below average (13%, 14% and 16% respectively). The share of respondents from South Eastern Europe (Group 5) cited the lack of data repositories as a barrier more often than those from other regional groupings which may account for the slightly below average use of data repositories.

Across the different FOS, the pattern is broadly similar with the highest share in all fields saying that they ‘sometimes’ or ‘always’ deposit their data with a repository. Respondents from the Natural Sciences are most likely to deposit their data with a repository (44% sometimes do this and 23% always do this) closely followed by researchers in the Humanities (41% sometimes deposit data with a repository and 22% always do). The highest share of respondents indicating that they never deposit their data with a repository are respondents from the Social Sciences (41%) followed by those in the Medical and Health Sciences (38%). This may be due to the fact that researchers in these domains tend to work with personally sensitive data and may require specialist services.

Figure 88. Frequency of depositing data with repositories across FOS (share of respondents)

Source: own elaboration based on unweighted researchers’ survey data, N=10,873.

The overall pattern is similar when looking at the use of repositories by career stage with more than half of respondents at all stages saying they deposit their data ‘sometimes’ or

'always'. Leading Researchers (R4) are most likely to deposit their data with a repository (61% do this 'sometimes' or 'always'). This group also has the lowest share of respondents indicating that they never deposit their data with a repository (31% compared with 35%-36% of respondents at other career stages). First Stage Researchers (R1) were those with the lowest share of respondents who 'sometimes' or 'always' deposit their data with a repository (51%). This may suggest that there is a need to increase awareness about the range of data repositories available for data deposit and the associated benefits of using repositories in doctoral level training.

Use of persistent identifiers

The survey asked respondents to indicate how often they make use of a range of unique and persistent identifiers. Overall, more than two thirds of respondents say that they 'sometimes' or 'always' use researcher identifiers such as ORCID's (68%). Acquiring PIDs for data is less common but half of respondents do this to some extent (50%). Just under a third of respondents indicate that they 'sometimes' or 'always' acquire a PID for their software/code. It is worth noting that almost a fifth of respondents could not provide an answer to the question about whether they acquired PIDs for their software/code (18%).

Table 14. Frequency of using unique and persistent identifiers for data, software/code, and researchers (share of respondents, rounded averages are shown for each breakdown)

Breakdown	How often do you make use of unique and persistent identifiers for:											
	Never			Sometimes			Always			Don't know / cannot answer		
	Data	Code	Researcher	Data	Code	Researcher	Data	Code	Researcher	Data	Code	Researcher
Full cohort (n=15066)	41%	51%	25%	31%	22%	33%	19%	9%	35%	9%	18%	7%
Country Type (n=15066)	34%	43%	22%	33%	26%	33%	23%	11%	37%	10%	20%	8%
Regional Groupings (n=15066)	39%	49%	24%	33%	23%	34%	20%	9%	35%	9%	19%	8%
Field of Science (n=15066)	40%	50%	24%	32%	23%	34%	19%	9%	36%	9%	19%	7%
Career Stage (n=11516)	40%	50%	24%	31%	23%	32%	19%	9%	37%	9%	18%	7%

Source: own elaboration based on unweighted researchers' survey data.

When looking at those who always acquire **persistent identifiers for data** across different country types, the average is just under a quarter (23%). Respondents based in Associated Countries with a lower R&D spending and those based in 'other' countries had an above average share of respondents saying that they always acquire a PID for their data (32%

and 26% respectively). EU14 countries have the largest above average share of respondents saying that they never acquire a PID for their data (46% against the average of 34%). Similarly, the regions with above average shares of respondents saying they never acquire a PID for their data are South Western and North Western Europe (47% and 45% respectively against an average of 39%). Associated Countries with a lower R&D spending were well below the average (23% never acquire PIDs for their data).

On average about a fifth of respondents across different fields of science report that they always apply a globally unique identifier to their data (19%). The share of respondents from the Agricultural Sciences are most active in acquiring PIDs for their data (24%) and the share of respondents from the Social Sciences least active (16%). Respondents from the Social Sciences are less likely to make use of repositories, which may be the reason that they also have a lower share of those who always acquire a PID for their data. When considering career stages, there is little variation between stages except for the share of those saying they never acquire PIDs for data. Established Researchers (R3) had an above average share of those who never acquire PIDs for data (46%) while First Stage Researchers (R1) had a below average share (36%). A recent EUA report revealed that a number of European Universities have introduced data-related skills training at the masters and doctoral levels which may account for the slightly higher share of First Stage Researchers making use of a range of identifiers.²³

Figure 89. Frequency of acquiring a persistent identifier (PID) for data across FOS (share of respondents)

Source: own elaboration based on unweighted researchers' survey data, N=10,889.

A much smaller average of respondents across the different FOS indicate that they always acquire a globally unique identifier for their software or code (9%) suggesting that this is an area where further support and guidance is needed. The share of respondents from Engineering and Technology are slightly more active than their peers in other FOS (11%

23 From principles to practices: Open Science at Europe's universities 2020-2021 EUA Open Science Survey results. <https://eua.eu/resources/publications/976:from-principles-to-practices-open-science-at-europe%E2%80%99s-universities-2020-2021-eua-open-science-survey-results.html>

always acquire a PID for software/code compared with between 7-9% in other fields of science). Looking at career stages, there is an above average share of Established Researchers who never acquire PIDs for software/code (56%) while the share of First Stage Researchers (R1) is below average (45%).

Figure 90. Frequency of acquiring a persistent identifier (PID) for software/code across FOS (share of respondents)

Source: own elaboration based on unweighted researchers' survey data, N=10,878.

Just over two thirds of respondents say they 'always' or 'sometimes' make use of a researcher identifier such as an ORCID (35% and 33% respectively). Across the different FOS, the pattern is broadly similar. However, always using a research identifier appears to be slightly more frequent among respondents from the Agricultural and Medical and Health Sciences (41% and 39% respectively compared to an average of 36%). When looking at those who never make use of a researcher identifier, Social Sciences and Engineering and Technology have a slightly above average share (28% and 27% respectively compared against the average of 24%).

Figure 91. Frequency of using researcher identifiers across FOS (share of respondents)

Source: own elaboration based on unweighted researchers' survey data, N=10,878.

4.2.3. Interoperable data

The use of controlled vocabularies and community standards for data and metadata are important for enabling interoperability. The use of community standards is slightly more common with more than a quarter of respondents indicating that they always use standards compared with about a fifth who say they always use controlled vocabularies. About a third of respondents say they never use controlled vocabularies compared with a quarter who say they never use community standards. The overall pattern is similar across all breakdowns.

Table 15. Frequency of using controlled vocabularies and standards (share of respondents, rounded averages are shown for each breakdown)

Breakdown	How often do you use controlled vocabularies and community standards?							
	Never		Sometimes		Always		Don't know / cannot answer	
	Vocabularies	Standards	Vocabularies	Standards	Vocabularies	Standards	Vocabularies	Standards
Full cohort (n=15066)	35%	26%	34%	35%	19%	27%	12%	12%
Country Type (n=15066)	32%	24%	34%	34%	20%	28%	13%	14%
Regional Groupings (n=15066)	34%	25%	34%	35%	20%	27%	12%	13%
Field of Science (n=15066)	32%	25%	35%	35%	21%	28%	12%	13%
Career Stage (n=11516)	34%	25%	34%	35%	20%	27%	12%	12%

Source: own elaboration based on unweighted researchers' survey data.

The share of respondents based in Associated Countries with a lower R&D spending are above average when it comes to always using controlled vocabularies (25% compared with the average of 20%). This group also has a below average share of respondents who report never using controlled vocabularies (27% compared with an average of 32%). Respondents based in EU14 countries have an above average share of respondents who never make use of controlled vocabularies (36%). A similar pattern is seen at the regional level. Respondents based in South Western Europe have the highest above average share of those who never make use of controlled vocabularies (38% compared with an average of 34% for regional groupings).

When looking at the use of controlled vocabularies across different fields of sciences, respondents from the Humanities were above average with more than a quarter (27%) indicating that they always use controlled vocabularies to describe their data compared with an average of 21%. Respondents from Engineering and Technology had a below average

share of those indicating that they always use controlled vocabularies (15%). Respondents from Engineering and Technology and those who work in the Social Sciences have an above average share of respondents who say they never make use of controlled vocabularies (37% each compared with an average of 32%). Respondents from the Humanities and Agricultural Sciences had below average share of respondents who say they never use controlled vocabularies (25% and 27% respectively). There is little variation across career stages, however Established Researchers (R3) were above average in the share of respondents who never use controlled vocabularies (39% compared with an average of 34%) while First Stage Researchers (R1) had a below average share (30%).

Figure 92. Frequency of using controlled vocabularies across FOS (share of respondents)

Source: own elaboration based on unweighted researchers' survey data, N=10,876.

With regards to describing data, almost two thirds of respondents indicate that they 'sometimes' or 'always' make use using community standards (62%). This is far higher than the share of those who answered a similar question about the use of standards in their current research (38% as discussed in Chapter 3). Indeed, when it comes to using community standards, it is far more common for respondents to make use of methodological standards than data description standards.

There is little variation at the country level, however respondents from Associated Countries with lower R&D spending have an above average share of those who indicate that they always use community standards to describe their data. This group also had the lowest share of those who say they never use community standards. A similar picture emerges when looking at different regional groupings.

When looking across different FOS, the overall pattern is similar to what is seen in the high-level distribution. Respondents from the Humanities have an above average share of those indicating that they always use community standards (36% compared with an average of 28%) as do the share of respondents from the Natural Sciences (32%). Respondents from Engineering and Technology have a below average share of those who say they always use community standards (21%) but this group has an above average share of those who

say they sometimes make use of them (40% compared with an average of 35%). These findings tally with those presented in Chapter 3.

Figure 93. Frequency of using community standards for data or metadata across FOS (share of respondents)

Source: own elaboration based on unweighted researchers' survey data, N=10,876.

There is little variation among the different career stages except that First Stage Researchers (R1) had a below average share of those who say they never make use of community standards (21% compared with an average of 25%). This seems in line with the findings in section 3.3 which show that younger researchers (those aged 26-35) were slightly more likely to make use of standards to describe their data.

4.2.4. Reusable data

A key aim for the production of FAIR data is that it can be used to support new research. To this end, the survey asked respondents to indicate how frequently they look for data to reuse when starting new research and whether they assign licences to their own datasets.

Looking for data to reuse

The vast majority of respondents indicate they look for existing data to reuse in new research activities (35% always do this and a further 50% sometimes do this). Just under a third of those respondents who stated that they did not check for existing data to reuse in the production section of the survey indicate here that they 'always' or 'sometimes' look for data to reuse (31%). Similarly, of the large share of those who left the question in the production section of the survey blank (67%) indicate that they 'always' or 'sometimes' look for data to reuse. Accordingly, it is difficult to gauge the accuracy of this finding. Only 13% of respondents say that they never look for existing data to reuse. As shown in section 3.4, the majority of respondents favour reusing data that are freely accessible without any restrictions (68%) while a smaller share tends to reuse data that are licenced with Creative Commons licences (29%).

Table 16. Frequency of looking for data to reuse (share of respondents, rounded averages are shown for each breakdown)

Breakdown	How often do you look for data to reuse and assign licences to your own data?							
	Never		Sometimes		Always		Don't know / cannot answer	
	Look for data	Licence data	Look for data	Licence data	Look for data	Licence data	Look for data	Licence data
Full cohort (n=15066)	13%	40%	50%	28%	35%	17%	2%	15%
Country Type (n=15066)	11%	36%	50%	29%	37%	19%	2%	16%
Regional Groupings (n=15066)	12%	39%	50%	28%	35%	17%	2%	16%
Field of Science (n=15066)	13%	39%	50%	28%	36%	18%	2%	15%
Career Stage (n=11516)	13%	39%	51%	28%	35%	18%	2%	15%

Source: own elaboration based on unweighted researchers' survey data.

The majority of respondents from all fields of science look for data to reuse 'sometimes' or 'always' (ranging from 80%-91%). Respondents from the Humanities indicate that they always look for data to reuse slightly more frequently than their peers in other fields of science (45% compared with the average of 36%). Respondents from the Humanities also have a below average share of respondents saying that they never look for data to reuse (8% compared with an average of 13%) as do those from Engineering and Technology (9%) and Natural Sciences (10%). Respondents from the Medical and Health Sciences were the least active with regards to 'always' looking for data to reuse (25%) which may be due to the sensitivity of the data they tend to work with. There is very little variation in practice among different career stages.

Assigning licences

Reusing data that is licenced is less common among the respondents as is assigning licences to their own data. Less than half of respondents say that they apply licences to their data 'always' (17%) or 'sometimes' (28%). There was a larger than average share of respondents who were not able to answer this question which indicates that licences are an area that researchers are less sure about. This is echoed in the next section on barriers which shows that legal restrictions are seen as a large barrier to data sharing.

There is very little variation when looking at the allocation of data licences across different country types, regions, fields of science and career stages. Respondents based in EU14 countries have an above average share of those who say that they never release datasets with a licence (41% compared to an average of 36%) while those in 'other' countries have a below average share (28%). At the regional level, Northern Europe has an above average share of respondents who never assign data licences (43% compared with an average of 39%).

When looking at different FOS, there are higher than average shares of respondents from the Social Sciences and Medical and Health Sciences who never assign licences to their data (46% and 44% respectively compared with an average of 39%). These groups also had lower than average shares of respondents who say that they always assign data licences (13% and 15% respectively compared with the average of 18%). Given that these two domains tend to work with sensitive data, it is likely that the legal issues are a major concern for researchers which may make them reluctant to assign licences to their data.

Figure 94. Frequency of releasing data with a licence across FOS (share of respondents)

Source: own elaboration based on unweighted researchers' survey data, N=10,870.

4.2.5. Brief summary of the findings

More than half of respondents indicate that they sometimes or always carry out seven of the nine FAIR-aligned practices. The most frequently reported FAIR-aligned practice is to look for data to reuse when starting new research. Far fewer report using repositories to share their own data which suggests that there may be a lot less data available for reuse than there should be. Respondents from the Natural Sciences make use of repositories most often and respondents from Social Sciences and Medical and Health Sciences the least often suggesting that there may be a gap in the availability of repositories that can accommodate the specific needs of sensitive data.

The widespread use of ORCIDs may reflect the fact that many publishers²⁴ and funders²⁵ require them to be used. However, using ORCIDs offers tangible benefits to researchers such as keeping their publications and other research activities up to date in an automated way. As Research Graph²⁶ technology matures and the potential it offers becomes better recognised, we may see a similar increase in the use of PIDs for data and software. However, assigning persistent identifiers for software/code is by far the least common

24 <https://info.orcid.org/requiring-orcid-in-publications/>

25 <https://info.orcid.org/funders-open-letter/>

26 <https://graph.openaire.eu/>

FAIR-aligned practice so additional measures will be needed to increase uptake of this practice in the short term.

Releasing datasets with a licence was the second least frequent practice with just under half of respondents saying that they sometimes or always do this. Dealing with copyright and legal issues are considered to be a significant barrier to FAIR data sharing so there is a need to develop support and guidance to help researchers navigate this complex landscape.

The 115 second most frequent activity is developing DMPs with more than three quarters of respondents indicating that they develop data management plans at least some of the time. However, when looking at the frequency of other FAIR-aligned practices such as assigning PIDs, using standards and depositing with repositories, it seems that there may be a disconnect between what is planned and what is actually carried out. This may suggest that there is a need for ongoing support and feedback for data management plans over the entire life of the research project to ensure that they are both feasible and ultimately implemented. This is echoed in a recent study on DMPs produced as part of H2020 which found that EC support for writing DMPs and providing feedback on them would be welcomed²⁷.

4.3. BARRIERS, MOTIVATORS AND ENABLERS FOR FAIR PRACTICE

This section analyses factors that motivate, enable or hinder FAIR data practice. The survey asked several questions to gauge the influence of different policy stakeholders on researchers' behaviour and to better understand which policy factors motivate them to engage in RDM and data sharing practices. The survey also asked about the barriers that researchers face in managing and sharing their research data as well as where they get support. Respondents were asked to identify the extent to which they encounter various obstacles to data sharing and which policy factors influence them to share their data and make it FAIR. The survey also asked who respondents currently turn to for support when they need help as well as who they felt *should* be providing them with support.

Box 4-4. Key findings on barriers, motivators and enablers for FAIR practice

- Data protection and legal restrictions are seen as the two biggest barriers across all factors.
- Lack of data repositories is seen as a barrier, but far more so in countries outside of western Europe.

27 Spichtinger D. Data Management Plans in Horizon 2020: what beneficiaries think and what we can learn from their experience [version 1; peer review:2 approved, 1 approved with reservations]
Open Research Europe 2021,1:42. <https://doi.org/10.12688/openreseurope.13342.1>

- Institutional support resources are critical enablers for researchers in terms of their awareness level and accessibility. They are not just who researchers turn to, but also who researchers think they should be able to turn to for support.

4.3.1. Barriers

The survey asked to what extent researchers considered certain factors an obstacle to creating FAIR data. All the factors are a barrier to ‘some’ or a ‘large’ extent but Figure 95 shows some factors are bigger barriers than others.

Half of respondents indicate that **lack of repositories** is little to no barrier, although that total includes the highest share of “Don’t know/Can’t Answer” (18%). **Time and effort required to share data** is a noticeably above average large obstacle, followed by **legal restrictions**, and, to an extent, **costs**. Aside from a lack of repositories, **commercial use** is considered a smaller “large” obstacle. The “To some extent” category was the plurality in all but legal restrictions, and financial costs, and mostly a stable share across all, with greatest deviation from the average for skills and data protection (above average) and repository availability (below).

Figure 95. Obstacles to RDM and data sharing (share of respondents)

Source: own elaboration based on unweighted researchers’ survey data, N=9898 who selected at least one option.

Obstacles by regional groups

Excluding the ‘others’ category, the highest share of “large” obstacles in relation to **data protection** came from Northern Europe at 46%, but all the EU groups treated it as a large obstacle by a greater percentage than Associate Country groups, especially the Associated Countries with lower R&D spending. This group didn’t necessarily find it little or no obstacle, but instead provided the largest share of the “some” obstacle (47%). South Eastern Europe was the group that found this topic to be the greatest obstacle when combining their share of “some” and “large” extent shares (42% plus 43%, respectively).

That combined share is also true when the question switches to **legal restrictions**, here South Eastern Europe's combined "large" and "some" responses are a combined 85%. That share of 48% in Eastern Europe responding "large" is the biggest share across groups for that category. Northern Europe has the largest share of "little to none" at 19%, three percent greater than the next closest group of Associated Countries with higher R&D spending. Northern Europe and Associated Countries with higher R&D spending cover all the Nordic nations in the survey responses.

Financial costs are striking in the variation in groups between those who find funding RDM little to no obstacle, and those that find it a large one. Over half of all respondents in either EU for South Eastern Europe (52%) and Associated Countries with lower R&D spending (50%) said it was large, but only 29% in Northern Europe.

Skills provided a stable split across EU and AC countries, with narrower ranges across categories from Northern Europe to Associated Countries with lower R&D spending, 3% for little to "none" (15 to 18%), 5% for "some" (41 to 46%), and 4% for large (31 to 36%).

North Western Europe found **time and effort** needed a "large" obstacle, 53% selected the "large" obstacle option, which is 7 points higher than the next closest share from Central Europe. Associated Countries with lower R&D spending had the smallest share of perceptions either "large" or "some", but also featured the highest share of Don't Know/Can't Answer responses at 12%, four points higher than the next closest value.

Lack of recognition is interesting in the number of "Don't Knows" in Northern Europe and Associated Countries with lower R&D expenditure, both in the upper teen percentages, compared to the lower teens for the other regions. For Northern Europe this share led to a lower share of "large" obstacle responses (28%), for Associated Countries with lower R&D spending it led to a smaller share of "Little or no" obstacle share. The biggest percentage for "large" was in North Western Europe (38%) just ahead of 37% for South Eastern Europe. Risks of **misinterpretation** is "Little or no" obstacle for nearly a third of respondents in North Western Europe (33%), Northern Europe (31%), and Northern Europe (30%), yet this share was in the teens for South Eastern Europe and Associated Countries with lower R&D spending. Unsurprisingly for South Eastern Europe and Associated Countries with lower R&D expenditure the "Large" obstacle share was highest at 34 and 35%, most of the others were around a quarter of responses. The "Some" category was between 34% (Northern Europe) and 39% (South Eastern Europe). Northern Europe and North Western Europe found **economic competitiveness/undesired commercial use** "Little or no" obstacle to the greatest extent, 37% and 36% respectively, and again South Eastern Europe and Associated Countries with lower R&D expenditure found it a "Large" obstacle at 31% and 30%.

The issue of data repositories was one that produced variation in shares of "Little to no" and "Large" across groups. North Western Europe (40%) and Central Europe (38%) and Northern Europe (37%) see it as "Little to no", but only 15% in Associated Countries with

lower R&D spending share that, while South Eastern Europe is just 21%, suggesting repository support declines when looking to the east of Europe.

Figure 96. Lack of data repositories and data centres where research data could be stored by country group (including within the EU) (share of respondents)

Source: own elaboration based on unweighted researchers' survey data.

Obstacles by field of science

Looking at the question of obstacles by field of science, it is perhaps no surprise to see the Medical and Health sciences (48%) and Social Sciences (44%) consider **data protection and confidentiality** a large obstacle, with the Natural Sciences having the largest share considering it little to no extent of an issue at 16%.

The largest obstacle share is, again, greatest for the Medical and Health Sciences when it comes to **legal restrictions** (45%), followed a shade lower by Engineering and Technology (44%).

RDM **costs** are seen as a large obstacle by all disciplines, with the lowest share for this category being 36% for Natural Scientists and the highest in the Humanities at 44%.

It is also striking that for RDM **skills**, all disciplines see it to some extent an obstacle at an almost identical share of 44-45%. Those finding it little or no obstacle find their greatest share among the Engineering and Technology respondents, where 19% see it as little to no extent an obstacle. For this question the Humanities have the lowest little to no share, at 11%.

Time and effort as an obstacle is mostly consistent across disciplines with ranges of 39% (Humanities) to 45% (Social Sciences) finding it to a large extent an obstacle, these two disciplines occupy the largest and smallest shares considering it to some extent an obstacle (38 to 42%).

Box 4-5. Illustration from free-text data

- Much of qualitative data is collected using proprietary programs. It is very difficult to make this raw data available for independent, unmediated use by other researchers. We would need support to convert the file formats we use into more standard file formats

Source: researcher survey.

Lack of recognition for RDM and sharing attracts a higher rate of "Do not know/Cannot answer" share, with an average share of 15% for this question, and similar splits between some extent and large extent with percentage shares in the mid-thirties.

For **risk of misinterpretation and falsification**, all disciplines had a smaller share of those seeing it as a large obstacle, disciplines squeezed the large share to an average share of 27.5%, but Medical and Health Sciences and Agricultural Sciences were 30% and 35% respectively. Instead, they, on balance, saw it as either little to none, or somewhat of an obstacle.

For **economic competitiveness/undesired commercial use**, the large obstacle share was squeezed again to 23%.

Finally, for **lack of data repositories**, no discipline broke the 20% mark for seeing it as a large obstacle. Thirty-eight and 36% of Medical and Health and Social Scientists respectively found it little or no obstacle. Even the lowest share for little or none, held by Agricultural Sciences, only just dipped below the 25% share of responses.

That combined share lowers for the question on **recognition** for RDM work, and for **risk of misinterpretation** it is the 'somewhat' of an obstacle category that is the plurality choice. It is not a surprise to see 41% of large company respondents see economic competitiveness/undesired commercial use as a large obstacle, though the small number of respondents to this question (n = 58) should be a caution. A small n is not such a concern when it comes to lack of data repositories from public university affiliated respondents, 31% say it is a 'little to none' obstacle.

Obstacles by career stage

Career stage was another demographic variable that held a level of consistency across groups.

Data protection and confidentiality was a big issue for all, with 41% finding it to some extent and another 39% a large extent obstacle, 11% little to no obstacle as an average share across all career groups, with little deviation from those average shares.

Legal restrictions were slightly less of an obstacle, but only slightly; here the average share across career progress was 13%, 37% found it somewhat an obstacle, and an average of 40% across groups found it a large one. That little to no category was also slightly larger when it came to financial **costs**, at an average of 16% selecting that response, with "Recognised" researchers a bit above the average with an 18% share. But

the story was again consistent across the groups with only a 3% range among some extent (34 to 37%) and 4% among the large obstacle respondents (35 to 39%).

Skills are again perceived mostly the same across groups, an average of 17% said little to no obstacle, 44% on average said some, and 32% was the average share saying they were a large obstacle. In all groups the variation from these averages was no more than 4% either way.

Time and effort required to manage and share data has leading and established respondents finding it a large obstacle by shares of 44% to 41% for first stage and recognised respondents. For the 'some extent' option the groups split 40 to 39%. First stage respondents were a touch higher with the don't know/cannot answer responses at 9%, compared to 8% for leading researchers and 6% each for established and recognised ones.

Lack of recognition has a higher level of little or no obstacles from leading researchers, at 17% and first stage ones at 12%, the other groups at 14% each. Those finding it a large obstacle averaged 35%, and to some extent 37%, with again, little variation either side of those averages.

First stage researchers were more likely to find obstacles to some or a large extent when it came to **risk of misinterpretation and/or falsification** of data, with only 22% saying little to no extent, but for leading researchers that was a 28% share, and 27% for established researchers. Recognised and first stage respondents had the highest levels finding it a large obstacle at 29% but as with the other questions, to some extent was the largest option selected at an average of 36%, and to a large extent at 27%.

As with the other demographics, the question on **economic competitiveness/undesired commercial use** sees higher levels saying it is little or no obstacle. The average score here was 30%, but first stage researchers had a lower share at 26%. Respondents finding it to some extent an obstacle were roughly a third, and to a large extent, a quarter of respondents.

First stage researchers also had a lower share when looking to **data repositories** as an obstacle. Twenty-eight percent said it was little to no obstacle – the lowest share for that response - while recognised researchers selected this option with a 34% share, with established researchers just behind with 33%, and leading researchers at 32%. Finding it a large obstacle was smaller as a share of responses across all groups, with a three percent range in responses from 16% (established) to 19% (first stage).

4.3.2. Motivators

More than half of respondents say that the policies of funding bodies and publishers are the most influential when it comes to their RDM and data sharing. The policies of their institution also appear to be a key influencing factor on their behaviour with just under half of respondents saying that these policies are 'very influential' (46%). Community norms and

national level policies are viewed as less influential (34% of respondents say these are very influential). The least influential policies are those of research infrastructures and data repositories.

Figure 97. Influence of different stakeholders' policies on researchers' practices as assessed by respondents (share of respondents)

Source: own elaboration based on unweighted researchers' survey data, n=10179-10183 depending on option.

When asked about their familiarity with the EU's Open Science policy, almost three quarters of those responding to the question say that they are aware of it. However, of these, almost half say that they are not very familiar with it in a practical sense (46%). A follow-on question asked those who said they are aware of the policy to specify what actions the policy had motivated them to undertake.

Almost a third of the respondents who answered this question said that the EU's policy encouraged them to make the data as open as possible, while about a quarter said it encourages them to make their data FAIR (25%) and to develop a DMP (23%). The policy does not seem to exert much influence on researchers to look for data to reuse (12%). As show in Figure 85, the vast majority of respondents (85%) indicate that they do look for data to reuse when starting new research so it seems that there are other motivating factors driving this behaviour. Respondents were able to choose 'other' and were able to provide a free text response if they wished. Only 163 respondents chose this option and of these only about 60 provided a written comment. While some stated that they were already converts to Open Science, many of the comments took a more negative view of the policy saying that it increases the burden on researchers and detracts from their actual research. While this view is in the minority, it does reinforce the need to focus on how RDM and data sharing contribute to the acceleration of scientific research and public good when promoting the policy.

Figure 98. Perceived influence of EU’s Open Science policy on respondents’ RDM and data sharing practice (share of respondents)

Source: own elaboration based on unweighted researchers’ survey data, n=6168. Note: respondents could select multiple answer options.

When it comes to the policy factors which would influence their FAIR data practices (Figure 99), the factors that most positively influence behaviour is that the policy is easy to understand and adhere to and that there is support provided to help researchers with compliance (close to two thirds of respondents in both cases). This tallies with findings from the FAIRsFAIR policy landscape review.²⁸ Other factors that are viewed as positive influences include that compliance with the policy is monitored and that rewards for compliance are introduced. On the other hand, penalties for non-compliance were viewed the least favourably, however about a third of respondents were neutral on this aspect and the difference between those in favour vs those against penalties is minor.

Figure 99. Respondents’ views on policy factors (share of respondents)

Source: own elaboration based on unweighted researchers’ survey data, N=11,831.

28 Davidson, Joy, Engelhardt, Claudia, Proudman, Vanessa, Stoy, Lennart, & Whyte, Angus. (2019). D3.1 FAIR Policy Landscape Analysis (Version v1.0_draft). <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.3558172>

This pattern was consistent across regions, although support from UK researchers for an understandable policy and support were noticeably higher at 72% in both cases. Looking at the question by primary field of science, it's a reasonably consistent picture across disciplines. There is some variation in the number of respondents by field, ranging from 3643 for Natural Scientists, down to 495 for humanities, but there is stability in the percentage shares across categories. There is often less than two percent variation either side of the average share for views. Around a quarter "Don't know", nearly a third "Neutral" and just under 40 percent positive. The only notable variation in these shares is for a positive view from Medical and Health (6.1% above average share), which also leads to a 3.4% reduction in the neutral view of the policy. The question examined by career stage yields similar shares of feelings towards the policy. If we disregard the small number of respondents who do not know or cannot answer as to their career stage (n = 209), the variation in career stage is small. Recognised researchers are a shade more likely to be neutral (2.1%) or positive (1.4%) above average in their view. First stage researchers have a 4% above average positive view, and 2.5% below average negative view. Other than that, variation is a point or under either side of the average level of support for a view.

Figure 100. Respondents' views on policy factors by FOS (share of respondents)

Source: own elaboration based on unweighted researchers' survey data.

4.3.3. Enablers

This question asks about where researchers seek support if they require help to manage, share and/or make data FAIR. There's a clear gap between institutional support, selected by 59% of respondents, and the rest. Not everyone responding to this question is a researcher at a university - although by far most are - and "help" can also cover a wide range of support needs. But it does show institutions have a significant level of awareness in the minds of researchers when it comes to managing research data.

Figure 101. Where researchers seek support if they require help to manage, share and/or make their data findable, accessible, interoperable and/or reusable (FAIR) (share of respondents)

Source: own elaboration based on unweighted researchers' survey data. Note: respondents could select multiple answer options.

When researchers do need help making data FAIR, it is institutional support services to which they are most likely to turn. Institutional support was selected by half of respondents in Northern Europe (51%) and North Western Europe (56%). South Eastern Europe and Associated Countries with lower R&D spending had the lowest shares, being 7% and 11% below the average share of 46%. Institutional support remains the most popular option, selected by just over 50% of those who collect and just under 50% or plan to collect data. Of course, this question does not ask the nature of that support, be it a major or minor query, which may affect the levels and choices of support resources.

Box 4-6. Illustration from free-text data

- It would be extremely useful to have a data manager from the institution, a technician that understands the kind of data in my field.

Source: researcher survey.

Across disciplines, the pattern of support choices was consistent. Institutional support was selected by half of respondents across all, with funding body guidance the least popular selection – no more than 15% of respondents in each discipline chose it as a resource – although, of course, this measures direct consultation with the funder rather than say a resource supported by a funder.

Selection by career stage also drew a similar pattern as clear majorities selected institutional support across categories, funders lagged at around 20% and the rest in the mid to upper thirties. The only time institutional support doesn't rank as the most numerous options selected is with private organisations, and even then, 35% of respondents affiliated with a private organisation selected it. Finally, for type of data, again, institutional support services were the option chosen by most respondents regardless of which forms of data they identified themselves as working with, with levels of selection hovering around the 60% value. It is perhaps also unsurprising that those working with software or code tend to select

search engines slightly more than other types of data users at 40%, compared to values around 30% for other types of data users.

The importance of institutional support is highlighted again in a question which asked who **should** provide guidance, training and support for managing, sharing and making data FAIR. Institutional level provision was ranked highest by more than 60% of respondents to this question. National level provision was also ranked highly - 20% ranked this option highest and a further 31% ranked this option as second. Discipline level provision was not ranked as highly as one might expect.

Figure 102. Who should provide training, guidance and support for making data FAIR? Respondents were asked to rank each support option with 1 being highest and 6 being lowest (share of respondents)

Source: own elaboration based on unweighted researchers' survey data, N=8,818, who selected at least one option.

4.3.4. Brief summary of the findings

Respondents tended to perceive challenges with consistency across a range of different measures. All groups found all of the obstacles presented in the survey a challenge to some extent. Notable exceptions were the variation in consideration of lack of data repositories by region, with a trend towards it being more of an obstacle in Central (Group 4) and South Eastern Europe (Group 5), and outside the EU for low R&D countries. For disciplines, noticeable variation came in Medical and Health Sciences and Social Sciences considering data protection and confidentiality a large obstacle compared to other disciplines, and the Medical and Health Sciences and Engineering and Technology identifying legal restrictions as a large barrier. The final area to feature notable variation is around the extent of data manipulation required. Those having to undertake large modifications selected data protection and confidentiality, and time and effort to larger degrees than those who did not have to undertake large modifications. Researchers see institutions as a big part of enabling FAIR data through support provision. Not just in the number of researchers that selected institutional support as their current source of support, but the number that chose institutional support as the most important source. When it comes to motivations, a policy that is easy to understand, and the provision of support are

easily the most popular ways to engage with FAIR data. Negative factors like compliance monitoring and sanctions are not popular.

The recommendations following from this section focus on paths to raising awareness of repository solutions where there may not be readily apparent ones (say, an institutional repository or research data support service).

Work on support avenues for data sharing and access where research data carries sensitive information that cannot allow it to be shared openly is also encouraged, through harmonising, where possible appropriate data licences and policies built around accessible language, but also on access restrictions. These can work both for supporting both FAIR data creation and reuse. A further benefit of this work would be to help mitigate the data wrangling needed to enable reuse, which was a notable obstacle identified in this survey.

4.4. RECOMMENDATIONS

Finding: there is still a need to raise general awareness about FAIR

The EOSC FAIR Working Group recommended in 2020 that awareness-raising is needed at all levels and that funding is needed to enable the provision of training, education, and community-specific support. While this study shows that there is some familiarity with the FAIR principles, more than two thirds of respondents have not heard of the FAIR principles or do not fully understand what they mean. Common misconceptions also persist such as FAIR data must also be open data. This study shows that there is still a need for general awareness raising about the FAIR principles and what they mean to ensure that specific objective 1 to ‘increase in the number of relevant research outputs that are made available as open as possible by researchers performing publicly funded research’ as outlined in the EOSC multi-annual roadmap²⁹ is feasible. As the vast majority of respondents resonate with the concepts of the FAIR principles and are primarily motivated to share data to support the acceleration of scientific research/public benefit rather than to meet funding body or national requirements, it is important that awareness raising activities focus on how FAIR data can support these aims rather than placing an emphasis on compliance.

Possible action:

- Develop a shared collection of real-life examples across different disciplines showing how FAIR data practices have led to real-world benefits and the acceleration of science to support awareness raising campaigns at the European, national, and

29 EOSC Multi-Annual Roadmap 2023-24. https://eosc.eu/sites/default/files/2022-02/20220226_EOSC_Multi_Annual_Roadmap_23-24_for_consultation_0.pdf

institutional level. The recent series of EOSC use cases³⁰ and FAIR Implementation Stories³¹ may offer a useful template that others can adapt for reuse.

- In partnership with the EOSC Researcher Engagement & Adoption Task Force³², the EC should encourage and coordinate the range of European Commission projects that are working to support the implementation of the European Open Science Cloud to harmonise dissemination activities and ensure that a range of different stakeholder groups can be targeted with consistent and key messages.

Finding: local support for FAIR practices is a crucial enabler

The EOSC multi-annual roadmap identifies the increased availability of professional data stewards in research-performing organisations as a critical success factor for realising the EOSC vision. This study shows that institutional level support is where researchers currently get the help they need. More importantly, their institution is where they think they *should* be able to turn to for support in making their data FAIR. As noted in a report from the EOSC Minimal Skillset Task Force, a wide range of skilled support staff including Research Software Engineers is needed to support researchers in the production and use of FAIR data. While some countries are investing in building Data Stewardship capacity at the institutional level such as the Netherlands and Belgium, similar levels of resourcing will not be feasible across all countries. Indeed, a recent EUA report found that specialist support services for RDM are lacking in just under half of the surveyed Universities³³. To ensure a level playing field, there is a need to ensure that Data Stewardship expertise can be made available to researchers regardless of whether they are in-house or pooled from regional, national or international sources. The EOSC Skills & Training WG recommended in 2021 that a competence centres approach for increasing coordinated provision of aligned training to support FAIR and open science should be encouraged and supported³⁴. The findings of this study support this recommendation.

Possible action:

- The EC should leverage the activities of the EOSC Data stewardship, curricula and career paths Task Force and Upskilling countries to engage in EOSC Task Force to support the development of national or regional data steward networks and

30 <https://eosc-portal.eu/eosc-in-practice/stories>

31 <https://fairsfair.eu/implementation-adoption-stories>

32 <https://www.eosc.eu/advisory-groups/researcher-engagement-adoption>

33 From principles to practices: Open Science at Europe's universities 2020-2021 EUA Open Science Survey results. <https://eua.eu/resources/publications/976:from-principles-to-practices-open-science-at-europe%E2%80%99s-universities-2020-2021-eua-open-science-survey-results.html>

34 European Commission, Directorate-General for Research and Innovation, Digital skills for FAIR and Open Science : report from the EOSC Executive Board Skills and Training Working Group, Manola, N.(editor), Lazzeri, E.(editor), Barker, M.(editor), Kuchma, I.(editor), Gaillard, V.(editor), Stoy, L.(editor), Publications Office, 2021, <https://data.europa.eu/doi/10.2777/59065>

competence centres where limited resources can be pooled and made available to support local support provision.

- Member States and national funding bodies should consider the example being piloted in the Netherlands with the National Coordination Point Research Data Management (LCRDM)³⁵ and funded support for the creation of Digital Competence Centres could be worth replicating in other countries and/or at the regional level. To support and informed review by MS, the EC in cooperation with NWO might commission a study to develop a blueprint for adopting this approach focusing on the practicalities of skills and staffing, costs and sustainability.

Finding: while data management planning is increasing, other FAIR practices do not necessarily follow

Strategic objective 4 states in the multi-annual roadmap identifies ‘increasing amounts of research outputs from publicly funded research in Europe are FAIR by design’ as being core to the realisation of the fully functioning EOSC. Good data management is crucial for ensuring that FAIR data is produced and is best realised through the development and updating of data management plans (DMPs). This study has found that developing data management plans when starting their research is becoming increasingly common with almost three quarters of respondents to the survey saying they do this sometimes or always. However, as other FAIR-aligned activities are less common, it seems that planned practice may not always materialise. This suggests that there is a need for continuous support to review, update and implement data management plans to ensure that FAIR data objectives are realised. Some institutions provide advice and guidance on developing DMPs (mainly at the grant application stage) but others do not have the in-house resource to support this. To increase the amount of FAIR data available, it is important that adequate support is made available over the entire research lifecycle and that DMPs are both realistic and that implementation is supported. The findings of this study support the FAIRsFAIR recommendation that stakeholders collaborate to ensure that data management planning is supported across the entire research lifecycle so that data can be “born FAIR” and kept “FAIR enough” over time and that updating of DMPs is required leading to comprehensive, high-quality end stage DMPs that reflect what has happened rather than what was planned³⁶. Many funding bodies encourage periodic updating, and some do require end stage DMPs. However, a recent report on DMPs produced as part of H2020 found that there was a perceived lack of feedback on the content of DMPs that were produced.

Possible action:

- As noted in the FAIRsFAIR recommendations, where resources allow, RPOs should provide domain specific RDM support locally. Where local support isn’t feasible, the

35 <https://www.lcrdm.nl/en>

36 Davidson, Joy, Grootveld, Marjan, Whyte, Angus, Herterich, Patricia, Engelhardt, Claudia, Stoy, Lennart, & Proudman Vanessa. (2020). D3.3 Policy Enhancement Recommendations (1.0). Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.5362183>

development of shared domain-specific resources should be supported and maintained with resources provided by all stakeholders. Building on the findings of the EUA assessment of RDM and support for FAIR at the institutional level, Member States may wish to carry out assessment to review the current support provision and resources available and to identify gaps.

- The EC might consider implementing a permanent panel of domain specific Data Stewards who would be available to support researchers over the life of their projects to support the co-creation of data management plans that actually lead to the production and availability of FAIR data. By providing access to on-demand advice and guidance over the life of the project, there is greater potential to ensure that appropriate standards are used, identifiers are assigned to outputs and that selected outputs are deposited with trusted repositories. Such support would be particularly beneficial to those working in institutions without local RDM expertise and support.

Finding: there is a need for support to improve the sharing of research software

Strategic objective 5 in the multi-annual roadmap envisages that the EOSC interoperability Framework will support an increasing range and quantity of FAIR digital objects including data, software and other research artefacts. For this vision to become reality, there is a need to improve the FAIRness of research software. This study found that aspects of software FAIRification such as the allocation of PIDs is the least common practice among researchers. As such, there is an urgent need to improve capacity in this area. In recent years, there has been an increase in the number of Research Software Engineers (RSE) employed at RPOs and this should lead to the availability of more FAIR software over time. Indeed, this study found that RSEs are amongst those most familiar with and putting FAIR into practice. However not all research performing organisations will be able to provide this level of expertise locally. As such, there is a need to ensure that there is access to such specialist knowledge externally.

Possible action:

- Individual member states and/or the EC may wish to support the development of a pan-European network of expertise such as that offered by the Software Sustainability Institute (SSI)³⁷ in the UK which is supported by UKRI. The SSI offers services to researchers such as virtual surgery sessions³⁸ and software health checks³⁹ to support researchers adopt best practice with regards to developing sustainable software.

37 <https://software.ac.uk/about>

38 <https://www.software.ac.uk/software-surgery-guidelines>

39 <https://software.ac.uk/programmes-and-events/research-software-healthcheck>

5. ASSESSING DATA FAIRNESS USING F-UJI TOOL

As shown above, more than half of respondents say that they ‘always’ or ‘sometimes’ deposit their data with a repository. In addition, half of respondents do not see a lack of data repositories as an obstacle hindering their ability to share data to any great extent. This suggests that researchers do have access to repositories to store and, where appropriate, share their research data. Indeed, as shown in section 3.5, about a fifth of respondents indicate that they used a repository to store the data for their current or most recent research activity and almost half have used a repository to store data from previous research projects. Of those, the majority make use of institutional repositories. When it comes to choosing which repository to use, continuity of the repository service and preservation of its data holdings is one of the main factors influencing respondents’ decisions (as shown in section 3.5.1).

While continuity of the service is seen as important, just under a fifth of those respondents who make use of a repository indicate that they use a repository created specifically for their project which is very risky with regards to long-term sustainability of the service. Only a small share of respondents indicate that they choose a repository which provides curation services (12%), which suggests that there is a lack of awareness between a repository’s ability to preserve the bits versus its ability to preserve the usability of the deposited data.

The provision of persistent identifiers such as DOIs was also a factor influencing respondents’ choice of repository. Encouragingly, 76% percent of repositories responding to the repository survey (see section 6.3) said they offer PIDs as part of their service, while 28 percent say they outsource creation of PIDs.

As shown in section 3.5, a number of repository types are currently being used. International and generalist repositories appear to be used slightly more often than discipline specific repository services (33% and 24% respectively compared with 21%). Certification of the repository appears to be an influencing factor perhaps due to the fact that a growing number of national funding bodies now encourage researchers to deposit their data with trusted digital repositories.

The findings suggest that researchers do have access to a range of research data repositories and that many make use of them. As part of this study, we also aimed to assess how FAIR the data held by different kinds of repositories currently is. In this section, we present the findings of FAIRness assessments carried out on selected data holdings within a wide range of repositories.

5.1. SELECTING REPOSITORIES AND DATASETS FOR F-UJI FAIR ASSESSMENT

Box 5-1. Key elements of repository selection

The core activity of this part of the study was to apply the F-UJI FAIR assessment tool to a selection of datasets in a sample of data repositories in EU member states, Horizon 2020 Associated Countries, and the UK.

- The basis for the sampling was the re3data registry and the sampling criteria aimed at a balanced distribution of certification status (certified, non-certified, expired), repository type (generic, disciplinary), supported domains (social sciences and humanities, life sciences, natural sciences, engineering sciences), and geographical area (north-west, south-east, south-west, central). This resulted in a sample of 31 repositories.
- A trial run was performed with one dataset for each of the 31 repositories to test F-UJI and the analysis pipeline. Some initial lessons learned are presented in the text.
- Using the F-UJI automated software, for each of the 31 repositories up to 300 datasets were randomly selected. Metadata service endpoints were collected for all repositories to guarantee the highest possible scores. The final dataset consisted of nearly 8,000 dataset.

5.1.1. Repository sample selection

Although FAIR could be considered as a process, a culture change, or a journey, which takes time and is to a substantial extent subjective, there is a clear interest in tools that automatically assess the level of FAIRness of data. In this part of the study we applied such a tool, F-UJI, to a set of nearly 8000 datasets. As a first step, the re3data API was queried to retrieve all repositories in its system that supported the Digital Object Identifier (DOI) system for persistent identifiers (PIDs)⁴⁰. This list of repositories was exported, after which a selection was made to only include repositories from EU member states, Horizon 2020 Associated Countries, and the UK. For this pool of eligible repositories, we aimed for a balanced distribution of **certification status** (certified, non-certified, expired), **repository type** (generic, disciplinary), **supported domains** (social sciences and humanities, life sciences, natural sciences, engineering sciences), and **geographical area** (North-West, South-East, South-West, Central).

Once the metadata were coded, a selection of 33 repositories was made. Next, each repository was individually investigated to collect information about the data holdings and

⁴⁰ re3data API query: <https://www.re3data.org/api/beta/repositories?query=&pidSystems%5B%5D=DOI>

filtering options. This step was taken to ensure that each repository could adhere to the dataset selection criteria, which are detailed in the Annex. After this process, a sample of 31 eligible repositories remained. A list of these repositories can be found in the Annex. An overview of the distribution of this sample on the different criteria is presented in Table 17.

Table 17. An overview of the repository sample for the initial F-UJI assessments

Criterion	Distribution
Certification status	Certified – 35.48% Non-certified - 48.39% Expired - 16.13%
Repository type	Generic – 35.48% Disciplinary – 64.52%
Domain(s) supported*	Social Sciences and Humanities – 70.97% Life Sciences – 58.06% Natural Sciences – 61.29% Engineering Sciences – 32.26%
Geographical area in Europe**	North-West – 77.42% South-East – 9.68% South-West – 6.45% Central – 6.45%

*This row indicates the percentages of repositories that support each domain. Since one repository can support multiple domains, these percentages cumulatively exceed 100%; **Based on the country codes list from re3data⁴¹

A flowchart of the complete repository selection process is presented in Figure 103. Flowchart of the repository sample selection process below. An overview of the geographical spread of the repositories in the sample is presented in Figure 104. The geographical spread of the repositories in the sample ($n = 31$). Given the small number of repositories in this sample, the geographical clustering differs from clustering in other parts of this study.

The next step, after sampling the repositories, was to randomly select 300 datasets per repository. This process is described in the Annex. A few selected repositories were too small or had few scholarly objects of type "dataset", therefore no random sample could be taken (see the Annex for the overview of the selected repositories and number of sampled datasets).

41 Country code list re3data: <https://www.re3data.org/browse/by-country/>

Figure 103. Flowchart of the repository sample selection process

Source: own elaboration.

Figure 104. The geographical spread of the repositories in the sample (n = 31)

Source: own elaboration.

5.1.2. Initial trial run and early lessons

After collecting the dataset samples, we performed an initial trial run with F-UJI. For each of the 31 selected repositories one dataset was manually selected to perform a F-UJI FAIR assessment. The aim of this initial pilot trial was to streamline the assessment and analysis process and discover possible areas of interest or concern early on. It was found that

several repositories scored exceptionally low on FAIRness. It turned out that F-UJI was not able to find the relevant metadata, e.g. because they are not on the landing page. For such FAIR criteria, the F-UJI scores were often 0. However, the F-UJI tool can carry out assessments with Content Negotiation based on the DOI URL. When this option is turned on, it retrieves metadata from DataCite, which in a sense allows F-UJI to look beyond the landing page. (Please see Annex for more information about Content Negotiation). Therefore, in the analysis of the full sample Content Negotiation was turned on. However, it is not available for repositories using other identifiers than DOI, which may therefore be disadvantaged if their metadata is not found on the landing page. Out of the 31 repositories, 26 use DOIs. Additionally, three use Handles, one uses URN:NBN, and one uses a local identifier.

Another early lesson learned is that we might not expect much variety of data FAIRness scores within repositories. This was not unexpected: it was noted before that the FAIR principles bear a great resemblance to the principles underlying the Data Seal of Approval⁴² (Doorn and Dillo, 2017), one of the forerunners of the current CoreTrustSeal certification⁴³ for digital repositories. Aspects like persistent identifiers, licenses, and metadata are addressed both in the FAIR principles and in the CoreTrustSeal requirements. Attributes such as persistent identifiers are usually assigned to datasets by the repository itself, so that if one dataset has a persistent identifier, they all have one. Therefore, to some extent, assessing the FAIRness of a dataset is in fact assessing aspects of the repository holding the dataset.

5.2. ANALYSIS OF FAIRNESS OF 7827 DATASETS IN 31 EUROPEAN REPOSITORIES

Box 5-2. Key findings of the F-UJI analysis

For the dataset sample (n = 7827), we found an overall average F-UJI FAIR score of 54.6%.

- Looking at the average F-UJI FAIR score for each repository: 5 repositories in the sample have a score lower than 25%, 8 have a score between 25-50%, 14 have a score between 50-75%, and 4 have a score higher than 75%. Overall, Findability contributes to the F-UJI FAIR scores the most, and Reusability contributes the least.
- Variation in F-UJI FAIR scores according to certification status was limited, though datasets in certified repositories tended to have somewhat higher FAIR scores than datasets in repositories which are not certified.

42 <https://www.coretrustseal.org/about/history/data-seal-of-approval-synopsis-2008-2018/>

43 <https://www.coretrustseal.org/about/history/>

- The average F-UJI FAIR scores for datasets in cross-disciplinary repositories showed minimal difference with the average F-UJI FAIR scores for datasets in disciplinary repositories.
- Repositories in north-west and central Europe showed higher F-UJI FAIR scores on average than south-western and south-eastern repositories. North-Western repositories are overrepresented in re3data.org and in our sample.
- In most repositories the score of their best scoring dataset is (somewhat) higher than the average score of their datasets. This implies that there is (some) room for improvement.
- No overall trend can be discerned regarding FAIR scores over time. About 9% of datasets have no metadata attribute “date” and have a much lower FAIR score on average. Repositories define the “date” attribute in different ways or leave it undefined (Section 4.6.6).

5.2.1. How the automated F-UJI FAIR assessment tool works

To understand the F-UJI FAIR assessment, it is useful to know details on what the assessment process entails. We give an introduction to F-UJI with more details in Annex. There is no global consensus yet about the best “translation” from the FAIR principles to unambiguous metrics. We take a closer look at that topic in Section 5.4.

F-UJI is a web service based on assessment criteria developed in the context of the FAIRsFAIR⁴⁴ project (Devaraju & Huber, 2020). “uji” means “test” in the Malayan language. In the FAIR data context, the word “principle” is often used for the main principles F, A, I, and R, as well as for the sub-principles F1, F2, etc. We will use the term **FAIR main principle** for F, A, I, and R and **FAIR principle** for F1, F2, etc. A **metric** is the unit being tested in the assessment procedure, and each metric yields a **score**.

Per dataset F-UJI reports on 11 FAIR principles, with different maximum scores (maximum score indicated in brackets): F1(2), F2(2), F3(1), F4(2), A1(3), I1(3), I3(1), R1(4), R1.1(2), R1.2(2), R1.3(2). In the results presented below, these scores are also aggregated per FAIR main principle: F(7), A(3), I(4), R(10), which add up to a F-UJI FAIR score of at most 24. (For more details, see Annex, which lists these principles and maximum scores). For easier interpretation we converted scores to a percentage score of 0-100% FAIRness. The F-UJI assessment in the current study was executed using version v1.3.9b of the software based on v0.4 of the Data Object Assessment Metrics⁴⁵.

In the following sections we will zoom into the assessment results by looking at the FAIR scores distribution of the sample as a whole, the FAIR scores per repository and also the

⁴⁴ <https://www.fairsfair.eu>

⁴⁵ Metrics specification of the F-UJI assessment run in the current study: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.4081213>

defined repository characteristics (certification, repository type, and geographical area) will be evaluated. We will also discuss the minimum and maximum FAIR scores. This section will end with some words on FAIR scores over time, by looking at the dataset dates where available.

5.2.2. Sample F-UJI results

Looking at the dataset sample as a whole ($n = 7827$), we found an overall average FAIR score of 54.6% ($sd = 36.89\%$). The distribution of the FAIR scores can be seen in Figure 105. The overall distribution has a more or less normal spread, with some more population on the upper side.

A breakdown of this graph is shown in Figure 106. These four graphs show the distribution of FAIR scores per FAIR main principle (Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, Reusable). These four graphs show that on average the Findability scores were highest (78% on a scale from 0-100%), followed by Interoperability (52%), Accessibility (51%), and lastly, Reusability (38%). Figure 106 shows the spread of the FAIR scores in the sample, with Findability showing the least, and Accessibility the most, variation in the obtained scores (28.81% and 52.25%, respectively). The breakdown of the scores into these separate main principles gives insight into the unique contributions of the four main principles to the overall score. These graphs can be split up even further into the scores on the 11 principles tested by the assessment. The figure displaying this distribution can be found in the Annex. From this level of detail, we can conclude that the *assignment of a unique persistent identifier* (F1) and *machine-retrievable metadata* (F4) are most often satisfied in the sample, whereas the *inclusion of the persistent identifier of the data in metadata* (F3) and the *specification of data content in metadata* (R1) are satisfied the least often.

Figure 105. The distribution of FAIR scores in the dataset sample (categories represent FAIR scores) by number of datasets

Source: repository assessment using the F-UJI tool, dataset N=7,827.

Figure 106. The distribution of FAIR scores in the sample (n = 7827) per FAIR principle (number of datasets)

Source: repository assessment using the F-UJI tool, dataset N=7,827.

5.2.3. Repository FAIR results

To visualise the assessment with finer granularity, an average of the FAIR score for each repository in the sample is presented in Figure 107. This figure shows that there is large variation between repositories in the mean FAIR score, with scores ranging from 3.5% to 92.1%. There are 5 repositories in the sample with a score lower than 25%, 8 with a score between 25-50%, 14 with a score between 50-75%, and 4 with a score higher than 75%. The scores for each repository are made up of the respective contributions of each FAIR principle. This gives some information on which of the FAIR principles is most often satisfied within a certain repository. Overall, Findability contributes to the FAIR scores the most, and Reusability contributes the least.

When looking at FAIR scores on the repository level, it is important to be mindful of a correct interpretation of the data. A lower FAIR score does not always indicate less FAIR-enabling practices in the repository. We go into further detail about this matter in Section 5.3.

Figure 107. The average FAIR score for each repository

Source: repository assessment using the F-UJI tool, dataset N=7,827.

The **variation in the average FAIR scores** was limited for many of the repositories (standard deviations ranging from 1.11% to 33.98%). Repositories with low variation have little difference in the FAIR scores for any given dataset in their holdings obtained in the F-UJI assessment. Two repositories, ISSDA and DABAR, showed no variation at all (relative standard deviation of 0%). Their smaller samples (of 60 and 51 datasets, respectively) all scored the exact same on the F-UJI tests. GESIS and AUSSDA showed a somewhat larger variation (56.27% and 40.84%, respectively). For GESIS, this larger variation is due to a group of 70 datasets with much higher scores than the repository average. In the AUSSDA

datasets there are many different scores present. To truly explain such variation, further investigation and consultation with the repository would be necessary. UK PDC showed a remarkable amount of variation in its sample ($sd(\%) = 173.37\%$), due to a small group of datasets ($n = 12$) which score much higher than the repository's average (52.25% compared to the 5.43% average). There appeared to be no overall correlation between the repositories' average scores and standard deviations ($r = -0.05$), indicating that repositories with on average higher FAIR scores did not have more, nor less variation in their dataset scores than repositories with on average lower FAIR scores (see Annex).

The **reliability of the average FAIR scores per repository** as presented in Figure 107 is high. Confidence Intervals (CI) were calculated for every repository's average FAIR score to discover how much this score could hypothetically vary if this same study was repeated and a different set of datasets would be selected from the repository. For most repositories, the average FAIR score would not change more than 6.5 percentage points (positively or negatively) in a hypothetical new study. On the 0-100% scale used in this study, this change in average score would not likely lead to different interpretations of general FAIRness. Two repositories, UK PDC and Ktisis, did show a higher degree of uncertainty (with 95% CIs of 19.70% and 26.12%, respectively). For UK PDC, this could be explained by the high variation in the datasets scores depicted previously. For Ktisis, this uncertainty likely stems from the fact that only 9 datasets could be sampled, causing every change in FAIR score to have a large impact on the average.

Zooming in on the contributions of each FAIR main principle to these average FAIR scores, we can look into the specific contributions of each of the 11 principles (Figures presented in Annex). This gives **information about the specific metrics and tests** that are on average most often either passed or failed. A finding worth highlighting from this analysis is that criterion F3 (*Metadata includes the identifier of the data it describes*) is only rarely (and partly) satisfied. From the repositories that scored on this criterion (9), all but one together formed the group of highest scoring repositories on the Findability principle. To satisfy the F3 criterion, the metadata needs to contain a PID or URL which indicates the location of the downloadable data content. The identifier included in the metadata needs to match the identifier provided in the F-UJI assessment request. Manual inspection of some of the repositories revealed that in some cases the repository does include the identifier in the metadata but does not receive a score for the criterion. Possibly, F-UJI may not be able to find the necessary information for criterion F3 in all repositories to score them. Interpretations of this finding are presented in Section 5.2.2. The highest variation in satisfied principles can be found in the Reusability principle. This is clearly reflected in the figure (Annex), with scores showing barely any pattern between repositories. Reusability may be less straightforward to implement for repositories, when compared to the Findability main principle.

5.2.4. Repository characteristics

The sample's FAIR scores can also be interpreted along one of the characteristics that were defined: certification status, supported domains, and geographical area. When interpreting the results in this way, it is important to keep in mind that the information on all repository characteristics was taken from re3data and thus could be inaccurate or outdated⁴⁶.

Variation in FAIR scores according to certification was, though certified repositories (11 repositories, 1500 datasets) tended to have somewhat higher FAIR scores (52.79%) than repositories which are not certified (15 repositories, 3060 datasets, FAIR score = 48.04%). Interestingly, repositories whose certification had expired (5 repositories, 3267 datasets) had even higher FAIR scores (57.58%). Specifically, repositories certified with the Data Seal of Approval (discontinued since it joined forces with the World Data System accreditation to form the CoreTrustSeal in 2018) showed the highest FAIR scores on average (see Annex for the FAIR scores per certification type). Expiration of certification therefore does not seem to imply a decrease in average FAIR scores. An absence of certification does show an average lower FAIR score in the repository, confirming that certified repositories provide curation for datasets with a high FAIR baseline. The findings were all stable (with 95% Confidence Intervals of less than 1 percentage point) and therefore statistically different from one another. However, real-world interpretation of 5-10% differences in FAIRness are negligible.

⁴⁶ See also this blogpost by re3data COREF about the characteristics of location information in re3data: <https://coref.project.re3data.org/blog/mapping-the-global-repository-landscape>

Figure 108. FAIR scores per certification status (certified, not certified, expired certification, as indexed on re3data)

Source: repository assessment using the F-UJI tool, dataset N=7,827

To compare FAIR scores on **repository type**, we first explored the differences in FAIR scores based on the **number of supported domains** as indexed on re3data (Social sciences & Humanities, Life sciences, Natural sciences, Engineering sciences). This analysis (Figure 109, top graph) showed some differences in FAIR scores, but once the repositories were categorised into repository type, these differences disappeared (less than 1% difference in FAIR score, see Annex for an overview of the scores). **Generic repositories** in the sample were defined as repositories who serve three or all four of the re3data main domains (social sciences and humanities, life sciences, natural sciences, and engineering sciences), **disciplinary repositories** were defined as those who serve one or two domains. A caveat of this analysis is that information about the domains was obtained on the repository level and not the dataset level. All datasets in one repository were therefore labelled as concerning all the domains that the repository serves. This introduces a potential bias in this figure due to aggregation errors. The sample was therefore not analysed on domain.

Figure 109. FAIR scores for repositories based on the number of supported domains (as indexed on re3data) and FAIR scores categorised per repository type

Source: repository assessment using the F-UJI tool, dataset N=7,827.

Repositories were also categorised by **geographical area in Europe**, based on the supplied repository location in re3data and on the general distinction of European regions⁴⁷. There was an overrepresentation of north-western repositories ($n = 24$ repositories), which is quite representative of the European landscape as available in re3data (79% of the European repositories in re3data are in north-western Europe). It is important to keep in mind these large differences in sample size when interpreting the average FAIR scores between geographical areas (Figure 110). The figure shows higher average FAIR scores in north-western and central repositories than in south-western and south-eastern repositories.

Figure 110. FAIR scores per geographical area (country as indexed on re3data, area as defined on the general distinction of European regions)

Source: repository assessment using the F-UJI tool, dataset N=7,827.

5.2.5. Room for improvement

Given that no dataset received a 100% FAIR score, there seems to be room for improvement. Results were also interpreted with a focus on the minimum and maximum FAIR scores for each repository. Figure 111 shows this information together. Variation within repositories was small, but the differences that were present within each repository can still provide important insights into the relationship between datasets, repositories, and FAIR.

⁴⁷ We use this classification due to the small number of repositories: https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Regions_of_Europe

The **minimum FAIR scores per repository** (Annex) give an indication of the presence of datasets which are remarkably less FAIR than on average. There are nine repositories for which extremely low FAIR scores occur in their holdings of datasets. These repositories have some overlap with, but are not identical to, the repositories that have the lowest average FAIR score. The lowest minimum scores are composed exclusively of Findability scores; the datasets involved score no points on any of the other principles. For the repositories with higher minimum scores, there is some variation in which principles contribute (or do not contribute) to the scores, but overall, the score composition is close to the average scores.

The **maximum FAIR scores per repository** (Annex) give insight into the most FAIR dataset(s) in each repository (in our sample). None of the maximum scores are “perfect” (100%). Again, there is partial overlap between the repositories which have the lowest maximum scores and those which have the lowest minimum and average scores, but there is still variation between the three categories. Most, but not all, of the five repositories with the highest maximum scores are also in the top five highest average scores.

Taking all this information together, Figure 111 shows that, overall, the average FAIR scores per repository are closer to the maximum score of that repository than to its minimum score. This may imply that the minimum scores indicate anomalies for the repository (e.g. unpublished, hidden, or deleted datasets). The differences between the average and maximum FAIR scores give an indication of the “room for improvement”, or the currently achievable aspiration for all datasets, assuming that they all receive the same curation and documentation from all involved stakeholders (e.g. repository managers, data-depositing researchers, data professionals).

Figure 111. The minimum, average, and the maximum FAIR scores of individual datasets per repository

Source: repository assessment using the F-UJI tool, dataset N=7,827

5.2.6. FAIR development over time

Creating FAIR data is recognized as a long-term developmental or “aspirational” process. Since the initial launch of the FAIR data principles in 2014, much work has been done to facilitate the creation and curation of FAIR data. In an assessment of FAIR data over time, one might therefore expect or hope to see an increase in the FAIRness of datasets starting around 2014. Figure 112 shows that this expectation was not confirmed in the current sample. No overall trend can be discerned regarding the FAIR scores over time. Datasets varied from 1936 to 2022, with some datasets ($n = 725$) having no date available in the metadata. There is a clear increase in the number of datasets in the later years, but the FAIR scores are not significantly higher or lower for more recent datasets than for older ones. For an overview of average FAIR scores per year, see Annex.

Figure 112. The FAIR scores of all datasets with a “date” attribute (n= 7102) by year

Source: repository assessment using the F-UJI tool, dataset N=7,827

Taking a more detailed look at Figure 112, the group of datasets with the highest FAIR scores ($n = 218$) remarkably comes from the period of 1996-2006, a considerable while before the inception of the FAIR principles. Furthermore, there is a group of more recent datasets (2014-2021; $n=51$) which have rather low FAIR scores.

Datasets without a date had significantly lower average FAIR scores than those with a date (11.42% and 59%, respectively. See Annex for a graph). In the example of the UK, PDC mentioned before, the small group of datasets with much higher FAIR scores were also the only datasets in this repository’s sample that have a publication date.

A methodological note to make regarding this analysis is that considerable difficulties were experienced in determining the publication date of each dataset, due to the **heterogeneous use of the metadata attribute “date” in repositories**, if available at all. The “date” attribute has been defined as publication date, date of data collection, date of last edit to the record, date of migration to current system, and also often has been left undefined altogether. This challenge was identified in the earlier stages of the task and remained a standing issue. Figure 112 can therefore not be unambiguously interpreted as any specific definition of “date”, which makes it difficult to translate the figure into any specific finding or recommendation. The question arises how this challenge affects the need for the Commission’s to have a baseline of FAIR characterisation. We will address this point further in our recommendations (Section 5.5).

Another metadata attribute we looked at was “modification date”. This attribute indicated whether F-UJI could find a modification to the dataset in the provenance information. We found this to be true in 1397 datasets (18%), spread over six repositories. The attribute does not indicate the reason for the modification, but it could be an indication of thorough care and curation by the repository and/or depositing researcher. The datasets that did not

have any modification indication could be unaltered, but they could also be modified without this being reported in the provenance information.

5.3. INTERPRETATION OF THE ANALYTICAL RESULTS OF F-UJI

Box 5-3. Key findings of result implementation

- We learned in the trial run that the F-UJI tool may not be able to find all information that could contribute to the FAIR scores. This makes it hard for the study to discern whether the datasets or the assessment tool is the source of observed shortcomings.
- The repository characteristics that were taken into account - certification status, repository type, and geographical area - showed no large implications for FAIR scores. This is hard to interpret, given the fact that the information used was at the repository level rather than at dataset level.
- Assessment results were compared with those from EOSC-Nordic, which revealed striking differences in average FAIR scores. Speculations are made to explain these differences, leading to conclude that sample composition for the landscape analysis is more important than initially thought.

5.3.1. Repository and dataset scores

No dataset obtained a perfect FAIR score of 100%, although quite a few datasets came near. Assuming our sample is representative of the European landscape, this finding seems to indicate that we currently lack the necessary means to produce completely FAIR data. As the FAIR principles were formulated as being “aspirational”, this is not a troubling outcome. Moreover, we must bear in mind that these are the FAIR scores as F-UJI assesses them, based on its metrics that are the FAIRsFAIR interpretations of the FAIR principles. Manual inspection of the datasets with the highest scores (95%) revealed failed tests related to the Interoperability and Reusability principles. To achieve complete FAIRness (as defined and measured by F-UJI), steps need to be taken with regards to semantic resources (I1-02M), data content (R1-01MD), licenses (R1.1-01M), and recommended file formats (R1.3-02D). However, **this study cannot discern whether the datasets or the assessment tool is the source of the shortcomings here**. It may be the case that the datasets are already perfectly FAIR, but F-UJI is not able to retrieve all relevant information to pass all relevant tests. One way in which repositories can ensure they receive their highest possible scores when using an assessment tool is by implementing Content Negotiation (see Section 5.1.2)

or FAIR Signposting⁴⁸, assuming that assessment tools such as F-UJI are aware of these implementations.

Average scores varied considerably in the sample, while internal repository variation was low. **Many of the F-UJI tests, and more broadly the FAIR principles in general, measure repository characteristics.** This suggests that an improvement of FAIR-enabling practices in a repository will yield considerable increases in FAIR scores for most datasets in their holdings (either new or newly curated datasets). To further understand and explain individual FAIR scores, it could be informative to look into dataset level factors such as domain and data type. Extremely low scores could be explained by data types that are more difficult to make FAIR. Such findings could drive initiatives to focus FAIR efforts on these areas of science that need more support.

5.3.2. Repository characteristics: certification, domain, geographical area

The repository characteristics that were taken into account (certification status, repository type, geographical area) showed no large implications for FAIR scores. As mentioned before, these findings may be difficult to interpret due to possible aggregation errors, because the information used was at the repository level and self-supplied to re3data. For more accurate comparisons on such characteristics, metadata would need to be collected on the dataset level and taken from an up-to-date source.

Certified and previously certified repositories had slightly higher scores than non-certified repositories, suggesting that certification may imply a certain level of care for datasets that improves FAIR characteristics. However, the differences were not large enough for meaningful interpretations. Repository certification is independent of the FAIR principles, despite a strong overlap in ambitions towards enabling data reuse. Therefore, the impact of a certification status on FAIR score may not be very large. Moreover, the re3data metadata gives no indication of whether repositories without certification are currently working to obtain it or otherwise implement FAIR and/or trustworthy practices. The same is true for the repositories with expired certification status. These repositories scored highest on FAIRness, which may be because they are in the process of renewing their certification or are otherwise still adhering to trustworthy requirements. Repositories with currently expired certifications obtained their initial certification at the early stages of interest in trustworthiness and long-term preservation, which could be an indication of higher affinity with the practices. However, as mentioned previously, assessment tools are only one way of measuring FAIRness and one interpretation of the FAIR principles. A repository making an effort to be more FAIR may not focus on increasing their outcome scores on a specific

⁴⁸ Signposting is an approach that data providers can use to indicate to machines where certain information, including the metadata needed in FAIR assessments, can be found, see <https://signposting.org/FAIR/>

assessment tool, but rather take a more general approach that is not directly reflected in an assessment tool.

Some differences in FAIR scores were observed for repositories serving a different number of domains. However, when aggregating this information to **repository type**, these differences disappeared. Since domain information was collected on the repository level, an analysis to compare FAIR scores in different domains on dataset level would not provide accurate information. To achieve this, metadata would need to be collected to determine the domain for each dataset. With information like this, insights could be obtained about which domains show more or less implementation of FAIR practices. Could it be that there is less interest in an uptake of the FAIR principles in a specific domain, or that uptake is harder? Or might the FAIR principles be less applicable to datasets from a given domain, for instance because of the great variation in data types, many of which are qualitative in nature? Further investigation would be needed to provide better insights.

Categorising Europe into **geographical regions** is not straightforward and for this part of the study we should keep in mind that the broad north-western European region makes up the largest European part of the re3data registry⁴⁹. To accurately depict the European landscape, these unequal group sizes should be reflected.

No increase of **FAIR scores over time** was observed. Repositories don't use the "data" metadata field consistently. At the same time, trustworthy repositories practised FAIR principles before this concept emerged in 2014. To really see an increase in overall FAIR scores, focus may need to be on Interoperability and Reusability, which are FAIR aspects that are notably more difficult to satisfy. Culture change in science will always be a slow development, and the FAIR principles may therefore need to be considered to be in its early stages still.

5.3.3. Consultation with sample repositories

To help validate the findings of the systematic assessments, the repositories in the sample (see Annex) were invited for a consultation session. Representatives from 22 of the 31 repositories joined the online workshop, in which they were informed about the study, the F-UJI tool, and the high-level F-UJI FAIR assessment results. Robert Huber, one of the developers of F-UJI, was also present to provide skilled input. There was active interest in F-UJI and in the information that the tool provides per dataset to explain the FAIR score. It was emphasised that nuanced information, which cannot always be provided in this large and largely machine-executed study, is essential for repositories to understand how they can adapt their internal processes and the dataset metadata to improve the scores. In addition, it relates to the well-known concern that FAIR scores from assessment tools might be interpreted in a too absolute sense, rather than in a consultation setting. We also learned that, since the moment we collected information from re3data for the study,

⁴⁹ <https://www.re3data.org/browse/by-country/>

metadata elements, such as the certification status, of some of the repositories involved have changed. Moreover, F-UJI and the underlying metrics have also since been updated. This underlines how the study is a snapshot in time of an ever-developing field.

5.3.4. Consultation with EOSC-Nordic

Throughout this study, contact has been established with the EOSC-Nordic project⁵⁰ and their work package on FAIR data. In this work package, one of the objectives is to help Nordic and Baltic repositories become more FAIR compliant and promote incentives for the uptake of FAIR data in the region. To this end, EOSC-Nordic used FAIR assessment tools to assess the FAIRness of their sample continuously for the past two years. This approach was complemented by webinars and personal support meetings to assist repositories in increasing their FAIR-enabling qualities. Their deliverable *D4.1. An assessment of FAIR-uptake among regional digital repositories*⁵¹ was used in our study to draw inspiration for our methodology, though EOSC-Nordic initially used a different tool: the FAIR Data Systems (FDS)/Wilkinson evaluation tool⁵². EOSC-Nordic later switched to using F-UJI. A new deliverable depicting this change and their more recent results, D4.3 Report on Nordic and Baltic repositories and their uptake of FAIR, will appear later this year.

Consultation with EOSC-Nordic partners was re-established after our assessment was completed, to compare results. The EOSC-Nordic assessments done in May 2022 with the F-UJI tool, personally communicated for the purpose of comparison, showed an average FAIR score of 24.5%, which was considerably lower than our sample average of 54.6% and their own previous assessments using the FDS assessment tool (34.4%). EOSC-Nordic have consulted the developers of both assessment tools to investigate the differences in their tools' results further. In our work, the topic of comparability was also raised. Section 5.4 covers our considerations on the comparability of assessment tools and their results.

The most clear difference between the studies, which could explain the striking differences in results, is the **sample composition**. EOSC-Nordic worked with a larger number of repositories, but assessed a lower number of datasets for each repository. Their scope was also limited to the Nordic and Baltic regions, but they included all repositories in this region that assigned unique identifiers to individual datasets. The inclusion of smaller and potentially less FAIR-aware repositories could be an explanation for their lower scores. As we saw in our study results, the differences in FAIR scores were quite large between repositories, and much smaller within repositories. Including more repositories could therefore influence the average score much more than originally thought, despite the reliability of our findings. This would lead to renewed discussions on how to accurately draw a sample for such a landscape analysis. The landscape may be too varied to base

50 <https://eosc-nordic.eu/>

51 D4.1 An assessment of FAIR-uptake among regional digital repositories: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.4045401>

52 <https://fairsharing.github.io/FAIR-Evaluator-FrontEnd/#!/#%2F>

conclusions on a subsample of repositories. Therefore, further studies would need to be done to explore the most insightful sample composition for assessments along this line.

Another difference between the two studies is the **F-UJI versioning**. Whereas EOSC-Nordic used v1.3.5 for their F-UJI assessment, our study used v1.3.9b. Based on the applied versioning convention (Semantic Versioning⁵³), differences between these versions should only be of small significance, but they will most likely have had some influence on the assessment results. This highlights the fact that the static nature of FAIR assessment results can never be interpreted as an accurate depiction of the dynamic landscape it is aiming to capture. With both repositories and assessment tools continuously developing, snapshot assessment results can hardly be extrapolated to a larger context.

Investigating the FAIR scores on the two repositories that overlap in both samples, SND and ICOS, it was observed that scores did not differ much in these cases. For SND, the average FAIR score was 64.6% in the EOSC-Nordic analysis and 68.7% in our assessment. For ICOS, EOSC-Nordic assessed an average FAIR score of 67.3% and we 65%⁵⁴. For both repositories, the differences were small, suggesting that neither the different numbers of datasets nor the different F-UJI versions used influence these scores much. This leads back to the suggestion that the overall sample composition, specifically the selection of repositories, might be the factor contributing to the study differences most.

5.4. CONSIDERATIONS ABOUT FAIR ASSESSMENT TOOLS

Box 5-4. Key findings on FAIR assessment tools

- The datasets used in the trial run (one per repository) were also scored by the FAIR-Enough tool. On average, FAIR-Enough provides higher percentage-scores than F-UJI.
- The two tools differ in the FAIR principles that they assess and in the way they implement their assessments. A close comparison of the computer codes of both tools would be needed to find all differences.
- More efforts are going on to understand different assessment approaches taken.
- Soon after the introduction and wide acceptance of the FAIR data principles in 2014, initiatives were taken to turn the principles into practice, aiming to measure the “FAIRness” of datasets. It was not the aim of the current study to evaluate alternative FAIR assessment methods. Yet, we felt we should at least explore the

⁵³ <https://semver.org/>

⁵⁴ The comparisons are done with assessment results from EOSC-Nordic based on their assessments in May 2022, communicated personally.

effect that different methods could have on FAIR assessment scores. That is the topic of this section.

5.4.1. From FAIR principles to measurable practice

Various initiatives for measuring the “FAIRness” of datasets emerged after the introduction of the principles. Both manual and automated approaches were suggested (e.g. see: Doorn & Dillo, 2016, 2017; Wilkinson et al., 2018). Currently, over 15 alternative tools and methods for measuring FAIRness exist (see box below for a selection; see <https://fairassist.org> for a more extensive list of assessment tools). Please note that using an “automated” may still require manual preparation, as described in Annex.

Box 5-5. List of FAIR assessment tools

Automated:

- F-UJI: <https://www.fairsfair.eu/f-uji-automated-fair-data-assessment-tool>
- FAIR Evaluator <https://fairsharing.github.io/FAIR-Evaluator-FrontEnd/#/>
- FAIR-Enough: <https://fair-enough.semanticscience.org>
- FAIR-Checker: https://fair-checker.france-bioinformatique.fr/base_metrics

Manual:

- DANS FAIR data review: https://docs.google.com/forms/d/e/1FAIpQLSfMzmSOEDcKJVEvfez8iDmN_1Ax_POrm_hSHap01uLaf6zuwg/viewform
- DANS FAIRdat: <https://www.surveymonkey.com/r/fairdat>
- ARDC FAIR self assessment tool: <https://ardc.edu.au/resources/aboutdata/fair-data/fair-self-assessment-tool/>
- Educational/checklist:
- FAIR Aware: <https://www.fairsfair.eu/fair-aware>
- EUDAT Fair Data Checklist: https://www.lcrdm.nl/files/lcrdm/2019-07/HOW%20FAIR%20IS%20YOUR%20DATA_flyer_2.pdf

It appears not so straightforward to turn the principles into practice objectively. It may seem easier to develop a manual evaluation system than an automated one, but the central problem of manual systems is the inevitable subjectivity of the evaluation, apart from, of course, the human work involved in evaluating large numbers of research datasets. On the other hand, automated testing procedures are inevitably mechanistic and therefore may seem more “objective” than they really are. In fact, several of the FAIR principles themselves contain subjective or multi-interpretable elements, as their wording betrays (F2:

“rich metadata”; F3 “clearly include”; A1.2 “where necessary”; I1 “broadly applicable”; I3: “qualified references”; R1: “richly described”; R1.1: “clear license”; R1.2: “detailed provenance”; R1.3: “domain-relevant standards”). So far, no automated method is able to measure every FAIR principle or criterion.

An EOSC Task Force on FAIR Metrics and Data Quality⁵⁵ was set up in November 2021. One of the Recommendations on FAIR Metrics for EOSC is to “Support the definition and implementation of evaluation tools; their thorough assessment and evaluation including inclusiveness; comparison of tools (manual, automated); identification of their biases and applicability in many different contexts, including thematic ones.”

In February 2022 a FAIR evaluation stakeholder meeting “Apples to Apples” was organised to discuss the situation, in which all these different FAIR evaluation methods exist alongside each other. One example demonstrated that the assessment metrics resulting from different methods could be wildly divergent indeed: for the same dataset, one method resulted in 8 points out of 24 (33% FAIR), the other in 20 out of 22 (91% FAIR). Even when one acknowledges that automated assessments and FAIR scores only tell part of the story of reusable data of good quality, such differences could be rather damaging for the credibility of the FAIR concept and raise doubts about the value of FAIR evaluations. Following on the workshop, a series of hackathon sessions is currently taking place. F-UJI participates in this hackathon.

It was not the aim of the current study to evaluate alternative FAIR assessment methods. However, to explore the effect that different methods could have on FAIR assessment scores, we decided to compare F-UJI with one other tool for FAIR testing, which is publicly available on the web, viz. the **FAIR-Enough** tool, developed at the Institute of Data Science at Maastricht University by Vincent Emonet and Michel Dumontier (Emonet & Dumontier, 2021).

The FAIR-Enough tool is largely inspired by the FAIR Evaluator, where people can create collections of tests, allowing communities to define their own set of FAIR assessments. Additionally, “some code for the assessment tests has been re-used from F-UJI” (Emonet & Dumontier, 2021). They find the structure of F-UJI’s code not straightforward when it comes to the assessments. Therefore, they built FAIR-Enough from the ground up, to make adding new FAIR assessments easy, with the goal to encourage communities to contribute assessments that matter to them, and to create collections of tests to validate a resource’s FAIRness following their requirements. The characteristics of F-UJI and FAIR-Enough are described in more detail in Annex.

According to the descriptions of F-UJI and FAIR-Enough, one would expect that the tests of both tools are principally the same. However, a closer comparison brings to light considerable differences in the definitions and groupings of the tests, as well as in the

55 <https://www.eosc.eu/advisory-groups/fair-metrics-and-data-quality>

(maximum) scores of every assessed element. A detailed comparison of all assessed FAIR elements is presented in Annex.

5.4.2. Comparing the F-UJI and FAIR-Enough assessments

To compare the results of the two assessment methods, we used a selection of 33 datasets in 31 European repositories (see Section 5.1.1 about the repository selection process).

The comparison of both assessment tools is visualised in Figure 113. Scores on both tools were standardised to a scale of 0-100% for better comparability. The bar chart shows the scores for each of the 33 datasets generated by FAIR Enough (blue) and F-UJI (red). On average, FAIR Enough provides higher FAIR scores than F-UJI, with only five datasets being an exception to this pattern. Eleven repositories score 90% FAIR according to FAIR-Enough. The corresponding F-UJI scores range from 50% to 83% for these repositories. The highest FAIR score according to F-UJI is for PANGAEA (83%). There are five datasets that score 30% for FAIR-Enough; the corresponding F-UJI scores range from 4% to 52%. Taken together, the two tools generate different outputs in many cases and therefore likely measure different things. A scattergram of these findings is presented in Annex, showcasing that in 60% of the cases the tools don't measure the same things for a dataset.

Figure 113. FAIR % scores per dataset according FAIR-Enough and F-UJI

Source: repository assessment using the F-UJI and FAIR-Enough tools.

For conclusions about this comparison and for recommendations to the EOSC Task Force “FAIR metrics and Data Quality” please see Annex.

5.5. RECOMMENDATIONS

The F-UJI assessment of nearly 8000 datasets from 31 repositories yielded a broad array of information to produce an overview of the European repository and data landscape (Section 5.2). In Section 5.3 this information is interpreted. Section 5.4 provides an insight into different approaches to assessing the FAIRness of datasets.

Drawing on these sections, we here make four recommendations that also take into account international developments with regard to the Open and FAIR EOSC. In particular we consider the recent EOSC Multi-Annual Roadmap 2023-2024⁵⁶, and the CoreTrustSeal Board's request for input for proposed changes to the CoreTrustSeal Requirements⁵⁷. The EOSC Multi-Annual Roadmap 2023-2024 (EOSC MAP23-24) will be incorporated into the Strategic Research and Innovation Agenda (SRIA⁵⁸) for EOSC. The new CoreTrustSeal Requirements (v03.00) will be in place from 2023-2025. The following recommendations therefore anticipate this.

Recommendation 1: In this study the F-UJI tool provided benchmark information about the FAIRness of 7827 datasets in 31 European data repositories. To keep informed about the status of FAIR in Europe, we recommend to the EC **to repeat this assessment** in a few years' time, taking into account the lessons learned from the current study. For more accurate comparisons on certification status, repository type, and geographical area, metadata would need to be collected on the dataset level (which may be challenging) and taken from an up-to-date source. One should take care to define the scope and the repository characteristics in order to *build* on the current benchmark data, rather than collect these again. Moreover, FAIR assessment tools and repository practices will have changed by then, which by itself will affect the data and the possibility to compare findings over time.

Contributes to: This recommendation supports EOSC MAP23-24 Operational Objective OO2 (“Develop and evolve monitoring systems...”) and OO6 (“Provide the metrics and tools to measure adoption of the FAIR principles...”), as well as the Priority Objective at the national level “Incentivise assessment and open certification of data repositories to ensure they enable FAIR outputs, are trustworthy and sustainable...”. In addition, it is recommended to take measures that over time increase the sample of assessable repositories, while maintaining the disciplinary and geographical spread.

Recommendation 2: In Section 5.4 it was discussed that there is no consensus yet about selecting, operationalising and implementing the specific FAIR assessment metrics. Therefore we recommend the EC to monitor and support the efforts with respect to first, understanding essential differences among the major tools and second, **converging**

56 https://eosc.eu/sites/default/files/2022-05/20220523_MAR_02_GL.pdf

57 <https://www.coretrustseal.org/why-certification/meeting-community-needs/trustworthy-data-repository-requirements-review-2023-2025/> (consultation period ends April 15 2022)

58 <https://eosc.eu/sria>

towards a minimal set of FAIR data assessment tools, in terms of exactly what principles to assess how and with what possible scores and/or weights. This is in line with the charter of the EOSC Association Task Force on FAIR Metrics and Data Quality⁵⁹

Contributes to: The recommended FAIR assessment tool convergence supports EOSC MAP23-24 Operational Objective OO6 (“Provide the metrics and tools to measure adoption of the FAIR principles...”). At least one FAIR data assessment service should be provided to repository managers via the EOSC Marketplace, while at the same time it could be part of the EOSC Observatory dashboard, mentioned in Operational Objective OO2 (“Develop and evolve monitoring systems...”).

Recommendation 3: As seen above, **repositories can become more FAIR-enabling** when they implement signposting, use standard metadata fields like “date” (with machine-readable explanation of the value chosen by the repo) and “modified”, and keep their information on re3data up to date. This is a substantial part of the remit of trustworthy digital repositories: they keep data FAIR, in addition to enabling them to become FAIR through e.g. persistent identifiers, licences and metadata standards. However, the current study revealed that datasets in certified repositories on average score only somewhat higher than those in repositories without a certification. Therefore, it makes good sense to make the FAIR principles more explicitly related to certification. The FAIRsFAIR project has done this with recommendations for “**CoreTrustSeal + FAIR**”⁶⁰. CoreTrustSeal+FAIR is the alignment between the 16 CoreTrustSeal Requirements and the 15 FAIR principles. This alignment was made so that repositories can self-assess their trustworthiness and FAIR-enabling status at the same time. The alignment is accompanied by a capability-maturity model which repositories can use to self-assess their practice and associated evidence, with a view to their development and improvement. FAIRsFAIR partners have also responded to CoreTrustSeal’s request for input to proposed changes of the certification requirements. We recommend the EC to **support this complementary development, e.g. by promoting the use of certified repositories.**

Contributes to: Recommendation 3 supports EOSC MAP23-24 Operational Objective OO6 (“...provide frameworks to help in certifying that repository services enable FAIR.”), as well as the Priority Objective at the European level to “Evaluate and as necessary develop trusted environments for managing, preserving and sharing sensitive data” (p.22).

Recommendation 4: Through consultation and collaboration with repositories whose data have been assessed or who aspire to get certified as trustworthy, it is clear that they are interested in exchanging experiences with fellow repositories. To support this, the FAIRsFAIR, SSHOC and EOSC-Nordic projects organised a workshop in January 2022⁶¹ to

59 <https://www.eosc.eu/advisory-groups/fair-metrics-and-data-quality>

60 Hervé L'Hours, Maaïke Verburg, Jerry de Vries, Linas Cepinskas, Ilona von Stein, Robert Huber, Joy Davidson, Patricia Herterich, & Benjamin Mathers. (2022). D4.6 Report on a maturity model towards FAIR data in FAIR repositories (1.0 DRAFT). Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.6090388>

61 <https://www.fairsfair.eu/events/fairsfair-event/workshop-network-fair-enabling-trustworthy-digital-repositories-tdrs>

explore ideas and needs around the creation of a **European network of FAIR-enabling trustworthy digital repositories**. We recommend the EC to support this development.

Contributes to: Recommendation 4 supports the EOSC MAP23-24 Priority Objective at the European level (“Support a network of FAIR-enabling trusted repositories for EOSC, including code repositories, that provide and adopt interoperable tools and aligned services. This network should act as a community platform for shared experience and practices that engages with and uplifts wider data services.” p.14). Furthermore, it supports the planned activities of the EOSC Association Task Force on Long-Term Preservation.⁶²

6. FAIR DATA AND RESEARCH DATA REPOSITORIES

The repository survey complements the work done by the F-UJI assessment to analyse data depositing characteristics, thus addressing Specific Objective 4: to assess research data repositories (public, commercial, institutional, community, federated) on their responsiveness and readiness with respect to the FAIR principles implementation. After an initial pilot testing phase, the repository survey was launched on 1st December 2021 and was closed on 14th February 2022. At that time, it collected 316 responses, with 105 of these being partial responses with parts of the questionnaire remained unfilled. In the analysis of the results all responses received, even partial, have been taken into account.

6.1. TYPOLOGY, SIZE AND DATA SHARING POLICIES OF DATA REPOSITORIES

Respondents to the survey were asked if they manage one or more than one data repository. Almost two thirds manage only one data repository, and slightly over a third manage more than one data repository (Figure 114). Therefore, in general terms more than half of the survey respondents manage just one data repository.

62 <https://www.eosc.eu/advisory-groups/long-term-data-preservation>

Figure 114. Share of surveyed institutions managing one versus several repositories

Source: research data repository survey. Note: Yes indicates that respondent manages one repository.

Within the group of domain specific repositories, answers were distributed across options indicating the management of domain/discipline -specific and general-purpose repositories. More than a half (63%) indicated that they manage a domain/discipline-specific repository, while over a third (38%) indicated that their repository has a general purpose.

Figure 115. Surveyed repository distribution by focus (share of respondents)

Source: research data repository survey.

The distribution of the first level FOS among respondents reflects a relevant prevalence of Natural Science (65%). The other disciplines are well balanced, with a slightly majority of Social Sciences (22%), followed by Humanities (21%), Medical and health Sciences (15%), Engineering and Technology (14%) and agricultural Science (8%).

Figure 116. Domain specific surveyed repository distribution by FOS (share of respondents)

Source: research data repository survey. Note: respondents could select multiple answer options. N = 140.

The respondents mostly managed institutional (50%) or public research data (33%) repositories, however the survey also raised interest among other actors and collected a good number of responses from Research project's data repositories (19%) and other types of repositories.

Figure 117. Surveyed repository distribution by type (share of respondents)

Source: research data repository survey. Note: respondents could select multiple answer options. N=258

The survey had at least one respondent from each EU country, with repositories registered in Germany and United Kingdom representing the highest number of participants taking the survey. 72 respondents indicated a country not included in the EU Member States or Horizon 2020 Associated Countries list. This shows how the survey had relevant international outreach and gathered a good number of responses from other countries beyond the EU and neighbouring countries associated to Horizon 2020.

Figure 118. Surveyed repository distribution by registration country (share of respondents)

Source: research data repository survey, N=232.

When it comes to data storage, however, the geographic dimension is quite variable with almost 1/3 of respondents indicating choice of storing data only in EU countries. This survey didn't ask details on solutions of storage, whether own resources, or procured ones. Future studies in the context of the EOSC sustainability may be tasked to perform a more in-depth analysis of the characteristics of IT resources used and policies concerning data storage. Yet, some general insights on criteria guiding choices for IT storage may also emerge from the interviews for the case studies.

Figure 119. Countries in which surveyed repositories store data (share of respondents)

Source: research data repository survey. N=220.

The survey had respondents from repositories with different age. A good number having existed for less than three years. Yet, the vast majority of responses came from repositories established 3 or more years ago. Through the interviews for the case studies, we aim to also identify the different challenges and level of FAIRness of repositories which have been recently set up compared to the ones with already a history of one or two decades.

Figure 120. Surveyed repository distribution by age (share of respondents)

Source: research data repository survey. N=226.

Though almost 1/3 of repositories is quite limited in size (below 1TByte), most respondents manage repositories of a TByte scale from 1 to 100. But a significant share of 10% of responding repositories hosts data with volumes of PBytes.

Figure 121. Distribution of surveyed repositories by approximate volume of research data that is available for users in these repositories (share of respondents)

Source: research data repository survey. N=219.

While almost half of respondents reported growth rate below or equal to 50%, over the last three years, the survey revealed almost 1/5 of repositories surveyed having doubled or more in size in the same period.

Figure 122. Distribution of repositories by approximate rate of growth in terms of research data volume it holds over the last 3 years in % (share of respondents)

Source: research data repository survey. N=186.

There is wide awareness on current international data policies of different type (e.g. personal data, copyright, security, etc.) with an understandable main prevalence of compliance to international policies underpinned by strong legal frameworks such as personal data protection, FAIR principles of responsible management and copyright policies. However, there is key attention given also to security related policies and aspect of sovereignty.

Figure 123. Types of government or international organisations’ policies that surveyed repositories must comply with (share of respondents)

Source: research data repository survey. Note: respondents could select multiple answer options. N=196.

6.2. FUNDING SOURCES AND GEOGRAPHICAL COVERAGE OF DATA PRODUCTION AND CONSUMPTION

In terms of funding sources, fund by the host institutions of the repository is the relatively most important one among the different sources mentioned. Yet, it is followed by structurally funded repositories and those funded through projects.

Figure 124. Funding sources of surveyed repositories (share of respondents)

Source: research data repository survey. Note: respondents could select multiple answer options. N=230.

6.3. CONCEPT OF TRUSTWORTHINESS AND CERTIFICATION ASPECTS

Survey shows that repositories mostly provide data storage and cataloguing and searching via metadata services.

Figure 125. Services provided by surveyed repositories (share of respondents)

Source: research data repository survey. Note: respondents could select multiple answer options. N= 220. Note: there was one response indicating that none of the above services apply to their activities.

6.4. USE OF STANDARDS, METADATA AND PIDS FOR CROSS-REFERENCING, FINDABILITY AND ACTIONABILITY

In the repository survey, four organisations mention having obtained or having started the CTS certification. A specific question on requirements for a repository to be considered ‘trustworthy’ and on how current certifications schemes contribute to trustworthiness, is included in the interviews for the case studies. From the interviews, both technical (security, measures to avoid data loss and data breach, etc.) and non-technical elements (reputation and long-term sustainability of the institution hosting the repository, choice of a repository as a recommended solution by the scientific community of reference and others) were identified as characterising the concept of trustworthiness among the users of data repositories.

6.5. CASE STUDIES

The aim of case studies is to investigate the context, clarify complex inter-relations of a range of factors as well as get a better understanding of both present and missing information mainly via targeted interviews and complementary desk research.

Out of the 211 complete responses to the repository survey, 149 declared availability to be contacted for a short interview and provided a contact email for this scope. To select the repositories for the case studies, EFIS extracted from this set of 149 respondents an initial shortlist of 21 candidates covering a wide range of attributes in terms of geographic location, general or domain specific nature of the repository, disciplines, openness, size, years of existence and others.

These key attributes for each candidate repository were summarized in a matrix to support a discussion, within the consortium and together with the European Commission, leading to the final selection of the following case studies:

- Bicocca Open Archive Research Data – Italy
- Digital Archive of the Archaeological Map of the Czech Republic – Czech Republic
- ioChem-BD – Spain
- Bavarian Archive for Speech Signals – Germany
- CLARIN.SI - Slovenia

One additional case study was added from the sample used for the F-UJI analysis:

- SURF Data Repository – The Netherlands

Interviews with repository managers were held throughout April and May and revealed some common concerns and views on priority actions, despite operating in different countries and disciplines. One key shared opinion expressed by all interviewees, is that stronger support is needed closer to researchers, who need to be guided by competent data stewards to make data FAIR before depositing and, possibly, since the early stage of the research work. The need to include digital and data management trainings in researchers' curricula was also particularly stressed by managers of data repositories focused on humanities and social sciences.

The case studies are included as a separate annex to this report.

6.6. LONG-TERM DATA PRESERVATION AND CONSIDERATIONS ON SUSTAINABILITY

Only a tiny fraction of respondents indicated a specific time limit in data retention. While 4/5 of the respondents stated that all the data is preserved for the lifetime of the repository.

Figure 126. Do surveyed repositories delete the uploaded data after a specific period of time (share of respondents)?

Source: research data repository survey. N=205.

Creative Commons is by large the most popular license used as a basis of policies implemented for access to data, but other licenses are also used. More than a dozen repositories indicated readiness to use of any available licenses.

Figure 127. Licences surveyed repositories use as a basis for standard terms and conditions for data access (share of respondents)

Source: research data repository survey. Note: respondents could select multiple answer options. N=143.

The main share of respondents indicated that they do not outsource any services. In case services are outsourced it is done by the creation of persistent identifiers (PIDs) (28%) or by data storage (21%), and cataloguing and searching via metadata 10%).

Figure 128. Services that are outsourced by surveyed repositories (share of respondents)

Source: research data repository survey. Note: respondents could select multiple answer options. N=220.

The basic curation (61%) is the leading one, followed by the enhanced curation, but with additional editing of deposited data of accuracy (27%).

Figure 129. Level of data curation performed by surveyed repositories (share of respondents)

Source: research data repository survey. Note: respondents could select multiple answer options. N=219.

6.7. LEVEL OF MATURITY IN FAIRIFICATION – KEY TRENDS, COMMONALITIES AND DIVERGENCES

In order to further assess the FAIR maturity of European research data repositories, we selected a sample of 199 repositories and one unit with data with non-assigned repository, on the basis of research data identifiers in OpenAire and DataCite. Each repository has between 50 and 100 (inclusively) identifiers assigned to it. We also add a separate unit for research data that could not be assigned to a specific research data repository, in order to see if there is variation in terms of FAIRness assessment results for different types of data. We used the F-UJI tool to assess the FAIRness of these repositories in order to provide a broader context for the analysis in this chapter. As the F-UJI tool was discussed in detail in Chapter 4, here we:

- provide an aggregate overview of the assessment as a contextual element of the analysis of this chapter, and not a detailed examination of individual repositories
- do not address the methodological issues here, rather focusing on the aggregate results of the analysis
- we take into account the data type dimension (extracted from DataCite)

The data show that Fairness is the principle that is followed the most, with all repositories scoring at least some points in this dimension. This is not surprising, as we could assess only those datasets that have identifiers, meaning that at least the minimum level of Findability is reached. Indeed, on average, assessed repositories scored 80% in terms of Findability, with the median being even higher at 85%. The interquartile range shows that

half of the repositories scored between 71% and 86%, further suggesting that most repositories seem to have developed

Other areas were assessed at lower levels. The least developed area seems to be Reusability, where the average score was only 31% (median – 30%), and half of the repositories scored between 20% and 40%, with maximum value being 68%. Therefore, while the data Findability seems to be more resolved, enabling data reuse is more limited (which is further complicated by relatively limited Accessibility and Interoperability). The Figure below shows the boxplots of each FAIR dimension.

Figure 130. FAIRness assessment using F-UJI tool by repository

Source: F-UJI assessment of 200 repositories (total dataset N = 18,338).

The largest variation seems to be in terms of interoperability, where both the lowest (0) and highest (1) scoring repositories are not outliers in the sample. Even the interquartile range is relatively large (from 25% to 61%). This finding suggests that variation in the Interoperability dimension is the highest among the tested repository sample. It also suggests, that there are significant learning opportunities in improving interoperability.

Taking the additional data breakdowns, we further look at the types of data stored in the repositories. In addition to extracting PIDs for data, we have also extracted data type, where it was available. We look at this data for repositories. This reduced sample size also means that there is a need for higher caution when extrapolating the implications of these results. The results in the figures show the distribution of research data repository averages for that specific data type. First, however, we show the distribution of research data repositories by data type and the number of data objects by type in that specific repository.

Figure 131. Distribution of data objects across different research data repositories in %

Source: F-UJI assessment of 200 repositories (total number of datasets is 18,338). Number of repositories per data type: Audio N=10, Creative Work N=26, Dataset N=147, Image N=18, Media N=10, NA N=9, Software Code N=4.

We first look at the findability of data of different types. As the figure below shows, the findability score is quite high on average in most cases, with the exception with the NA group, where the data type could not be established. Therefore, the results are as could have been expected, as less information on those data is available overall.

Figure 132. FAIRness assessment using F-UJI tool: findability by data type in %

Source: F-UJI assessment of 200 repositories (total number of datasets is 18,338). Number of repositories per data type: Audio N=10, Creative Work N=26, Dataset N=147, Image N=18, Media N=10, NA N=9, Software Code N=4..

In terms of data accessibility, the scores are lower than for findability in accordance to the general overview, discussed above. The highest variation seems to be among repositories storing datasets, though this is also explainable by larger N for this type of data. On the other hand, there are not outliers in that particular case. Contrary to some of the other FAIR

dimensions (e.g. findability, interoperability), NA scores relatively high in the case of accessibility.

Figure 133. FAIRness assessment using F-UJI tool: accessibility by data type in %

Source: F-UJI assessment of 200 repositories (total number of datasets is 18,338). Number of repositories per data type: Audio N=10, Creative Work N=26, Dataset N=147, Image N=18, Media N=10, NA N=9, Software Code N=4..

Interoperability seems to be more varied. Audio data scores the highest, getting around 80% of the score on average, far exceeding the other types of data. This may suggest that audio data may overall be easier to make interoperable, but this would require new analysis, focusing more specifically on the data types.

Figure 134. FAIRness assessment using F-UJI tool: interoperability by data type in %

Source: F-UJI assessment of 200 repositories (total number of datasets is 18,338). Number of repositories per data type: Audio N=10, Creative Work N=26, Dataset N=147, Image N=18, Media N=10, NA N=9, Software Code N=4..

Finally, in terms of reusability, the scores seem to be mostly similar, with audio data score higher on average, although this may also be affected by a relatively small number of used repositories where we extracted PIDs with audio data.

Figure 135. FAIRness assessment using F-UJI tool: reusability by data type in %

Source: F-UJI assessment of 200 repositories (total number of datasets is 18,338). Number of repositories per data type: Audio N=10, Creative Work N=26, Dataset N=147, Image N=18, Media N=10, NA N=9, Software Code N=4..

Overall, while there is variation in terms of the FAIRness in terms of different data types, a more in-depth analysis would be needed to determine the actual extent of variation and understand the reasons for it (or for the lack of it). What can be seen, however, is that audio data seems to score higher on average, at least to an extent, and data with type not determined when collecting data scores mostly lower. Nonetheless, these differences may be affected by other factors (such as the repositories where they are stored) and subject to biases due to small N.

7. RECOMMENDATIONS

Below we present the key findings, associated recommendations that emerged from the study and a list of suggested actions. As the findings of the different parts of the study pointed towards similar recommendations, we employed a thematic framework that links the recommendations together.

7.1. THEME 1 - PROVISION OF LOCAL SUPPORT FOR RESEARCH DATA MANAGEMENT IS CRUCIAL

Reasoning. This study shows that researchers currently get the help they need at institutional level. More importantly, their institution is where they think they *should* be able to turn to for support in making their data FAIR. The availability of local data stewards would help researchers to overcome some of the obstacles to data sharing and deposition identified in the study (e.g. by providing guidance on data handling, data protection, platforms for data sharing). As noted in a report from the EOSC Minimal Skillset Task Force, a wide range of skilled support staff is needed to support researchers in the production and use of FAIR data; however, local support among European organisations is currently patchy. A recent European University Association (EUA) study found that only

around half of the higher education institutions surveyed provide such support⁶³. While some countries are investing in building data stewardship capacity at institutional level, such as in the Netherlands and Belgium, similar levels of resourcing will not be feasible in all countries. To ensure a level playing field, there is a need to ensure that expertise in data stewardship can be made available to researchers regardless of whether they are in-house or pooled from regional, national or international sources. The EOSC Skills & Training WG recommended in 2021 that a ‘competence centres’ approach to increasing coordinated provision of aligned training to support FAIR and open science should be encouraged and supported⁶⁴. The findings of this study support this recommendation. In recent years, there has also been an increase in the number of research software engineers (RSE) employed at organisations performing research, and this should lead to the availability of more FAIR software over time. Indeed, this study finds that RSEs are among those most familiar with FAIR, and with putting it into practice. However, not all research-performing organisations will be able to provide this level of expertise locally. As such, there is a need to ensure access to such specialist knowledge externally.

Recommendation:

- Researchers must have access to professional data steward expertise to support research data management and to prepare data for sharing and depositing.

Specific actions that should be considered:

- Develop a minimum EU curriculum, and professionalise the cooperation of data stewards with the relevant EC projects, Research Data Alliance working groups and EOSC task forces. In parallel, professionalise Data Steward specialisations in terms of disciplinary research practices.
- Facilitate data stewardship by leveraging relevant EOSC activities to support the development of national or regional data steward networks and competence centres, at which limited resources can be pooled.
- Member States should consider supporting the creation of National Coordination Points for Research Data Management (piloted in the Netherlands) and funding for the creation of local digital competence centres.

63 From principles to practices: Open Science at Europe’s universities 2020-2021 EUA Open Science Survey results. <https://eua.eu/resources/publications/976:from-principles-to-practices-open-science-at-europe%E2%80%99s-universities-2020-2021-eua-open-science-survey-results.html>.

64 European Commission, Directorate-General for Research and Innovation, Digital skills for FAIR and Open Science: report from the EOSC Executive Board Skills and Training Working Group, Manola, N. (editor), Lazzeri, E. (editor), Barker, M. (editor), Kuchma, I. (editor), Gaillard, V. (editor), & Stoy, L. (editor), Publications Office, 2021, <https://data.europa.eu/doi/10.2777/59065>.

- Develop a blueprint for implementing different models of data stewardship provision such as those being piloted in the Netherlands⁶⁵, focusing on the practicalities of implementation such as skills and staffing, costs and sustainability.
- Individual countries and/or the EC may wish to support the development of a pan-European network of expertise such as that offered by the Software Sustainability Institute (SSI) in the UK, which is supported by UKRI. The SSI offers services to researchers such as virtual surgery sessions and software health checks to support researchers in adopting best practices with regard to developing sustainable software.
- A number of the H2020 INFRAEOSC projects aimed to establish knowledge hubs that provide access to training materials and resources to support FAIR data stewardship. Similar efforts are planned among the new Horizon Europe INFRAEOSC projects. As such, there is potential for the duplication of effort, as well as widely acknowledged challenges associated with sustaining such hubs beyond the lifetime of the projects that created them. The EC and EOSC Association may wish to jointly support a project that could pool and harmonise the information contained in the existing knowledge hubs and work proactively with the new tranche of INFRAEOSC projects to ensure that upcoming knowledge hub efforts are coordinated and align with previous work, leading to a shared body of high-quality resources that is more sustainable and can support data stewardship activities at Member State level. To ensure that work on coordinating knowledge hub activity reflects current and emerging priorities, the EOSC Research Careers and Curricula task forces should be actively involved in any initiative taken forward.

7.2. THEME 2 - LIFECYCLE SUPPORT IS NEEDED FOR DATA MANAGEMENT PLANNING AND IMPLEMENTATION

Reasoning. Good data management is crucial to ensuring that FAIR data is produced. This is best realised through the development and updating of data management plans (DMPs). This study finds that the development of DMPs is becoming increasingly common, with almost three-quarters of respondents to the researchers' survey reporting that they do this 'sometimes' or 'always'. However, as other FAIR-aligned activities were less frequently reported, it appears there may be a disconnect between what is planned and what is actually carried out. Although many funding bodies now either encourage or require periodic updating of DMPs, a recent report found that there was a perceived lack of

65 Jetten, M. et al. (2021). Professionalising data stewardship in the Netherlands. Competences, training and education. Dutch roadmap towards national implementation of FAIR data stewardship. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.4623713>.

feedback on the content of such DMPs⁶⁶. This suggests there is a need for access to continuous support and feedback over the entire research lifecycle in order to review, update and – most importantly – ensure that DMPs are implemented in practice. Some institutions provide such advice and guidance, but others do not have the in-house resources to support this. Providing such support could help to reduce the challenges to data sharing and depositing identified by researchers, as well as increasing awareness of data handling standards, data access and conditions of reuse.

Recommendation:

- Provide ongoing support to researchers for data management planning over the entire research lifecycle to ensure that DMPs are realistic in scope, cover all aspects required to realise the production of FAIR data, and to ensure that planned actions are actually implemented.

Specific actions that should be considered:

- Collaboratively identify and promote examples of real-world DMPs that effectively address common barriers such as handling sensitive data and dealing with legal issues. The quality and implementation of DMPs should also be assessed to understand how they contribute to researchers' practices. Several data management planning tools offer users the option to make their DMPs public, and some provide access to these DMPs via their platform (e.g. the DMP online collection of public DMPs⁶⁷). Efforts have been made in recent years to provide access to a body of peer-reviewed DMPs such as the LIBER DMP Catalogue⁶⁸. However, the body of public DMPs is spread across various platforms, and different approaches are taken to the metadata associated with these DMPs. The EC may wish to commission a small study to identify sample DMPs from the pool of completed H2020 projects as well as those starting to emerge from the new Horizon Europe projects. These could be used to build a DMP reference collection with improved search functionality, by extending the DMP catalogue metadata used by LIBER (e.g. to include more fields relating to the specific challenges encountered and the nature of the data being managed).

66 Spichtinger, D. Data Management Plans in Horizon 2020: what beneficiaries think and what we can learn from their experience [version 1; peer review:2 approved, 1 approved with reservations] Open Research Europe 2021,1:42. <https://doi.org/10.12688/openreseurope.13342.1> .

67 https://dmponline.dcc.ac.uk/public_plans.

68 <https://libereurope.eu/working-group/research-data-management/plans/>.

- Where resources allow, research-performing organisations should provide domain-specific research data management planning support locally⁶⁹. Where local support is not feasible, the development of shared domain-specific resources should be supported and maintained using resources provided by all stakeholders.
- Consider the establishment of a shared panel of domain-specific data stewards at national level who would be available to support researchers over the lifetime of their projects, co-creating DMPs that will lead to the production and availability of FAIR data. Providing access to on-demand advice and guidance over the lifetime of a project offers greater potential to ensure that appropriate standards are used, selected outputs are deposited with trustworthy repositories, and persistent identifiers are assigned to outputs. Such support would be particularly beneficial to those working in institutions without local data steward expertise and support.

7.3. THEME 3 - FACILITATE THE ASSESSMENT OF RESEARCH DATA FAIRness, AND TRACK PROGRESS TOWARDS FAIR-ENABLING SERVICES AND SUPPORT

Reasoning. In order to implement recommendations and improve research data management processes, it is important that research-performing organisations, repositories and data services are able to assess their current FAIR-enabling capabilities and identify gaps. Periodical assessment and monitoring of progress in terms of FAIR-enabling capabilities and the FAIRness of data will improve our shared understanding of the European research data landscape and highlight the areas in which improvement is most needed. Measuring data FAIRness at scale needs to be carried out in an automated fashion, using tools such as F-UJI. Other assessment tools and initiatives exist in addition to F-UJI, and as yet there is no consensus with regard to selecting, operationalising and implementing specific FAIR metrics. Therefore, the possible variety in approaches to operationalising FAIR criteria is another challenge that also needs to be addressed.

A substantial part of the remit of trustworthy digital repositories is to keep data FAIR, in addition to enabling data to become FAIR – for instance, through the assignment of persistent identifiers, or by demanding and curating sustainable file formats. The present study reveals that on average, datasets in certified repositories score only slightly higher than those in repositories without certification. Repositories can become more FAIR-enabling by implementing signposting to help automated assessment tools find the information expected, use standard metadata fields such as ‘date’ and ‘modified’, and keep

⁶⁹ As recommended by FAIRsFAIR in 2020. Davidson, J., Engelhardt, C., Proudman, V., Stoy, L., & Whyte, A. (2019). D3.1 FAIR Policy Landscape Analysis (Version v1.0_draft). <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.3558172>.

their information in the re3data.org repository registry up to date. The FAIRsFAIR project has developed recommendations for 'CoreTrustSeal + FAIR', which aligns the 16 CoreTrustSeal certification requirements with the 15 FAIR principles: another instrument to become more FAIR-enabling. Consultation and collaboration should be undertaken with repositories whose data have been assessed or who aspire to become certified as trustworthy, or which make clear that they are interested in a network to exchange experiences and advance together with fellow repositories.

Recommendations:

- Research-performing organisations should carry out self-assessments to review their current infrastructure and support provision, identifying gaps in their support for research data management.
- Repositories should assess the FAIRness of their data holdings and identify where their services could be improved in order to progress their journey towards being FAIR-enabling.
- The development of an international network of trusted digital repositories⁷⁰ should be supported to share knowledge and practical experiences with regard to certification and improving FAIR-enabling capabilities.

Specific actions that should be considered:

- Research-performing organisations should consider making use of self-assessment frameworks such as ACME-FAIR⁷¹ and Do I-Pass for FAIR⁷² to review their current capability for enabling FAIR. Based on the outcomes, organisations should develop action plans to implement improvements⁷³.
- Repositories should assess the FAIRness of their research data holdings using automated tools such as F-UJI or similar. Carrying out such assessments provides a snapshot of data FAIRness at a point in time but also helps to identify areas of repository service provision where improvements might be made.
- At European level, support should be given to monitoring efforts with respect to first, understanding the essential differences between the major FAIR assessment tools; and second, converging towards a minimum set of FAIR data assessment tools.

70 The FAIRsFAIR, SSHOC and EOSC-Nordic projects organised a workshop in January 2022 to explore ideas and needs surrounding the creation of a European network of FAIR-enabling, trustworthy digital repositories.

71 <https://www.fairsfair.eu/acme-fair-guide-rpo>.

72 de Bruin, T., Coombs, S., de Jong, J., Haslinger, I., van den Hoogen, H., Huigen, F., Jetten, M., Koster, J., Miedema, M., Öllers, S., Slouwerhof, S., Verheul, I., & Ringersma, J. (2020). Do I-PASS for FAIR. A self assessment tool to measure the FAIR-ness of an organization (Version 1). Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.4080867>.

73 The following case study provides an overview of work undertaken by Utrecht University. Verburg, M., & Grootveld, M. (2022, February 23). Recognising and implementing FAIR throughout the organisation. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.6413951>.

These should determine exactly what principles to assess, how, and with what possible scores and/or weights. To achieve this requires understanding of and convergence between assessment tools, preferably at international level, from whence it can spread to national and institutional levels. In 2022, the EOSC Association Task Force on FAIR Metrics and Data Quality organised workshops with the developers of several FAIR assessment tools, including F-UJI. Based on these workshops, the task force will make recommendations to both tool developers and repositories – for instance, with regard to benchmark environments. The EOSC Association, in particular its Task Force on Long-Term Data Preservation, would be the appropriate body to endorse and promote the recommended processes. The combination of setting requirements and providing recommendations and training would facilitate a better understanding of the differences between the major FAIR assessment tools. Repeated assessment exercises, such as those carried out in this study, could then help to track progress.

- Guidelines should be developed to support harmonised monitoring at both European and national levels. EOSC-A could use its network to promote the use of automated FAIR assessment tools. It could also coordinate the development of assessment and progress-tracking guidelines, possibly contributing to harmonising the different approaches employed by research data repositories and research-performing organisations.
- At European level, support should be ensured for the complementary development of criteria for trustworthy repositories and FAIR by promoting the use of certified repositories as well as supporting the creation of a European network of FAIR-enabling trustworthy digital repositories.

7.4. THEME 4 - A CONTINUING NEED TO RAISE AWARENESS OF HOW FAIR BENEFITS SCIENCE AND SOCIETY

Reasoning. The EOSC FAIR Working Group recommended in 2020 that awareness raising is needed at all levels, and that funding is needed to enable the provision of training, education and community-specific support. While the present study shows that there is some familiarity with FAIR principles among researchers, more than two-thirds of respondents had either not heard of the FAIR principles or did not fully understand what they mean. Common misconceptions also persist, such as “FAIR data must also be open data”. As the vast majority of respondents resonate with the *concepts* behind the FAIR principles and are primarily motivated to share data to support the acceleration of scientific research/public benefit rather than to meet funding body or national requirements, it is important that awareness-raising activities focus on how FAIR data can support these aims.

Recommendation:

- Continued efforts to raise awareness concerning the FAIR principles and what they mean in a practical sense, focusing on how FAIR data supports the acceleration of science and public benefit.

Specific actions that should be considered:

- Develop a shared collection of real-life examples across different disciplines, showing how FAIR data practices have led to real-world benefits and/or the acceleration of science. These can be used during awareness-raising campaigns at European, national and institutional level. The EC and the EOSC Association could encourage the knowledge hubs mentioned under Theme 1 to refer to these examples.
- At European level, coordinate and support cooperation between EOSC Association task forces and the range of current and future EOSC-related projects, to harmonise dissemination activities and amplify key messages. For example, a working group, similar in its terms of reference to the EOSC Cluster Projects Communication & Engagement group, could be established to include relevant members of the current tranche of INFRAEOSC-supported projects and relevant EOSC task forces. The EOSC Cluster Projects Communication & Engagement group met every three months, allowing members to share best practices and build on and promote each other's efforts. Such a group could develop a shared set of key messages concerning the benefits of FAIR in different contexts, and show how the EOSC can support the realisation of a FAIR ecosystem. Setting up and coordinating the efforts of such a group would require a small amount of administrative support, which could perhaps be provided by the EOSC Association.

ANNEXES

ANNEX 1. F-UJI ASSESSMENT

Dataset Sample selection

The process of selecting datasets from the list of repositories appeared not to be self-evident. Though F-UJI provides an *automated* tool (machine2machine) to perform FAIR data assessments, selecting datasets requires a process that must be performed partly manually.

To give all repositories the chance to reach the highest assessment score possible, the harvesting protocol endpoint for each repository was included in the assessment. The repositories that did not have an endpoint publicly available (on re3data, openDOAR⁷⁴, openarchives⁷⁵, or on their own website) were contacted by email personally to provide the endpoint to the project team.

Selecting PIDs for assessment has been done as automatically as possible, though in this process it was necessary to make some explicit choices, which are set out in Figure 136.

74 <https://v2.sherpa.ac.uk/opensoar/>

75 <https://www.openarchives.org/Register/BrowseSites>

Figure 136. Flowchart of PID selection process

Each green diamond in Figure 136 indicates a manual process. For each repository we started the selection procedure by finding (in re3data) or asking the repository itself for an endpoint in which the persistent identifiers are listed (email). Mostly - in 22 cases - OAI-PMH endpoints were given, but also other types of API's were consulted, like SPARQL, Catalogue Service for the Web (CSW) or even static index files (for one repository an HTML file was used). We then searched for "suitable" PIDs in the endpoint. This involved checking the metadata of an object to find out its type, which for the F-UJI assessment has to be "dataset".

We also looked at other indicators, like the OAI-PMH set names, which could be indicative for certain types of scholarly objects listed there. In some repositories both Handle and DOI identifiers for one object were available. In that case DOI's were preferred (at the object level), because F-UJI could then use the DataCite Content Negotiation feature within the assessment of this object. If no PID could be found, we collected the landing page URLs. Landing pages can also be used by F-UJI as a starting point for collecting metadata, instead of dereferencing a PID.

If no suitable endpoint could be found at all at the repository, we looked for existing DOIs of this repository in the DataCite REST API⁷⁶, as most of the DOIs are also registered at

76 <https://support.datacite.org/docs/api>

DataCite. (This makes the F-UJI FAIR assessment more effective. By itself, however, the DOI registration process at DataCite, performed by the source repository, is one more link in the chain away from the source repository and therefore less desirable.) Next, after determining the appropriate PIDs, it was a minor effort to collect the PIDs automatically and take a random, unique sample of up to 300 PIDs per repository. A sample size of 300 should be enough in a normally distributed environment within 95% confidence level. A few selected repositories were too small or had few scholarly objects of type "dataset", therefore no random sample could be taken.

How the automated F-UJI FAIR assessment tool works

F-UJI is a web service based on assessment criteria developed in the context of the FAIRsFAIR⁷⁷ project (Devaraju & Huber, 2020). "uji" means "test" in the Malayan language.

A word on terminology: in the FAIR data context, the word "principle" is often used for the main principles F, A, I, and R, as well as for the sub-principles F1, F2, etc. We will use the term **FAIR main principle** for F, A, I, and R and **FAIR principle** for F1, F2, etc. A **metric** is the unit being tested in the assessment procedure, and each metric yields a **score**.

For measuring the extent to which research data objects are FAIR, F-UJI currently uses the FAIRsFAIR data object assessment metrics v0.4⁷⁸. These are 17 defined assessment metrics that address 12 of the total of the 15 FAIR principles, at both data and metadata level. The FAIR principles *not* addressed by the assessment metrics, are A1.1, A1.2 (open protocol, authentication and authorization) and I2 (FAIR vocabularies).

F-UJI conducts at least one test per assessment metric, except for the "FSF-A2-01M" metric that *Metadata must remain available, even if the data is no longer available*: this does not contribute to the FAIRness of an existing data object, but instead to a deleted object and therefore cannot be tested automatically.

As a result, F-UJI reports on the following 11 FAIR principles (maximum score indicated in brackets): F1(2), F2(2), F3(1), F4(2), A1(3), I1(3), I3(1), R1(4), R1.1(2), R1.2(2), R1.3(2). Per dataset F-UJI reports on the scores that are earned per principle, based on the associated tests performed and the maximum scores attainable. In the results presented below, these scores are also aggregated per FAIR main principle: F(7), A(3), I(4), R(10), which add up to a total FAIR score of at most 24. (For more details see Annex for Definitions and scores, which lists these principles and maximum scores).

The F-UJI tool has the option to carry out assessments with or without Content Negotiation based on the DOI URL to retrieve DataCite JSON metadata. Most of the DOI persistent identifiers are also registered at DataCite and can be found via the DataCite REST API⁷⁹. If the option is not used, F-UJI uses the information it finds on the landing page URL to which

77 <https://www.fairsfair.eu>

78 <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.4081213>

79 <https://support.datacite.org/docs/api>

the identifier refers. When Content Negotiation is turned on, however, F-UJI retrieves this metadata from DataCite, which harvests the metadata from repositories that are registered DataCite DOI providers. In the full analysis Content Negotiation was turned on. Such Content Negotiation is not available for repositories using other identifiers than DOI, which may therefore be disadvantaged if their metadata is not found on the landing page. Out of the 31 repositories in the sample, 26 use DOIs. Additionally, 3 use Handles, 1 uses URN:NBN, and 1 a local identifier.

The F-UJI assessment in the current study was executed using version v1.3.9b of the software based on V0.4 of the Data Object Assessment Metrics⁸⁰.

Average FAIR score per principle

Figure 137. The distribution of average FAIR scores for the sample (n = 7827) per principle in %

Source: compiled by the authors

80 Metrics specification: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.4081213>

Correlation average and standard deviation

Figure 138. The correlation between the average and standard deviation of FAIR scores ($r = -0.05$)

Note: Correlation was calculated for the non-percentage scores (0-4) for more straightforward interpretation. UK PDC was omitted from this graph, since the outlier influenced the graph and correlation coefficient strongly (UK PDC included: $r = -0.11$).

Composition of principle scores per repository

Figure 139. The compositions of the principle scores per repository

Note: not all principles receive equal weight in the F-UJI assessment (e.g. I1 can score 3 points while I3 can score only 1 point).

Average FAIR scores and repository characteristics

Figure 140. Average FAIR scores according to certification type

Note: Not certified = 46.30%; CoreTrustSeal current = 52.79%; CoreTrustSeal expired = 56.38%; Data Seal of Approval = 60.09%; World Data System = 54.95%

Table 18. Calculation of average FAIR scores on repository type categorization

Number of supported domains			Average FAIR score (%)	Repository type	Average FAIR Score (%)
	Repositories (N)	Datasets (N)			
One	13	3282	48.60%	Disciplinary	50.60%
Two	7	2097	54.33%		
Three	2	309	38.98%	Generic	50.10%
Four	9	2139	52.57%		

Maximum and minimum FAIR scores per repository

Figure 141. Maximum (left) and minimum (right) FAIR score per repository

Note: The repository has at least one dataset in our sample with this score.

FAIR scores analysed on year

Figure 142. Average FAIR scores per year in the dataset

Note: Datasets with no "date" attribute available in their metadata are represented by the red bar. There is no clear increase in FAIR scores over time.

Figure 143. FAIR scores by "date" availability in %

Note: Difference in average FAIR scores between datasets with ($n = 7102$) and without ($n = 725$) a "date" attribute available in the dataset metadata (as found by F-UJI). The error bars represent the relative standard deviations (25.56% and 86.27%, respectively).

Overview of repositories for F-UJI FAIR assessment

Repository Name (English Native Language Shorthand)	URL	re3data ID	Datasets selected
Flanders Marine Institute Vlaams Instituut voor de Zee (VLIZ)	http://www.vliz.be/en	r3d100010661	300
Digital Repository of Ireland Taisclann Dhigiteach na hÉireann (DRI)	https://repository.dri.ie	r3d100011805	300
DataverseNO	https://dataverse.no/	r3d100012538	300
Archaeology Data Service (ADS)	https://archaeologydataservice.ac.uk/	r3d100000006	300
UK Polar Data Centre (UK PDC)	https://www.bas.ac.uk/data/uk-pdc/	r3d100010120	300
PANGAEA	https://www.pangaea.de/	r3d100010134	300
Swedish National Data Service Svensk nationell datatjänst (SND)	https://snd.gu.se/en	r3d100010146	300
EASY	https://easy.dans.knaw.nl/ui/home	r3d100010214	300
UK Data Archive (UKDA)	https://www.data-archive.ac.uk/	r3d100010215	300
4TU.ResearchData (4TU)	https://data.4tu.nl/info/en/	r3d100010216	300
GESIS Search GESIS-Suche (formerly: GESIS Datenbestandskatalog (DBK))	https://search.gesis.org/	r3d100010251	300
Movebank Data Repository	https://www.datarepository.movebank.org/	r3d100010469	300
Austrian Social Science Data Archive (AUSSDA)	https://data.aussda.at/	r3d100010483	300

Irish Social Science Data Archive (ISSDA)	http://www.ucd.ie/issda/	r3d100010497	60
Apollo - University of Cambridge Repository	https://www.repository.cam.ac.uk/	r3d100010620	300
Institutional repository of the Spanish National Research Council Repositorio institucional del Consejo Superior de Investigaciones Científicas (DIGITAL.CSIC)	https://digital.csic.es/?locale=en	r3d100011076	300
Social Scientific Research Documentation Centre Repository Kutatási Dokumentációs Központ (RDC)	http://openarchive.tk.mta.hu/	r3d100011132	297
DARIAH-DE Repository	https://de.dariah.eu/repository	r3d100011345	300
ZBW Journal Data Archive	http://journaldata.zbw.eu	r3d100012190	201
Integrated Carbon Observation System Portal (ICOS)	https://www.icos-cp.eu/node/1	r3d100012203	300
Research Data Repository (RADAR)	https://www.radar-service.eu/en	r3d100012330	132
National Research Institute for Agriculture, Food and the Environment Data INRAE	https://data.inrae.fr/	r3d100012673	300
SISMER Oceanographic Data (French Research Institute for Exploitation of the Sea) IFREMER-SISMER Portail de données marines	http://data.ifremer.fr/	r3d100012965	300
SURF Data Repository	https://repository.surfsara.nl	r3d100013084	300
TU Graz Repository - Graz University of Technology	https://repository.tugraz.at/	r3d100013565	21
Zenodo	https://zenodo.org/	r3d100010468	300

Mendeley Data	https://data.mendeley.com/	r3d100011868	300
Slovenian Social Science Data Archives Archiv Družboslovnih Podatkov (ADP)	https://www.adp.fdv.uni-lj.si/eng/	r3d100010487	300
Ktisis - institutional repository of Cyprus University of Technology	https://ktisis.cut.ac.cy	r3d100013287	9
Digital Academic Archives and Repositories Digitalni Akademski Arhivi I Repozitoriji (DABAR)	https://dabar.srce.hr/en	r3d100013510	51
Rovira i Virgili Institutional Repository Repositori institucional de la Universitat Rovira i Virgili (URV)	http://repositori.urv.cat/en/	r3d100013438	156

Characteristics of F-UJI and FAIR-Enough

F-UJI provides scores for each FAIR principle that is met, either completely or partially. A total of 16 metrics has been implemented, but the number of tests vary per FAIR principle, and so does the number of points that can be scored. There are five tests for Findability, three for Accessibility, three for Interoperability and three for Reusability. It appeared to be unfeasible to operationalize and invent automatic tests for the FAIR principles A2, I2, and R1.3⁸¹ (Devaraju & Huber, 2020).

The maximum number of points that can be scored ranges between 3 for Interoperability and 10 for Reusability. Of course, the scores can be weighted to give each FAIR letter the same influence in the FAIR total, for instance by calculating percentage scores.

Except for raw scores and percentages, F-UJI also calculates the “FAIR maturity” per element, criterion, and total, in an attempt to implement the Specification and Guidelines of the FAIR Data Maturity Model Working Group of the Research Data Alliance (RDA): <https://www.rd-alliance.org/groups/fair-data-maturity-model-wg> (Willems, 2020). However, for the analysis presented here the added value of the maturity scores is limited, as these scores boil down to a grouping of the raw scores. For instance, F-scores lower than 3 result in a maturity of 1, scores between 3 and 6 in maturity 2, and scores of more than 6 in maturity level 3.

The FAIR-Enough tool is largely inspired by the FAIR Evaluator, where people can create collections of tests, allowing communities to define their own set of FAIR assessments. Additionally, “some code for the assessment tests has been re-used from F-UJI” (Emonet & Dumontier, 2021). They find the structure of F-UJI’s code not straightforward when it comes to the assessments. Therefore, they built FAIR-Enough from the ground up, to make adding new FAIR assessments easy, with the goal to encourage communities to contribute assessments that matter to them, and to create collections of tests to validate a resource’s FAIRness following their requirements. However, the FAIR principles have been formulated so generically, that one wonders whether domain-specific assessments are desirable. One could argue that we rather need more unity in FAIR metrics than more diversity: diverging interpretations and implementations of the principles lead to differences in metrics that may be hard to understand and explain.

According to the descriptions of F-UJI and FAIR-Enough, one would expect that the tests of both tools are principally the same. However, a closer comparison brings to light considerable differences in the definitions and groupings of the tests, as well as in the (maximum) scores of every assessed element.

The test for I2 in FAIR-Enough is not implemented in F-UJI, whereas tests for I3, R1, R1.3 and R1.4, which are present in F-UJI, are not implemented in FAIR-Enough. FAIR-Enough

⁸¹ A2: because it concerns data that is deleted; I2: because the principle says that vocabularies should follow the FAIR principles - this principle suffers from recursion; R1.3 because it is impossible to check in how far data use domain-relevant standards: there is an endless amount of these, applied at different levels of granularity and completeness.

differs in another respect from F-UJI in that it provides optional bonus points for a number of tests: F2 (maximum of 2 bonus points), F3 (1), I1 (1), R1.1 (1). Our calculation demonstrated that bonus points are usually earned if a resource scores high on a certain criterion, hence they mainly result in larger differences in FAIRness between resources with low and high scores.

Using the maturity scores of F-UJI or the bonus points of FAIR-Enough did not significantly alter the patterns of the comparisons we will present below. To reduce complexity, we decided therefore not to use these additional possibilities in this report.

The F-UJI tool has the option to carry out the assessments with or without Content Negotiation based on the DOI URL to retrieve DataCite JSON metadata. If this option is not used, F-UJI uses the information it finds on the landing page URL to which the identifier refers. In some repositories, however, richer metadata is available on other pages, which F-UJI cannot “see”. The difference appeared to be substantial, as the landing page in several repositories does not provide sufficient information about a resource.

Alternative visualisation of comparison results

A scattergram of the total percentage FAIR scores⁸² according to both methods displays the following pattern (Figure 144). Each dot in the graph represents a dataset in a repository. The numbers provide a legend to the resources and repositories (see Figure 115 in the main text).

⁸² Total percentage FAIR scores are calculated as the sum of scores on all FAIR criteria according to the assessment divided by the summed maximum possible scores on all criteria.

Figure 144. Scatterplot of total FAIR scores (expressed as % of maximum possible score) according to F-UJI and FAIR-Enough

In order to compare both methods, we standardised the scores to a scale of 0-100%. The first thing that catches the eye is that on average FAIR-Enough provides higher percentage-scores than F-UJI, as most values are below the diagonal from (0, 0) to (100, 100%). There are only 5 datasets that receive a lower FAIR-Enough than F-UJI score.

Secondly, because the dots are rather scattered, one can see that the relationship between the scores according to both methods, albeit positive, is far from linear. If there was a perfectly linear relationship, all dots would be on a straight, upward sloping line. The correlation coefficient is 0.63, meaning that about 40% of the variance in the one method is the same as in the other one. In this context this is rather low: it means that for 60% both methods measure different things.

Overview of assessed repositories and resources in the tool comparison

The comparison of F-UJI and FAIR-Enough, described in Section 5.4, was carried out on the following sample of datasets. The overview of repositories is identical to that in Annex 9.

Nr	re3data ID	Repository name	Short name	Repository URL	Resource PID used in §4.7	Certificate	Domain				Country	EU Area
							SSH	LS	NS	ES		
1	r3d100010661	Flanders Institute Marine	VLIZ	http://www.vliz.be/en	https://doi.org/10.15468/5tb6ze	WDS	No	No	Yes	No	BEL	NW
2	r3d100011805	Digital Repository of Ireland	DRI	https://repository.dri.ie	https://doi.org/10.7486/DRI.vq28c740x-3	CTS	Yes	No	Yes	No	IRL	NW
3	r3d100012538	DataverseNO	DataverseNO	https://dataverse.no/	https://doi.org/10.18710/0257WR	CTS	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	NOR	NW
4					https://doi.org/10.18710/EBH77W							
5	r3d100000006	Archaeology Service Data	ADS	https://archaeologydataservice.ac.uk/	https://doi.org/10.5284/1029430	CTS	Yes	No	No	No	GBR	NW
6	r3d100010120	UK Polar Data Centre	UK PDC	https://www.bas.ac.uk/data/uk-pdc/	https://doi.org/10.5285/b5ffac8a-9846-4f86-9a71-3ce992a18148	CTS	No	Yes	Yes	No	GBR	NW
7	r3d100010134	PANGAEA	PANGAEA	https://www.pangaea.de/	https://doi.org/10.1594/PANGAEA.510729	CTS	No	Yes	Yes	No	DEU	NW

Nr	re3data ID	Repository name	Short name	Repository URL	Resource PID used in §4.7	Certificate	Domain				Country	EU Area
							SSH	LS	NS	ES		
8					https://doi.org/10.1594/PAN/GAEA.869618							
9	r3d100010146	Swedish National Data Service	SND	https://snd.gu.se/en	https://doi.org/10.5878/wd8j-2c36	CTS	Yes	Yes	No	No	SWE	NW
10	r3d100010214	Data Archiving and Networked Services EASY	DANS-EASY	https://easy.dans.knaw.nl/ui/home	https://doi.org/10.17026/dans-xh4-29fb	CTS	Yes	Yes	Yes	No	NLD	NW
11	r3d100010215	UK Data Archive	UKDA	https://www.data-archive.ac.uk/	http://doi.org/10.5255/UKDA-SN-853992	CTS	Yes	No	No	No	GBR	NW
12	r3d100010216	4TU.ResearchData	4TU	https://data.4tu.nl/info/en/	https://doi.org/10.4121/uuid:bbdf6137-18bd-4973-b917-748528cd6637	DSA	No	Yes	Yes	No	NLD	NW
13	r3d100010251	GESIS Search	GESIS	https://search.gesis.org/	https://doi.org/10.4232/1.13149		Yes	No	No	No	DEU ITA	NW
14	r3d100010469	Movebank Data Repository	Movebank	https://www.datarepository.movebank.org/	http://dx.doi.org/10.5441/001/1.8ms7mm80/2		No	Yes	No	No	DEU	NW
15	r3d100010483	Austrian Social Science Data Archive	AUSSDA	https://data.aussda.at/	https://doi.org/10.11587/W8NEVE	CTS	Yes	No	No	No	AUT	NW

Nr	re3data ID	Repository name	Short name	Repository URL	Resource PID used in §4.7	Certificate	Domain				Country	EU Area
							SSH	LS	NS	ES		
16	r3d100010497	Irish Social Science Data Archive	ISSDA	http://www.ucd.ie/issda/	https://www.ucd.ie/issda/data/irishsportsmonitor/ism2019/	CTS	Yes	No	No	No	IRL	NW
17	r3d100010620	University of Cambridge Repository	Apollo	https://www.repository.cam.ac.uk/	https://www.repository.cam.ac.uk/handle/1810/250343		Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	GBR	NW
18	r3d100011076	Institutional repository of the Spanish National Research Council	DIGITAL.CSIC	https://digital.csic.es/?locale=en	http://dx.doi.org/10.20350/digitalCSIC/222	DSA	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	ESP	SW
19	r3d100011132	Social Scientific Research Documentation Centre Repository	RDC (KDK)	http://openarchive.tk.mta.hu/	http://dx.doi.org/10.17203/KDK345		Yes	Yes	No	No	HUN	Central
20	r3d100011345	DARIAH-DE Repository	DARIAH-DE	https://de.dariah.eu/repository	https://dx.doi.org/10.20375/0000-000B-D553-7		Yes	No	No	No	DEU	NW
21	r3d100012190	ZBW Journal Data Archive	ZBW	http://journaldata.zbw.eu	http://dx.doi.org/10.15456/jbnst.2021257.143925		Yes	No	No	No	DEU	NW
22	r3d100012203	Integrated Carbon System Observation Portal	ICOS	https://www.icos-cp.eu/node/1	https://hdl.handle.net/11676/yVN6HhNF4m5Z9BNqWVm0T4yA		No	No	Yes	No	EEC SWE	NW

Nr	re3data ID	Repository name	Short name	Repository URL	Resource PID used in §4.7	Certificate	Domain				Country	EU Area
							SSH	LS	NS	ES		
											NLD	
23	r3d100012330	Research Repository	Data RADAR	https://www.radar-service.eu/en	https://dx.doi.org/10.22000/53		Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	DEU	NW
24	r3d100012673	Data INRAE	INRAE	https://data.inrae.fr/	https://doi.org/10.15454/V91SS2		No	Yes	Yes	No	AAA FRA	NW
25	r3d100012965	SISMER Oceanographic Data	IFREMER-SISMER	http://data.ifremer.fr/	https://doi.org/10.17600/15004600	CTS	No	No	Yes	No	FRA	NW
26	r3d100013084	SURF Data Repository	SURF	https://repository.surfsara.nl	https://doi.org/10.25606/SURF.578c6039-81f76e8f		Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	NLD	NW
27	r3d100013565	TU Graz Repository	TU Graz	https://repository.tugraz.at/	https://doi.org/10.3217/datacite.ijs3x-4f133		No	No	Yes	No	AUT	NW
28	r3d100010468	Zenodo	Zenodo	https://zenodo.org/	https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.1163707		Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	EEC	Central
29	r3d100011868	Mendeley Data	Mendeley	https://data.mendeley.com/	https://doi.org/10.17632/9xyp88y6n5.1	CTS	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	NLD	NW

Nr	re3data ID	Repository name	Short name	Repository URL	Resource PID used in §4.7	Certificate	Domain				Country	EU Area
							SSH	LS	NS	ES		
30	r3d100010487	Slovenian Social Science Data Archives	ADP	https://www.adp.fdv.uni-lj.si/eng/	https://doi.org/10.17898/ADP_NOVTEH20_V1	CTS	Yes	No	No	No	SVN	SE
31	r3d100013287	Institutional Repository of Cyprus University of Technology	Ktisis	https://ktisis.cut.ac.cy	http://ktisis.cut.ac.cy/handle/10488/13361		Yes	Yes	No	Yes	CYP	SE
32	r3d100013510	Digital Academic Archives and Repositories	DABAR	https://dabar.srce.hr/en	https://urn.nsk.hr/urn:nbn:hr:195:416494		Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	HRV	SE
33	r3d100013438	Rovira i Virgili Institutional Repository	URV	http://repositori.urv.cat/en/	https://doi.org/10.1016/j.scitotenv.2019.02.128		Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	ESP	SW

Definitions and scores of FAIR-Enough and F-UJI assessment criteria

FAIR-Enough assessment criteria					F-UJI assessment criteria				
Identifier	Assessment name	Assessment method	Max score	Max bonus	Assessment Identifier	Assessment name	Assessment method	Max score	
F1	Resource identifier is unique and	Check if the identifier of the resource is unique (HTTP) and persistent (some HTTP	2	0	FsF-F1-01D	Data is assigned a globally unique	Check if the identifier is specified based on a globally	1	

FAIR-Enough assessment criteria					F-UJI assessment criteria			
Identifier	Assessment name	Assessment method	Max score	Max bonus	Assessment Identifier	Assessment name	Assessment method	Max score
	persistent	domains)				identifier.	unique identifier scheme.	
					FsF-F1-02D	Data is assigned a persistent identifier.	Check if the data identifier specified is based on a commonly accepted persistent identifier scheme, and whether it resolves to a landing page with metadata containing further information on how to access the data object.	1
F2	Metadata is machine-readable	This assessment will try to extract as much metadata it can from the resource URI, and put it in eval.data It can be useful to put it at the start of your collection, and then search for properties in the metadata extracted. Search for structured metadata at the resource URI. Use HTTP requests with content-negotiation (RDF, JSON-LD, JSON), and extract metadata from the HTML landing page using extract	1	2	FsF-F2-01M	Metadata includes descriptive core elements (creator, title, data identifier, publisher, publication date, summary and keywords) to support data findability.	Use the data identifier to access its metadata document. Parse or retrieve core metadata, combine the results and then verify the presence/absence of the core elements in the metadata.	2

FAIR-Enough assessment criteria					F-UJI assessment criteria			
Identifier	Assessment name	Assessment method	Max score	Max bonus	Assessment Identifier	Assessment name	Assessment method	Max score
F3	Resource Identifier is in Metadata	Whether the metadata document contains the globally unique and persistent identifier for the digital resource. Parse the metadata to search for the given digital resource GUID. If found, retrieve informations about this resource (title, description, date created, etc)	1	1	FsF-F3-01M	Metadata includes the identifier of the data it describes.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Use the data identifier to access its metadata document. • Verify if the data identifier provided is the same as the identifier specified in the metadata. • Check if the identifier (link) to access data content is included in the metadata and test if the content identifier is active. 	1
F4	The resource is indexed in a searchable resource	Search for existing metadata about the resource URI in data repositories, such as DataCite, RE3data.	1	0	FsF-F4-01M	Metadata is offered in such a way that it can be retrieved by machines.	<p>The following methods may be applied to determine if metadata of the data is accessible programmatically:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Check if the metadata provision endpoint returns metadata records based on a request using the data identifier • Check if search engine friendly structured data is 	2

FAIR-Enough assessment criteria					F-UJI assessment criteria			
Identifier	Assessment name	Assessment method	Max score	Max bonus	Assessment Identifier	Assessment name	Assessment method	Max score
							embedded in the data landing page with a proper resource type, e.g. schema.org representation of type 'Dataset' or 'Collection'.	
A1	Check Access Protocol	The access protocol and authorization (if content restricted). For the protocol, do an HTTP get on the URL to see if it returns a valid document. Find information about authorization in metadata	2	0	FsF-A1-01M	Metadata contains access level and access conditions of the data.	Use the data identifier to access its metadata document. Check the presence/absence of data access level through metadata element(s). If it is embargoed data, check if the embargo end date is specified. If it is restricted data, check if the data access conditions are specified.	1

FAIR-Enough assessment criteria					F-UJI assessment criteria			
Identifier	Assessment name	Assessment method	Max score	Max bonus	Assessment Identifier	Assessment name	Assessment method	Max score
					FsF-A1-02M	Metadata is accessible through a standardized communication protocol	Use the data identifier to access its landing page (metadata document). Verify the application protocol used to serve the page based on the scheme part of the IRI. In case external metadata is linked to the landing page by typed links, use the data identifier specified in the typed link.	1
					FsF-A1-03D	Data is accessible through a standardized communication protocol	Check the application protocol of the data identifier based on the scheme part of the given IRI. In case external metadata is linked to the landing page by typed links, use the data identifier specified in the typed link.	1

FAIR-Enough assessment criteria					F-UJI assessment criteria			
Identifier	Assessment name	Assessment method	Max score	Max bonus	Assessment Identifier	Assessment name	Assessment method	Max score
I1	Metadata uses a formal knowledge representation language	Check if the resource metadata found can be parsed as RDF	1	1	FsF-I1-01M	Metadata is represented using a formal knowledge representation language.	Machine-actionable representation (e.g. RDF) of the metadata may be retrieved as follows: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • If content negotiation is supported, use the identifier to perform a request, e.g. an RDF-based document. • Use the 'typed links' given in the HTML header section of the landing page to access the RDF-based metadata of the data. • Query the SPARQL endpoint using the identifier (or optionally title) of the data. Perform a full text-search within the SPARQL query if it is supported. 	2

FAIR-Enough assessment criteria					F-UJI assessment criteria			
Identifier	Assessment name	Assessment method	Max score	Max bonus	Assessment Identifier	Assessment name	Assessment method	Max score
					FsF-I1-02M	Metadata uses semantic resources.	<p>This assessment is the continuation of the assessment FsF-I1-01M, but focuses on the metadata contents:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Extract namespaces declared from the machine-actionable metadata document. Filter out common namespaces (e.g. rdf, rdfs, xsd, owl). • Compare the remaining namespaces with entries from existing (known) ontology registries. 	1
I2	Metadata uses FAIR Vocabularies	The metadata values and qualified relations should themselves be FAIR, for example, terms from open, community-accepted vocabularies published in an appropriate knowledge-exchange format. Resolve IRIs, check FAIRness of the returned	1	0	FsF-I1-02M	Not implemented		

FAIR-Enough assessment criteria					F-UJI assessment criteria			
Identifier	Assessment name	Assessment method	Max score	Max bonus	Assessment Identifier	Assessment name	Assessment method	Max score
		documents.						
I3	Not Implemented				FsF-13-01M	Metadata includes links between the data and its related entities.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Use the data identifier to access its metadata record. • Check the metadata elements which indicate the relationship between data and related entities. • Test if the URLs of the related entities are active (not broken links). 	1

FAIR-Enough assessment criteria					F-UJI assessment criteria			
Identifier	Assessment name	Assessment method	Max score	Max bonus	Assessment Identifier	Assessment name	Assessment method	Max score
R1	Not Implemented				FsF-R1-01MD	Metadata specifies the content of the data.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Use the data identifier to access its metadata document. Verify the presence/absence of elements representing data content descriptions in the metadata document. • Use the data access URL specified in the metadata to retrieve the actual data. Check if ontology terms are used to describe data content. • Compare the content descriptions found with actual data properties. 	4
R1.1	Check accessible Usage License	The existence of a license document, for BOTH (independently) the data and its associated metadata, and the ability to retrieve those documents Resolve the licenses IRI	1	1	FsF-R1.1-01M	Metadata includes license information under which data can be reused.	Use the data identifier to access its metadata document. Verify the presence/absence of metadata element(s) corresponding to license information of the data. The license information may be	2

FAIR-Enough assessment criteria					F-UJI assessment criteria			
Identifier	Assessment name	Assessment method	Max score	Max bonus	Assessment Identifier	Assessment name	Assessment method	Max score
							used to request additional information from an external license registry.	
R1.2	Detailed Provenance (Not yet implemented)	<p>That there is provenance information associated with the data, covering at least two primary types of provenance information:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Who/What/When produced the data (i.e. for citation) • Why/How was the data produced (i.e. to understand context and relevance of the data) 	1	0	FsF-R1.2-01M	Metadata includes provenance information about data creation or generation.	Use the data identifier to access its metadata record. Verify the presence/absence of metadata element(s) corresponding to the minimum data provenance properties.	2

FAIR-Enough assessment criteria					F-UJI assessment criteria			
Identifier	Assessment name	Assessment method	Max score	Max bonus	Assessment Identifier	Assessment name	Assessment method	Max score
R1.3	Not Implemented				FsF-R1.3-01M	Metadata follows a standard recommended by the target research community of the data.	Gather all metadata standards used by a data repository. Filter out domain-agnostic standards from the list. Cross check the remaining standards with an external metadata registry. Request metadata of the data identifier specified based on one of the remaining standards as a test case.	1
R1.4	Not Implemented				FsF-R1.3-02D	Data is available in a file format recommended by the target research community.	Extract file format information (mime-type) from the metadata based on elements. Check if the format is an open and long-term file format.	1

Comparison per FAIR principle

In addition to the substantial differences between the total percentage FAIR scores according to F-UJI and FAIR-Enough, presented in the main text, this annex turns to the scores for the FAIR main principles - F, A, I, and R - in order to see whether we can pinpoint from where the differences are stemming, and how they impact the total FAIR scores (Fig.).

Figure 145. FAIR scores of the individual FAIR criteria according to FAIR-Enough and F-UJI

Note: bubble sizes are relative to the number of resources/repositories with the corresponding assessment scores.

The correspondence between the two assessment methods is even worse than appeared from the total percentage scores in Annex 10, with the exception of the Findable criterion:

Findable: The pattern of the correspondence between the F-UJI and FAIR-Enough scores is roughly similar to the one for the total percentage scores, and the correlation coefficient is only marginally lower ($R = 0.61$). As the ranges of the values are smaller, more repositories/resources occupy the same position in the graph, for example, there are 10 datasets that score 5 for Findable on the FAIR-Enough assessment and 6 on the F-UJI assessment.

Accessible: Both methods only test the A1 criterion, which consists of three sub-criteria in the case of F-UJI. Hence we see a greater variation in the scores for F-UJI (ranging between 0 and 3) than for FAIR-Enough, which either scores 0 or 1. Only two resources score a 0 for FAIR-Enough, although they receive either a 1 or 1.5 points from F-UJI. One resource scores a 0 for F-UJI, but it still passes the FAIR-Enough test. Twenty resources receive a 1 or 1.5 score for F-UJI, and 1 for FAIR-Enough. The most

remarkable pattern in the bubble chart is that all but two (31) resources which pass the FAIR-Enough test cover the full range of scores from 0 to 3 in the F-UJI assessment.

Interoperable: The basic pattern of this chart is comparable to the previous one. FAIR-Enough tests criteria I1 and I2, F-UJI tests I1 (in two parts) and I3. The FAIR-Enough scores are either 0 (6 resources fail) or 2 (27 resources pass). For F-UJI the scores vary between 0 and 4. FAIR-Enough and F-UJI agree that 4 resources fail completely on interoperability (score 0 on both assessment methods). For 3 resources they disagree whether it is a (partial) pass or fail. The 27 resources that pass FAIR-Enough receive F-UJI scores across the full range from 0 to 4, with the majority (20 resources) receiving 2 or 3 points.

Reusable: In this plot the dichotomous pattern of the previous two graphs is repeated, albeit in a different form. FAIR-Enough only implements element R1.1, F-UJI assesses all five elements of R. As a result, the R scores for FAIR-Enough are again binary (either 0 or 1), but this time only 13 resources pass the test. For the 20 fails, we observe the full range of scores handed out by F-UJI, from 0 (which occurs only once) to 7 (out of a theoretical maximum of 10), where the majority is in the middle (15 resources receive a score between 2 and 4). The resources passing the FAIR-Enough test receive relatively high F-UJI scores: from 4 to 7.

Conclusions about the comparison of F-UJI and FAIR-Enough

There are substantial differences in the FAIR assessment methods and their outcomes between FAIR-Enough and F-UJI. This is true both at the level of the total percentage FAIR, and at the level of the individual F, A, I, and R main principles. The differences can be summarised as follows:

- Selection of FAIR criteria: from the comparison in Annex for Definition and scores of Fair-Enough and F-UJI assessment criteria, it appears that there are differences in the selection of the FAIR elements to be assessed.
- Operationalisation of FAIR principles (in Annex for Comparison per FAIR principle) and FAIR main principles: the descriptions of the criteria in Annex for definitions and scores differ in detail. The comparison at the level of the FAIR principles reveals that even where the same criteria were assessed, the outcomes were substantially different.
- Implementation of assessment criteria: it is difficult to say whether the differences in outcomes of the assessments are caused by the differences in operationalisation or in implementation (or both). To establish what is the case would require a close comparison of the computer codes of both tools. This should be possible, as the source code of both tools in python is openly available on Github⁸³.
- F-UJI makes DataCite Content Negotiation optional, FAIR-Enough has optional “bonus points”. F-UJI also provides “maturity scores” (which are however not fundamentally different from the “normal” FAIR scores). Content Negotiation appeared to substantially improve F-UJI’s capability to find the needed information for its assessments, as was argued before. Maturity scores and bonus points appeared not to influence the outcome of our conclusions.
- Scoring method: the maximum scores per test are not always the same. In practice, it appears that FAIR-Enough results boil down to a pass (score 1) or fail (score 0) of the test per FAIR criterion, at least for the 33 resources in our selection for the A, I and R, whereas F-UJI provides more gradual scales of scores.
- Weighting of scores: because of the previous point, also the composite scores result in different maximum totals, and in different ways in which they contribute to percentage scores.

83 In the F-UJI code, all FAIR tests are in one python script of 1124 lines (latest version 28/12/2021: https://github.com/pangaea-data-publisher/fuji/blob/master/fuji_server/controllers/fair_check.py).

The FAIR-Enough tests are in separate scripts, one per test (version 26/11/2021: <https://github.com/MaastrichtU-IDS/fair-enough/tree/main/backend/app/assessments>).

Mark Wilkinson, co-chair of the EOSC Task Force on FAIR Metrics and Data Quality⁸⁴, concluded in the “Apples to Apples” workshop⁸⁵ (personal communication), that one reason why FAIR evaluation systems result in such dissimilar results is because they differ in the way they gather metadata about digital objects. Moreover, “data infrastructure providers and repository hosts have disparate ways to provide metadata” (Wilkinson, 2022). At the same occasion, Herbert van de Sompel proposed that FAIR Signposting⁸⁶ could alleviate these differences, as signposting is an approach that scholarly portals and data providers can use to indicate or “tell” machines where certain information, including the metadata needed in FAIR assessments, can be found (Van de Sompel, 2022 and COAR (nd)).

On the basis of the conclusions above, the following recommendations for the EOSC Task Force “FAIR metrics and Data Quality” emerge:

1. It seems useful if the teams behind different assessment methods such as F-UJI and FAIR-Enough compare and discuss their approaches, choices and implementations in more detail. Different philosophies, aims and use cases appear to have serious consequences for FAIR measurements.
2. For all assessment methods it seems useful to implement (optional) Content Negotiation and FAIR Signposting, so that the findability of the metadata needed for assessments improves. Of course, this effect will be maximised if repositories also implement these techniques.
3. A close inspection of the codes of different tools may shed more light on the causes of the differences. If these are deliberate and a consequence of different assumptions or methodologies, so be it: for instance, the FAIR-Enough team explicitly favours different tests for different communities. But the communities should first of all know why different tests of the same criterion lead to different results. Only when the assessment purposes and characteristics are clearly specified and understood, informed choices can be made about which tests to use.
4. Different assessment methods should look at the operationalisations and implementations of alternative methods. For instance, we recommend the F-UJI team to consider implementing FAIR-Enough criterion I2; and we recommend the FAIR-Enough team to consider implementing F-UJI’s I3, R1, R1.3 and R1.4.
5. It would be useful to extend this fairly detailed comparison of two methods with other ones, both manual and automated. In this phase, it is probably inevitable that different assessment methods coexist, but ultimately we would like to have solid ground in order

84 <https://www.eosc.eu/advisory-groups/fair-metrics-and-data-quality>

85 Held online, 7 and 10 February 2022.

86 For more information, see: <https://signposting.org/>

to establish which characteristics make a digital research resource FAIR (or to what degree). After all, what is the point of employing beautiful principles, if the practice can not be established more or less unequivocally?

ANNEX 2. CASE STUDY: IOCHEM-BD

Description:

The ioChem-BD is a software platform developed by the Institute of Chemical Research of Catalonia (ICIQ) and the University of Rovira i Virgili with the purpose to manage large volumes of quantum chemistry results from a diverse group of already common simulation packages. The platform provides services related to data creation and curation, publishing, storage, indexing data and search engine services. The platform provides tools for researchers to validate, enrich, publish and share information. The main node of the network runs the Find service module¹, which acts as the central server and is fed by any new data published in the repositories. The Find module provides a fast chemical-aware search engine open public service and is hosted at the Barcelona Supercomputer Center (BSC). Also, the first public-access node is provided by BSC.

The ioChem-BD has been endorsed by the American Chemical Society (ACS) and Nature Scientific Data journals as a FAIR repository solution.

Summary of survey results:

The ioChem-BD is a domain-specific public research data repository covering the area of natural sciences, more specifically the sub-discipline of chemical sciences with related data hosted both in EU and non-EU countries.

The ioChem-BD provides the following services: data storage, cataloguing and searching via metadata, content-based searching and creation of persistent identifiers though the creation of persistent identifiers (PIDs) (e.g. DOI, ORCHID ID) is an outsourced service. The repository is structurally funded and offer two levels of data curation: basic (brief checking, addition of basic metadata or documents) and enhanced (conversion to new formats, enhancement of documentation). The repository uses data standards, metadata, persistent identifiers (PIDs) and license defining data accessibility.

Concerning alignment with specific data policies, the ioChem-BD implements personal data protection policies (e.g. GDPR) and general rules on responsible management of research data in line with the FAIR principles.

The rate of growth of the repository in terms of research data volume ranges between 50% and up to 100%. The approximate number of items available for users of the repository is close to 250000.

In terms of costs, the approximate yearly costs are 50000, covering staff costs (75%) and costs of maintenance and development of systems (25%).

The repository is using Creative Commons as a basis for standard terms, in specific CC BY (attribution to the author required) and CC BY-NC-ND (attribution to the author required, only for non-commercial use, no derivatives for adaptations allowed).

Key findings from interview:

The ioChem-BD repository was setup in Barcelona (Spain) in 2015. It is a specific software to manage data and facilitate researchers to use services. The repository counts with up to 1500 users in own institutions and other hundreds of users in many other institutions/nodes (Barcelona Supercomputing centre node 300 users from 50 countries). All nodes are sync with central nodes hosted by Barcelona supercomputing centre. Spain setup a big storage infrastructure hosted by BSC.

FAIR principles application started bottom up, then data sharing became a strong movement also in Spain. Since a couple of years ago the Government of Spain started taking care of the matter when EU calls started requiring DMPs, alignment to open access in nationally funded calls. This was translated into recommendations about data sharing and open science practices at national level. There is also support, in terms of infrastructures, with setup of dedicated hardware including grants for new technicians to manage the data. Some support is foreseen in terms of human resources in the form of a national programme to train Support technicians for research centres.

There are still gaps in terms of data stewardship: ioChem-BD has a person (a graduate in computer sciences and biotechnologies) holding the role of data steward and supporting researchers in data management. Getting the appropriate data format is usually challenging for researchers so, in many cases, there is the need to convert and curate data at the level of the repository, but it's important to facilitate the work of researchers in improving the level of data curation before depositing.

There were no common data management plans and data management practices before FAIR principles became paramount in research communities. Datasets are stored in ioChem-BD repository permanently because many datasets are linked to scientific papers, and DOIs are included in the datasets. there is also consistent use of persistent identifiers for datasets deposited.

An important barrier is to have users deposit to the repository, as there is still some reluctance in sharing data, particularly when there is familiarity with the depositing practices. A key role for the repository is creating tools facilitating its use by the researchers.

In terms of funding, there has been some earmarked funding from the government, via public calls focused on data aspects. This allowed institutions to hire technical people supporting researchers.

In Spain there are no specific incentives for data management or guidelines to provide support in this area, but only strong recommendations hinting at well-developed DMPs and good data practices as key requirements to obtain project funding. Catalunya created data

management tutorial (40 pages manual), providing general guidance to researchers. This is the first version of the documents, yet it still needs further development to spread culture about data management. Raising awareness so later researchers are better able to express their detailed needs.

Data creators are already producing computational datasets in this specific field of science, so the process is easier to be made FAIR along the way. Special care needed in introduction of additional metadata putting data in context.

Many publishers are accepting their way of working (like use of persisting identifiers rather than annexing pdf papers referenced in a scientific article). Now publishers recommend use of specific repositories. Users realizing that the repository works, run smooth, easily and in a robust way. Relevance of the institution supporting the repository. For example, the fact that the repository is hosted at the Barcelona Supercomputing Centre suggests reliability of the repository in the long term in the view of users. Researchers perceiving that data is there to stay and managed by competent people in a solid institution.

Overall, there is a need for more support in data curation, stewardship, software and costs of infrastructures are increasing with the increase in size of the repository. More investment in data stewardship activities is needed.

Assessment

The ioChem-BD repository serves its users with good set of services and tools to improve data FAIRness and is structurally organised to provide a reliable support to the research community of reference. The character of the scientific domain under focus, computational chemistry, reduces the number of challenges faced for example by repositories active in humanities, as datasets are already produced in a computational format. There is appropriate alignment and commitment to FAIR principles, also demonstrated by the recruitment of a person with dual background in biochemistry and IT for the role of data steward, as well as the awareness of more investment needed to accompany researchers in curate data at an earlier stage ahead of depositing.

ANNEX 3. CASE STUDY: SURF

Description:

The SURF Data Repository has been established to ensure long-term data preservation and provide an online data publication platform service to share and publish research data and it has been operational in the last 5 year. The focus of the repository is in helping researcher to publish research data and to preserve published datasets for the long-term, thus complying with the requirements of publishers, financiers and (Dutch) science organisations regarding data publication. Researchers have complete freedom to decide on the structure, the metadata schemas, the designated community, and access levels of the

published data, yet, the repository provides guidelines on acceptable and preferred data formats.

The SURF repository provides access to mostly open access data which can be found and downloaded by anyone interested. Publication of datasets, requires the previous registration of an account. The repository is directly connected to the Data Archive service. All data in the data repository will eventually end up in the data archive for long-term storage and preservation. The SURF Data Repository is specifically designed for the publication of large datasets: research data that is several TBs to PBs in size and it is tape-aware, this means that data can automatically be put offline when it is not required for a certain amount of time.

Summary of survey results :

SURF manages a public research data repository, but it also holds aspects of a commercial repository since one of the main sources of funding is through data depositing fees (i.e. in the form of annual contracts with depositing institutions or per-deposit fees) and partly also from projects. The repository has adequate funding to address technical data and metadata quality managed through a clear system of governance and it offer a level of basic data curation. The main categories of cost are staff costs, maintenance and development of systems, preservation and storage, but no breakdown has been provided for these cost categories.

The SURF data repository is domain-agnostic as it supports multiple communities with different policy and metadata requirements. It is open globally though data is stored only in EU countries. The main services offered are data storage, cataloguing and searching via metadata, as well as the creation of persistent identifiers (PIDs). None of these services is outsourced.

The repository guarantees the integrity and authenticity of the data with a minimum storage time of 5 years foreseen and archiving takes place according to defined workflows from ingest to dissemination. The approximate volume of data stored is currently between 100 TeraByte and 1 Petabyte.

The repository is certified with main cybersecurity standards, and it has a continuity plan to ensure ongoing (mid- and long-term) access to and preservation of its holdings. Some conditions are set for data deposited and they are related to use of data standard, use of metadata, assignment of a persistent identifiers (PIDs) (e.g. DOI, ORCHID ID) and the use of a licence defining data accessibility.

The repository accepts data and metadata based on defined criteria to ensure relevance and understandability for data users and it has an explicit mission to provide access to and preserve data in its domain. Metadata are machine- actionable and standardized and users are enabled to discover data and refer to them in a persistent way through proper citation.

The technical infrastructure of the repository provides for protection of the facility and its data, products, services, and users, with services and holdings visible to aggregators services.

The repository is compliant with international organisations' policies such as GDPR and security related policies.

Key findings from interview:

The SURF data repository has a multidisciplinary scope and the key objective of storing and sharing large datasets 1TB and over.

Smaller repositories cover data up to 10GB for publishing, whereas SURF covers very larger datasets (eg. from research infrastructures such as Lofar and Astron) from any scientific community.

Data services are currently offered to researchers affiliated to the work of SURF but the repository is increasingly being opened to European researchers.

The focus is on very large datasets for long-term data preservation with tape used for this purpose. There are no explicit rules for SURF to align in terms of FAIRness but SURF is committed to providing services and support aimed at making data FAIRer in alignment to national and European policies. SURF also collaborate closely with the *Dutch* Research Council (*NWO*) and is very committed to making research data FAIR.

There wasn't a difficult transition toward alignment to FAIR principles, but there have been several iterations and developments in the last couple of years, with current versions of data models more focused on FAIR data. Extensive tooling is now available to support different data schemas and to ensure machine readable data.

No proactive initiative is carried out by SURF to reach out to researchers and encourage them on depositing data. The repository operated on demand. The main challenge is having good quality metadata. Normally, it takes long time for researchers to prepare the data and to go from the idea of publishing/sharing data to actual publication.

There isn't structural funding allocated to help improving quality of data before depositing. More funding should be earmarked to helping researchers in making their data ready for publication as it is impossible for a multidisciplinary repository to create metadata for different communities of researchers. SURF offer training to researchers on general data management (even when they are not going to deposit with SURF) as well as specific trainings, offered on demand, on publishing via the SURF data repository.

There is no specific incentive for data managers and researchers about complying to FAIR data, however, NWO is invested in making research more open so DMPs are required to obtain funding for research projects. The level of awareness of the importance of open science and FAIR data is increasing in the country and the users served by SURF. Young researchers are getting keener to share data and trying to put FAIR principles in practice. But there is still some lack of knowledge on how to implement FAIR principles effectively.

One of the advantages of publishing large datasets is that there is always a SURF advisor involved in the data publication process. So, there is constant dialogue with the researchers wishing to publish and exchanges on the quality of the metadata. There is a limited set of metadata that people must fill but is not enough to ensure appropriate findability.

Communities can and are encouraged to publish sets of metadata for their own discipline and the SURF data repository enable users to create communities that can set their own metadata schemas (eg LOFAR that this and their metadata are reusable). Larger communities are pouring a lot of effort into standardising metadata.

Recently SURF has undergone a FAIR assessment (via F-UJI tool): it scored well in findability and accessibility. The repository has more control over these two aspects, particularly a level of control over the quality of the metadata and in exposing it.

Interoperability and Reusability are more challenging aspects for a repository, as these elements are more related to the creation of the datasets. These aspects are closer to the research communities and had better be handled within them. Yet, for a repository, the accessibility aspect is the one where the repository can do the most for the research communities.

From the perspective of researchers, a repository is a service they must trust for them to deposit data. They must be aware that their data is safe and secure. Data safety (eg ISO norms for data protection) is important as well as adherence to FAIR principles. The reputation for the hosting institution and structural funding in the long term is critical for a repository to be considered trustworthy.

There are so many elements to be aware of and as a researcher is hard to understand if a repository is trustworthy, then the standardizing would help understand if the repository can be trusted and give it the control of own data.

Assessment :

SURF Data Repository has integrated FAIR practices in its daily operations and is aware of the need to improve in the areas closer to its responsibilities to make data deposited FAIRer. The set of services and tools meet demands and allow the repositories to effectively achieve their objectives, of storing, sharing, and preserving very large datasets from different disciplines. The management of SURF Data Repository is aware that

improvements are possible, though the good scores in the various areas assessed with the F-UJI tool, but also of the existing gaps that must be filled with support to data curation and improvement of data quality, in a FAIR perspective, in phases of the research work closer to the researchers and preceding the deposit of data.

ANNEX 4. CASE STUDY: ARCHAEOLOGICAL MAP OF THE CZECH REPUBLIC

Description:

The Archaeological Information System of the Czech Republic (AIS CR) is a platform which integrates digital objects on Czech archaeology. Its main component is the Archaeological Map of the Czech Republic (AMCR) information system which is hosted by the Institutes of Archaeology of the Czech Academy of Sciences (CAS) in Prague and Brno.

The institutes are mandated by the Czech law of the collection, management and presentation of data on archaeological research in the territory of the Czech Republic and a key task is the processing of databases for Moravia and Czech Silesia and their consolidation with existing databases on the Czech territory. The data stored in the AMCR describe tens of thousands of archaeological investigations and their concrete findings. They include information about research leaders, when the research was conducted, its location, what findings, and from what period the research was found.

A special type of record is data on archaeological sites, detected by both surface and remote sensing. Most records are linked to digital document storage and bibliographic catalogue.

The Digital Archive of the AMCR is also part of the AIS CR This Digital Archive is a web application designed for viewing digital documents stored in the AMCR and it replaces the previous applications for the data archives of the Institute of Archaeology Prague and the Institute of Archaeology Brno. The interface is fully interconnected with the AMCR and makes accessible archived documents, including associated descriptive and spatial data. It provides access to more than hundred thousand digital documents. Following completion of the ongoing migration and digitisation process, their number will amount to around half a million records.

Other services offered by the AIS CR are 1) the Archaeological Atlas of the Czech Republic underpinning the publication under the same name while expanding its content in the virtual environment and presenting formation on 106 significant localities to the wider public; 2) the Archaeological Prague (Map of Archaeological Documentation Points) – a portal that aims to make Prague’s archaeological sources available to experts and the general public alike. The portal makes it possible to visit Prague beneath Prague and follow in the footsteps of Prague’s past; 3) Archaeology Online – The portal presents digital

information sources associated with knowledge of the past of the Czech landscape and Czech archaeology. Other key services include the development of public API, making data available in machine readable format and others. ¹ The aim of the portal is to offer users a signpost with data that is frequently hard to access that will provide the user with an orientation in the existing infrastructures, record systems, tools, and portals.

The survey and interview focused on the AMCR and related data repository.

Summary of survey results:

The AMCR is a public research data repository, registered in Czech Republic and hosting data related to the field of humanities with a focus on archaeological data. Data is stored within the EU, and the repository is mainly focused to serve national users, though it is also open to researchers abroad.

The repository offers a good range of services including:

- Data storage,
- Cataloguing and searching via metadata,
- Value added services providing information on the repository,
- Value added services providing information on the stored data records,
- Value added services providing instructions for use and dissemination,
- Value added services helping with compliance towards data reporting standards and/or metadata,
- Policy or license-based access control.

The repository software development is instead outsourced.

The AMCR relies on different funding sources: as for 2022, it is structurally funded as national research infrastructure (for about 50%), from contributions by the host institution (for about 30%), and from projects (20%).

The approximate yearly costs associated with running the data repository are of about 800000€ with a breakdown of 70% in staff costs, 15% for costs of maintenance and development of systems, 5% of costs of preservation and storage and 10% for investments into the e-infrastructure. The volume of research data available via the repository range between 1TB-10TB, with about 100000 files stored in it and an increase in volume of data deposited of more than 250% in the last 3 years.

The AMCR has a continuity plan to ensure ongoing (mid- and long-term) access to and preservation of its holdings and an explicit mission to provide access to and preserve data in its domain, but it holds no certification on cybersecurity aspects. It adopts mechanism(s) to secure ongoing expert guidance and feedback and offers explicit information online about their policies applied to their services.

The conditions set for data deposited include use of data standards, use of metadata, use of licence defining data accessibility, and the declaration of datasets not including personal data.

The AMCR performs data-level curation – enhanced curation, with additional editing of deposited data for accuracy and all the data is preserved for the lifetime of the repository.

Creative commons is the licensing scheme used as a basis for standard terms and conditions for data access, with CC BY-NC (attribution to the author required, only for non-commercial use) as a specific license accepted for the data deposited.

Key findings from interview:

Two people, the manager of the data repository and a senior user belonging to the institute were interviewed.

The data repository has been evolving for long time and the Czech Academy of Sciences (CAS) oversees storing data for the Czech Republic and it has been operating an IT system for archaeological documents and data since the 90s. More recently the archives and processes for data collection and fruition were digitised.

The AMCR was established in 2012 and became operational in 2017. The collection of archaeological data and the operations of the AMCR are directly connected to the agenda set by the government of the Czech Republic concerning the archaeological data of the country. For researchers working on excavations, it is mandatory to deposit data in the AMCR repository. The digital archiving tool is used to access data in the repository.

The main category of users comes from institutions in the country: about 100 institutions working on the data. There are 2500 active registered users, out of which 500 are professional archaeologists. However also unregistered users can view and browse the repository and there are about 80000 unregistered users accessing the overall infrastructure yearly. The AMCR Digital Archive had about 10000 individual users last year with 17% foreign users.

The establishment of the repository was ongoing when the FAIR concept emerged. FAIR principles were used as an advocacy argument by the CAS toward research institutions in Czech Republic to change approach and practices. FAIR was an opportunity to advocate for a change as it provided a good framework in which data managers could work also at international level.

AMCR managers see implementation of data FAIRness as beneficial for users, particularly in the context of collaborative international projects. When the project of the repository started in 2012 there was no vision for the Digital Archive which came later. One very important evolution is the use of standards now used across international teams in the archaeological community. In CZ standardisation was favoured by having one central repository for archaeological data.

The implementation of FAIR data principles didn't generate a disruptive transition from previous operational model of data management, the change was evolutionary. Not really a sudden change in data model but slow yet continuous transition adaptation in workflow, practices, etc. There were some complexities in translating FAIR principles in technical solutions. And it was difficult to match IT competences of data managers with awareness of needs for archaeological data to make them FAIR. There wasn't knowledge on practical means and practices to adopt and implement FAIR practices.

When coming the main barriers/challenges in this transition the main concern is the lack of specific digital/IT competences related to the archaeology field. There are limited resources to get the appropriate knowledgeable people able to manage the transition.

Nevertheless, there is a generation change in archaeology: older researchers are not fully using the infrastructure and sceptical in uploading the data in. In Czech Republic (but it is the same in Germany) for archaeological student there is no education/training module in computer science basics and management of data.

Cataloguing of the artifacts and consistent linking to records in the repository is quite challenging due to the maintenance of two independent registers under two different laws for documentary archives (i.e.: AMCR) and finds (museum recording systems).

There wasn't specific funding earmarked for the repository. As the hosting institution is funded as a large and stable RI there was reasonable funding – mainly from the national horizontal research programmes in Czech Republic - and that was enough to setup and operate the infrastructure. A key issue concerned recruitment as it was very difficult to find candidates with the appropriate skills. There may also be some concerns about sustainability in case funding for this Research Infrastructure is suspended.

In adhering to FAIR principles, data managers at the AMCR had to look to their peers in the international community while also discussing with users to get useful insights for implementation. Currently, there is very low regulation about archaeological data and how they should look like in Czech Republic. So, there were exchanges with the users to negotiate the data model and open licensing. There were key messages to users on benefits to open data and recommendation to promote FAIR data principles. Many people very reluctant to share data and it required a big effort to convince a share of users to FAIRify and open their data.

Compared to the situation up to 3-5 years ago, today people are generally accepting the FAIR principles and increasingly making data open. Yet the effort of FAIRification and data curation is more on the side of the repository, at present. If it were up just to the users, there would be no FAIR. The AMCR can't assess if there were some relevant changes in the researchers' practices concerning FAIR principles. There seems to be a positive trend, but it's the repository setting the policy of how data should look like when depositing.

More consistent support needed on the side of researchers. But currently they don't get any support and change in practices must be encouraged and followed up. There is need for

data managers/stewards and sound data policy in their institution to shift their data standards towards FAIR.

The internal structuring of the datasets (for example: format, vocabulary, standards and other elements) is impossible to manage at the level of the repository. The repository handles the metadata description and the standardization according to the data model adopted. Data stewards should be the people closer to the researchers to fill this gap in FAIRification of data.

There has been a publication on good practice by the European community in archaeology. There are some good practices published around but it is not clear, from the repository's perspective to which extent they are executed.

Artifacts are consuming space and if there is no good order in the cataloguing of archaeological fieldwork archives, this is reflected negatively in the data. This is an additional layer of complexity for archaeological data compared to data managed in other disciplines, particularly on natural sciences.

When reflecting on the concept of trustworthiness, the first requirement to be considered is sustainability. Repositories should be sustainable financially, technically, and concerning acquisition and retention of competences of people managing them. Trustworthiness also lies on the mission of the repository. Overall, another key element of trustworthiness is acceptance by the community of the data management policy implemented. There should be some accepted agreement on mission and aims of the repository reflected in the data policy.

Concerning certification there are two main issues: in Czech Republic there is almost no certified repository. This makes it difficult to work with the terms of certification. The certification is not directly supported and even questionable as the certification process assesses more your technical capabilities than acceptance by users. Researchers are keener to deposit when the process is made easy. This is to be considered even more when researchers are guided/mandated to use specific repositories. Generally, solutions involving payment for storage are excluded. Standards for reuse of data are an important factor too in the choice of depositing data in a repository.

Growth of size of the repository so far not much affecting costs, as still in TB scale. The digitisation of the archives has not generated an impact on operational costs so far, but increasing adoption of high resolution/3D imaging, the situation can change this. Some steps are being done for alignment to the EOSC and possibilities for capacity sharing.

The AMCR is not collecting secondary data from projects, just from fieldwork and other archaeological activities that have mandatory rules concerning depositing of data. But data from projects should also be collected and stored in FAIR compliant repositories.

Overall, there is a clear need for specific education/training in data management/data stewardship and in developing communities of users adopting data practices FAIR

compliant, as they are not yet ready for it. Individual archaeological institutions lack the resources and systematic support for these activities.

Assessment:

This data repository was established with a clear political and legal mandate to collect, curate and preserve archaeological data of the Czech Republic.

Notwithstanding the gaps in legislation concerning digital data and the problems related to linking the data to cataloguing of the artifacts, there is increasing alignment and awareness of the FAIR principles. However, it is paramount to train researchers in digital skills and data management practices, and to include in the picture the roles of data stewards closer to the researchers (particularly the more reluctant older ones) in charge of supporting implementation of open science practices and FAIR principles to increase FAIRification of datasets since the early stage of the research work.

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ANNEX 4. CASE STUDY: BICOCCA OPEN ARCHIVE RESEARCH DATA (BOARD)

Description:

The BOARD (Bicocca Open Archive Research Data) is the institutional and multi-disciplinary data repository of the University of Milano-Bicocca. BOARD became operational in 2020 and it is open and free-to-use for the members of the institutions and enable them to make their research data publicly available. By depositing their research data in BOARD researchers can make their research data citable, share their data privately or publicly, ensure long-term storage for their data, keep access to all versions and link their article to their data.

The repository builds on the Digital Commons Data platform by Elsevier. This allows the board to offer a comprehensive set of useful services for effective data management as well as APIs and authentication service based on Mendeley OAuth 2.0 authorization. The BOARD supports a wide range of preferred and acceptable formats, for each file type

Summary of survey results:

The board is an institutional research data repository with general-purpose, so not focused on a specific field of science. BOARD is registered in Italy, but open globally and it does not target specific regions/countries. Data is stored only in EU countries. Services offered by BOARD include:

- Data storage
- Cataloguing and searching via metadata
- Content based searching (i.e. of the values in the data)
- Creation of persistent identifiers (PIDs) (e.g. DOI, ORCHID ID)
- Value added services providing information on the repository
- Value added services providing information on the stored data records
- Value added services providing instructions for use and dissemination
- Value added services helping with compliance towards data reporting standards and/or metadata
- Policy or license based access control

All the services offered listed above are outsourced.

The repository is funded by UniMIB, the host institution curating the repository (i.e. direct or indirect support from the host institution) and it has been existing for about 2 years in its current form.

BOARD currently has adequate funding to address technical data and metadata quality managed through a clear system of governance and sufficient qualified staff to address technical data and metadata quality managed through a clear system of governance.

The repository has a continuity plan to ensure ongoing (mid- and long-term) access to and preservation of its holdings and it has an explicit mission to provide access to and preserve data in its domain.

The repository adopts mechanism(s) to secure ongoing expert guidance and feedback (either in-house, or external, including scientific guidance, if relevant) and it offers explicit information online about their policies, which define their services (e.g. acquisition, access, security of content, long-term sustainability of service including funding etc.)

The approximate volume is between 100 TB – up to 1 Petabyte (PB) with a current number of about 1800 datasets.

In terms of data curation, the repositories offer different levels of service including:

- Basic curation – e.g. brief checking, addition of basic metadata or documentation
- Enhanced curation – e.g. conversion to new formats, enhancement of documentation

- Data-level curation – enhanced curation, but with additional editing of deposited data for accuracy
- All the data is preserved for the lifetime of the repository

At present, BOARD has no certification under any cybersecurity standard like ISO/IEC, ETSI GS ISI or others. The operational costs/year are of about 50K€ and in the last 12 months the breakdown was of 25% for personnel related costs and 75% for costs of maintenance and development of systems.

Conditions set for data deposited requires:

- Use of data standards
- Use of metadata
- Use of persistent identifiers (PIDs) (e.g. DOI, ORCID ID)
- Use of licence defining data accessibility
- No personal data

The license scheme used for as a basis for standard terms and conditions is Creative Commons.

Licenses accepted are the ones listed below:

- CC0 (no rights reserved)
- CC BY (attribution to the author required)
- CC BY-NC (attribution to the author required, only for non-commercial use)

There is no policy in place to deal with consequences if non-compliance with licensing terms is detected (e.g. sanctions on current or future access/use of data)

The repository ensures, to the extent possible, that data are created, curated, accessed, and used in compliance with disciplinary and ethical norms. BOARD maintains all applicable licenses covering data access and use and monitors compliance and it guarantees the integrity and authenticity of the data and accepts data and metadata based on defined criteria to ensure relevance as well as understandability for data users.

The repository enables reuse of the data over time, ensuring that appropriate metadata are available to support the understanding and use of the data. It also ensures that metadata are machine-actionable and standardized (e.g. Dublin Core, Data Cite etc.).

Users are enabled to discover the data and refer to them in a persistent way through proper citation (assign persistent unique identifiers to contents, e.g. DOIs, handles, etc.)

The repository makes its services and holdings visible to aggregators services and applies documented processes and procedures in managing archival storage of the data.

Archiving takes place according to defined workflows from ingest to dissemination.

The repository functions on well-supported operating systems and other core infrastructural software, while use of hardware and software technologies is appropriate to the services to be provided to the designated community. The technical infrastructure of the repository provides for protection of the facility and its data, products, services, and users.

Types of government or international organisations' policies the repository must comply with:

- Personal data protection policies (e.g. GDPR)
- Copyright related policies
- Security related policies (e.g. related to encryption, hashes, logs, breach)
- Responsible management of research data in line with the FAIR principles
- Open Science policy recommendations

Key findings from interviews:

In 2019 the UniMiB adopted a open science policy based on open access, open data and open infrastructure. This policy stresses importance to have data as open as possible. Promoting publication of data openly in alignment with international good practice. Constant monitoring of policy issued by the EC and initiatives like EOSC. BOARD is registered in r3data and other listing of international data repositories. It's a data management system helping users to manage research data effectively. The repository started in 2020, and it is based on the Digital Commons Data product by Elsevier.

There is an Open science team in the university dedicated to BOARD. Lots of new features were developed and offered to users in the last few months.

Thanks to FAIR principles, the process of publication has become much more transparent. Use of licenses make clearer to users what they can or can't do with specific datasets. FAIR principles helped researchers providing some structure in the way they deal with research data.

Sometime researchers make some confusion between FAIR and open data. Many options are available to set levels of embargo on use of the data deposited to restrain access from some categories and/or for specific period. FAIR data is becoming the standard rather than exception. The institution is constantly promoting FAIR principles in data management. Focus and share of good practices.

Only recently, as open access and open science principles are becoming established also in national policies, funding in support for FAIRification has started being considered. Open access is now regarded as a key metric in the multi-annual planning for Italian research. Not yet so for FAIR data or open data. The university invested in hiring a data curator/steward and in open science activities.

There is still no incentive for adherence to the FAIR principles, and no clear position on Open Science and FAIR science. However, depositing and publishing research data ahead of the publication of the article is becoming common practice and a metric in progress

Today there is a trustworthy and centralised institutional data repository. Before they were either not published or in domain repositories. This implementation allows the institution to monitor and better exploit data produced by research done in the institution. Data are transmittable via JSON format.

BOARD offers support for the preparation and implementation of DMP for international projects. Guidelines are provided to researchers on how to manage data according to FAIR principles and overall support is offered, including on copyright matters, licensing, etc. A series of webinar is held to explain FAIR principles and good practices to make data FAIR. Core users are internal users, but the system can host external users, particularly from collaborative projects.

UniBM would like to spread FAIR culture among researchers and PhD so that data management is planned at the beginning of the research work. There is willingness to assign a persistent identifier to each dataset and domain specific requirements, integrating other taxonomies of key FOS as well as willingness to become data providers for EOSC, though the procedure and timing to become a provider via the EOSC Portal has not been very clear to BOARD so far. Sometimes in the EOSC context is not very clear how to use/approach existing initiatives and becoming part of it (eg. Becoming data providers for EOSC). Maybe some paths should be defined to find the right response from EOSC.

A PID is assigned as soon as a research object/dataset is created. Standard metadata sets are provided by the supplier and adding specific metadata and there is use of standards vocabularies. The platform is interoperable with large metadata harvester like Open Aire, data cite. BOARD gives the opportunity of using 16 different types of licenses for both data and software. References supported for each research object. The platform ensures long-term data preservation, and data archiving service in collaboration with DANS for redundancy.

Looking at the security aspects for the data deposited, there are procedures in place to ensure no event of data loss and /or data breach happens. Interoperability with other platforms is ensured as well as long-term data preservation/sustainability. Users can directly upload data and the BOARD platform is able to harvest resources from other repositories. BOARD applied to obtain the CoreTrustSeal certification.

The expected growth in the next 12 months, as open science practices are becoming the default mode of doing research now. Costs so far are fully paid by the University. Maybe in the future, there will be the possibility to have other sources of funding if the repository expands.

Assessment:

BOARD highlights a valuable example of a general-purpose repository established at the university level to implement open science practices and long-term preservation of research data generated within the institution. While the adoption of a comprehensive solution like the Digital Commons enabled to rapidly offer a wide range of services enabling alignment with FAIR principles, it makes the repository dependent on the architecture of this product with a degree of uncertainty from a long-term perspective. However, the redundancy ensured by parallel storage in DANS increases the level of reliability and trustworthiness. BOARD shows a sound willingness to be active as a data provider for the EOSC platform and to pursue certification with Core Trust Seals. It offers a good level of support to the community also thanks to the initiative of hiring a data steward.

References:

- <https://board.unimib.it/research-data/>
- <https://www.re3data.org/repository/r3d100013433>
- <https://www.elsevier.com/solutions/digital-commons/data>
- <https://catoblepas.oerc.ox.ac.uk/biodbcore-001799/>
- <https://board.unimib.it/research-data/>

ANNEX 5. CASE STUDY: BAVARIAN ARCHIVE FOR SPEECH SIGNALS (BAS)

Description:

The Bavarian Archive for Speech Signals (BAS) is a public institution hosted by the University of Munich founded in 1995 with the aim of making speech resources of contemporary spoken German as well as tools for the processing of digitized speech available to research and speech technology communities. It receives funding from the Bavarian State, the University of Munich and, additionally, externally funded projects.

Speech material is structured in a manner allowing flexible and precise access, with rich annotations, metadata, and linguistic-phonetic evaluation forming an integral part of it. Since June 2013, the BAS has been one of the licensed CLARIN B centres which share the same principles and standards as the BAS to maximize inter-operability in the future throughout Europe.

The BAS Web Services comprises a collection of speech processing tools accessible via web browser, and there is no need to install any software locally. The services have been mainly designed for linguists, phoneticians and speech engineering, but in recent years we found that many more disciplines make use of BAS services, such as computer science,

psychology, computational linguistics, sociology, oral history, music and computer aided language learning.

Specific terms of usage¹ are described for users from academic institutions and from commercial entities.

Summary of survey results:

The BAS is a public research data repository, discipline specific at the crossroad of both Engineering & Technology and Humanities fields. Data hosted comes from different subdisciplines such as Electrical engineering, electronic engineering, information engineering, History and archaeology, Languages and literature. The repository is registered in Germany, with data stored only in EU countries, and it is open globally.

The services offered by the BAS include:

- Data storage,
- Cataloguing and searching via metadata,
- Content based searching (i.e. of the values in the data),
- Creation of persistent identifiers (PIDs) (e.g. DOI, ORCID ID),
- Value added services providing information on the repository,
- Value added services providing information on the stored data records,
- Value added services providing instructions for use and dissemination,
- Value added services helping with compliance towards data reporting standards and/or metadata,
- Policy or license based access control.

It also offers AAI as an outsourced service (via the DFN) and uses Shibboleth access for academic users.

The BAS has existed for over 20 years and it is funded mainly by the host institution curating the repository. Other minor sources of funding are depositing fees (i.e. in the form of annual contracts with depositing institutions or per-deposit fees), access charges (i.e. charging for access to standard data) and projects.

The repository has a continuity plan to ensure ongoing (mid- and long-term) access to and preservation of its holdings and it currently has adequate funding to address technical data and metadata quality managed through a clear system of governance.

The BAS repository has sufficient qualified staff to address technical data and metadata quality managed through a clear system of governance, as well as an explicit mission to provide access to and preserve data in its domain. Information on cybersecurity certifications were not provided.

The current size of the BAS repository is between 10 TB and 100 TB and it registered a rate of growth of about 25% in the last 3 years for both data volume and number of datasets.

The repository offer enhanced data curation including, for example, conversion to new formats, and enhancement of documentation.

The costs to operate the BAS repository amount to about 200K€ per year, with salaries of staff, maintenance and development of systems, preservation and storage as main cost categories. A specific breakdown of these costs in percentage was not provided.

The minimum duration of data preservation guaranteed to researchers is 10 years but, generally, data deposited is preserved for the lifetime of the repository.

The conditions set for data depositing include:

- Use of data standards
- Use of metadata
- Use of licence defining data accessibility

The BAS repository accepts any available license as a basis for standard terms and conditions for data access but there is no policy in place to deal with consequences if non-compliance with licensing terms is detected.

The repository ensures, to the extent possible, that data are created, curated, accessed, and used in compliance with disciplinary and ethical norms, and it guarantees the integrity and authenticity of the data. BAS repository accepts data and metadata based on defined criteria to ensure relevance and understandability for data users. Reuse of the data is enabled over time, by ensuring that appropriate metadata are available to support the understanding and use of the data. The repository also ensures that metadata is machine-actionable and standardized (e.g. Dublin Core, Data Cite etc.)

The BAS enables users to discover the data and refer to them in a persistent way through proper citation (via the assignment of persistent unique identifiers to contents, e.g. DOIs, handles, etc.) and it makes its services and holdings visible to aggregators services.

The BAS repository applies documented processes and procedures in managing archival storage of the data. Archiving takes place according to defined workflows from ingest to dissemination. The repository functions on well-supported operating systems and other core infrastructural software and it is using hardware and software technologies appropriate to the services it provides to its Designated Community. The technical infrastructure of the repository provides for protection of the facility and its data, products, services, and users

Personal data protection policies (e.g. GDPR) and responsible management of research data in line with the FAIR principles are the two main international policies implemented by the BAS.

Key findings from interview:

The information below has been gathered via an interview with the manager of the data repository.

The BAS repository implements FAIR principles as this is also required by their status of licensed CLARIN B centre. The transition toward alignment to FAIR data principles took some years starting around 2015, when the concept of FAIR data started being discussed within international for a on research data.

The main barriers in implementing the FAIR principles were due to the cultural approach of owners/copyright holders of the research data that hosted by the BAS. Different actions were undertaken to encourage owners to offer their data for scientific purposes where BAS offers several infrastructural/safety services to these owners, such as PID registration, standardized metadata (DC, OLAC, CMDI), double-secure backups, online access via Shibboleth and other services.

Specific funding has been allocated for the BAS by its host institution, LMU Munich, which supports the operations of the repository by covering two permanent job positions, and partly by providing physical infrastructures (network, cooling for servers etc.)

There haven't been instead, targeted incentives for researchers, apart from general encouragement in adopting open science and data sharing practices.

Until 15 years ago most of BAS research data was distributed only for royalties to be paid to the owner; now, most of its resources are freely accessible for researchers that are members of an Europeana university (including students).

To increase data FAIRness before time of depositing researchers gets some support from BAS for example with the creation of (CMDI) metadata sets, particularly in the phase of planning projects generating data.

FAIRification effort invested by the repository depends very much on the type of data and the category of interested users. One typical FAIRification task on the repository may be the creation of standardized metadata that can be harvested by search engines or science indices as this can be a simple but effective way to make data available for scientists without registration and Shibboleth access.

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FAIRness of data before depositing could be improved by supporting creators of datasets with specific funding to record and deposit data with format and structure enabling wider sharing among scientists.

Trustworthiness is very linked to the independence of the repository (not focusing on commercial purpose), long-term funding and/or a robust exit plan with backup organizations for data redundancy. It is crucial to fund independent supervision (eg. an advisory board) for the governance of data repositories. Concerning available certification schemes, Core Trust Seal (CTS) seems to cover most aspects that BAS deem important, but it is too generic. CLARIN Centre Certification builds on CTS but adds some important specific requirements for speech and language data. As often happens in other disciplines, the effectiveness of certification depends on how the certificate considers the special nature of the scientific data addressed.

Assessment:

Overall, the BAS repository relies on sufficient funding to be operational and to ensure the level of FAIR compliance required by the community of reference, with the recognition of being a Clarin-B centre. There is a clear awareness of the need to improve FAIRification of data before point of deposit and ideas on options to encourage good practices to increase open datasets and make them findable for non-registered users by curating the quality of metadata. An increase in support for researchers is considered a key point to be addressed in the immediate future.

References:

- <https://www.re3data.org/repository/r3d100010381>
- <https://clarin.phonetik.uni-muenchen.de/BASWebServices/help/tutorial>
- <https://www.bas.uni-muenchen.de/Bas/BasBaseng.html>
- <http://hdl.handle.net/11858/00-1779-0000-0028-421B-4>

ANNEX 6. CASE STUDY: CLARIN. SI

Description:

The Common Language Resources and Technology Infrastructure (CLARIN) is a research infrastructure that was launched with the idea that all digital language resources and tools from all over Europe and beyond are accessible via single sign-on online environment to support researchers in the field of humanities and social sciences. The CLARIN Infrastructure is fully operational in many countries and offers, for example, certified repositories for long term accessibility of language resources. CLARIN.SI is the Slovenian node of the infrastructure with the aim to help research communities with language resources and technologies, as well as to provide expertise and knowledge transfer. Its aim

is to enhance the interdisciplinary collaboration as to expand the scope of technological solutions for language studies, focusing on the Slovenian and other South-Slavic languages.

Summary of survey results :

The repository is domain-specific with focus on Humanities and Social Sciences, as well as natural language processing.

The repository is open globally, does not target specific regions/countries and does not outsource any of its services and it receives funding in a structured and stable way from the national government. The uploaded data is not deleted after a specific period – all data is preserved for the lifetime of the repository.

Data licences are chosen from a list of available licenses (including CC licneces, GPL,etc.) in the process of deposit. The approximate yearly costs associated with running the data repository are 40.000 euros and the overall costs for the last year were distributed to cover staff costs and costs of maintenance and development of systems.

The repository complies with the following policies:

- Personal data protection policies (e.g. GDPR)
- Copyright related policies
- Security related policies (e.g. related to encryption, hashes, logs, breach)
- Responsible management of research data in line with the FAIR principles
- Sovereignty related policies (e.g. related to views, downloads, other sharing and access limitations, logging, requests for access) international policies

The approximate number of items, each one including a variable number of files, available for users is 400, and the rate growth for the last 3 years was between 50% and up to 100%.

The conditions set for data deposited are the following:

- Use of metadata
- Use of data standards
- Use of persistent identifiers (PIDs)
- Use of license defining data accessibility

Key findings from interview:

CLARIN.SI is based at the Jožef Stefan Institute, which is the largest Natural Science research institute in Slovenia. Language resources for Slovenia serving computational linguists, language researchers and for machine learning. Clarin is an ESFRI infrastructure, organised around a leading ERIC based in The Netherlands, and it aims at making language data accessible to researchers in languages and humanities in genera.

Operations for the Slovenian node started in 2014 and the node serves about 90% of institutions working with language data in Slovenia. The software is based on DSpace used also by other Clarin national members to ensure interoperability. CLARIN SI is committed to follow FAIR principles and other aligned with good practices of other repositories on language data. Self-archiving functionalities, but also editorial procedures are in place as well as guidelines for the creation of metadata and acceptable data format, FAQs, and documentation, both in Slovenian and English. There are about 350 registered users, but many datasets are available for download without logging (CC license) and the number of downloads is measured for statistical purposes. Options to set embargo period are supported (metadata visible and public but you can't download the data) and restricted access to registered users by use of specific licenses.

Basis for guidelines come from CLARIN with some recommendations implemented even before they were considered by the Slovenian government. CLARIN guidelines are very technical, mostly addressing computer scientists. Some guidelines are devoted to researchers in humanities with low level of technical IT competences.

Before being part of CLARIN the institution had some language resources dated to the 90s, and data made available in old ways, through file transfers. After becoming part of CLARIN adoption of specific software and some FAIR principles were already implemented by CLARIN so adaptation was not difficult. In the repository there are items with their own metadata: every item has PIDs. RDA nodes Slovenia project, to disseminate practices for journals on how to cite resources from repository.

Among many researchers in humanities and linguistics there is still some reluctance in sharing data. Making the data public requires more work in labelling, documenting, describing, etc. Humanities researchers and linguists always worry about mistakes and this increase reluctance to release data.

Researchers used to keep research/data/results in their own storage devices. Now there is legal basis and regulation on data sharing, so a new approach has become mandatory with a shift from voluntary principles to obligation. The initial regulatory framework came from EU level then translated in national laws. All these initiatives, including EOSC, were very important factors leading to this new framework in member states. There were resistances when promoting these principles and practices to wider audience in Slovenia, but the situation is improving also due to explaining benefits of this and why these provisions are in place. Young generation adheres to these practices and rules more naturally and easily. Important how these motivations are promoted and mentored in universities and among policymakers.

For a repository to be considered trustworthy easiness of use, in parallel with security and long-term availability of storage, is paramount for researchers. The output format is sometimes too old to be deposited and it must be processed before depositing.

On the one hand, trust is related to technical standards, processes in place, and user expectations in terms of protocols, equipment, etc. On the other hand, it is paramount to assure sustainability in the long term. Here the role of the gov is very important. In this strategic thinking on RIs it is important to have these exercises of preparing strategies and roadmaps for a 10-year period, so going beyond a regular term of government. This helps in having political support from all parties with a long-term oriented outlook. Availability and operational 24/7, long term availability of data, framework in place preventing data breach and data loses and sustainable funding are all key elements determining trustworthiness of a data repository. CLARIN network ensuring availability of data in the long term. Ensuring complete and curate metadata is another factor for trustworthiness as well as overall data quality.

Currently researchers are provided with training in FAIR principles, regarding their area of research. There is a new legal framework on public funding for research, as researchers are now required to make data open under new projects funded. For older ones, only a partial percentage of data is open, also because the costs were not covered to do so. What is needed is to improve the understanding of what the research data is, there is still more focus on finalising the product, not the data. And this is main hinderance in considering FAIRness earlier in the research and in view of deposit.

At national level, a long pilot period is in place to make people make their data and publications open. Now in Slovenia there is alignment to open science policies of the EC. Costs for opening/sharing data are eligible costs also for Slovenian funded projects. There are tutorials/workshops for PhD students on how to make data open, FAIR and so on but more on general policy indications, but more is to be done particularly to train students on how to implement good practices and material available more in EN and little in Slovenian.

CESSDA doing something, yet more focused on social sciences. In future calls for research projects adherence to open science practices, open data, DMPs, is required, in alignment with rules of EU projects.

In relation to past practices, the situation has improved in comparison to 5-7 years ago, also because of the work of the repository and the community. Learning through trying, when depositing data in the repository. The main challenges in transition are the cultural barriers in researchers after 50 on open science, but younger generation feels differently, so it is crucial to show them what benefits of Open Science/Open Data are there for them too.

CLARIN is a relatively small infrastructure and there is not enough HR to provide tutorials and support to researchers to follow FAIR principles. Occasionally, short introductions to CLARIN RI for students have been organised in some faculties, but more effort is needed for this activity.

If a researcher has data that is not a good fit for depositing, there are small grants (mini projects) available and help to restructure the data. When rejecting data there is

explanation of what is not done properly and how things should be corrected. Additionally, there isn't enough support to enable different AAI protocols and, with technology changing fast, some legacy systems still used are getting older.

Another main issue is how the data are coded/annotated/formatted. In linguistics data is very complex and inside lot of text. Each text has metadata which can be quite diverse. Linguistic annotations on semantic, morphology and other aspects are complex and there are problems in the way this data is encoded across the community and this hinder interoperability. It's more a problem with this FOS rather than linked to the specific country or repository.

An important message is that FAIR data is not a problem if all the research communities are aware that the public funding and equipment is available to support that. Support to improve quality of data and info for reuse. Community important to set good practices.

The Slovenian government adopted special laws on research and innovation and those have been the basis for the whole strategy in the mid-term. Research and innovation strategy for 10 years adopted in March and included a data policy document (implementation document plus National roadmap for the Research Infrastructures).

There is progress mainly in the sense of formalisation/institutionalisation in related documents. Yet, awareness and practice has been present and increasing in the last years, particularly since Slovenia joined some international RI like Clarin/CESSDA. This facilitated alignment to international principles for data management, thanks to preparatory work in international meetings/workshops and so on. It was somehow parallel work, not even triggered by the international/EU level but spontaneous though favoured by the international context. The question of investment of public money was a key aspect as it was clear that production of this data, from publicly funded research, couldn't be handed to private entities for commercial purposes. This was the main drivers.

There are different pillars concerning funding. For RI projects there is financial support from the government. Membership fees are paid by the government and are not a burden on research institutions. Such EU RI projects are eligible to have funds via the RI programme in the executive agency for research in Slovenia. Also, in preparatory period is possible to have funding for collaborative work in this area. According to the new law mentioned there will be more stable funding for research institutions and participation to large EU projects.

Also, cohesion funds are used when there is the need to upgrade nodes or enhance national RIs (for examples in upgrade of IT equipment/instruments). CLARIN also benefited from structural funds for few years.

For the action plan on Open Data in preparation, there will be calls to financially support the open science initiatives with the Recovery and Resilience Facility (RRF) calls.

It is very important that these community projects/initiatives (like EOCS) have their own calls for these specific objectives. Recovery funds from the EU could also be used for

implementation of the action plan. Mandatory provisions on DMP and data opening for national calls.

No more is needed at this stage from EU level, but national investment must be encouraged and incentivised.

Sometimes the EU tier look a bit complex. Difficult for smaller countries to follow all the streams of work (EOSC, HPC, RIs initiatives, and so on, crossing with HE Missions, KICs, etc.) and track who is responsible for what, how to approach that layer. In small countries, a single officer follows many projects/initiatives, but it can be overwhelming compared to other countries where they have teams more numerous and with specialised expertise in ministries., so sometimes it's easier to track projects than high-level discussions ongoing at EU level.

There have been lots of initiatives and is already challenging for national administrations to keep pace effectively.

For Slovenian institutions, it is very attractive to be part of these international RIs, so that high level standards and competences/know how/requirements are transferred to national level.

Regular dialogues within different bodies also on these strategic aspects. Keep into account effort allocated by smaller countries, help them being able to keep pace and play the game (ensure level playing field for small countries or newer EU members to participate to strategic steering).

Assessment:

CLARIN SI is very well aligned with FAIR data implementation and with recommendation set among international communities working on language data and it is committed to increase awareness on FAIR data and good practices of data sharing and data management within the Slovenian national context.

European Research Data Landscape study looks at researchers practices in data production, reuse, depositing, making it FAIR, as well as the research data repository landscape. During the study two surveys were carried out, one of researchers (over 15,000 responses) and one of research data repositories (over 300 responses), alongside case studies and an automated assessment of research dataset FAIRness using F-UJI tool. The findings show that while certain FAIR practices are being picked up and researchers are motivated by open science ideals, there still are obstacles to making data FAIR, such as limited local support, actual FAIR practice, awareness, and monitoring of progress at different levels. Based on the findings, the study proposes a number of recommendations and possible actions that could help make European researchers practices FAIRer and research data repository more FAIR-ready.